

Deliverable 4.1
AI toolkit, Architecture and Knowledge Graph – first version

**WP 4 – Develop AI Toolkit,
Architecture and Knowledge Graph to
support Deliberative Processes**

**T4.1 and T4.2 – Develop AI toolkit,
Architecture, and Knowledge Graph –
first and second sprints**

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<p>Abstract: This deliverable (D4.1) reports on the technical infrastructure of AI4Deliberation, including the identification and sandboxing of open-source AI tools and models, the first version of the Deliberation Knowledge Graph semantic model, and the first release of a reusable, modular reference architecture developed through design science, agile, and ethics-by-design methods. Building on the first pilot evaluation (WP5), the report outlines ongoing T4.2 work to refine and (if needed) fine-tune and re-evaluate models, provide concrete AI services for pilots (e.g., deliberation summarisation and gamification), and deploy and populate a FAIR Deliberation Knowledge Graph hosted in an open-source graph database, alongside a second version of the reference architecture aligned with WP2 and WP3.</p>	
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Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.1 (“AI Toolkit, Architecture and Knowledge Graph – first version”) consolidates the first two WP4 sprints (T4.1 and T4.2) and reports the technical foundations that enable AI4Deliberation’s AI-assisted, multimodal and gamified deliberations. In line with the Grant Agreement, it documents: (i) the WP4 AI toolkit and sandbox used to identify, evaluate and operationalise open-source AI tools and models (including LLMs and multimodal/video-capable models) as deliberation services, (ii) the first operational design of the Deliberation Knowledge Graph (DKG), including semantic modelling and a FAIR-oriented implementation approach, and (iii) the first and refined versions of the Reference Architecture, which ties platforms, services, models, and the Knowledge Graph into a reusable and modular blueprint.

WP4’s implementation follows an agile, ethics-by-design methodology organised in four sprints, with D4.1 covering the first two. Sprint 1 established the baseline: a sandbox for controlled experimentation, a prompt-engineering test suite for model assessment, the initial semantic model for the DKG, and Architecture v1. Sprint 2 then refined these outputs based on the first pilot evaluation cycle, strengthening model/tool choices, introducing improvements and (where justified) fine-tuning/explainability measures, deploying a first operational Knowledge Graph approach, and updating the architecture to v2. Across the full WP4 lifecycle—tool scouting, down-selection, sandbox experimentation, evaluation and integration—the consortium applies the ALTAI framework as a shared operational reference for the EU’s Trustworthy AI requirements, ensuring that safeguards (e.g., human oversight, robustness and safety, privacy/data governance, transparency, fairness, societal well-being, accountability) are embedded as part of routine technical decision-making rather than treated as an afterthought.

A core output of T4.1–T4.2 is the WP4 sandbox: the project’s execution environment for experimenting with, comparing and packaging deliberation-oriented AI capabilities before citizen-facing deployment. The sandbox enables controlled and repeatable testing across pilots and languages, supports evidence-driven refinement (by linking evaluation findings to concrete technical updates), and acts as the common integration layer that exposes AI functionality as reusable services via APIs—so that different deliberation platforms can “plug in” the same capabilities without having to build separate AI stacks. This approach is intentionally modular: tools can be replaced or upgraded across sprints, while stable interfaces support pilot integration planning and reduce platform lock-in risks.

D4.1 also reports the first “working design” of the Deliberation Knowledge Graph as a structured, reusable representation of deliberation content. The DKG is implemented through a dual-layer semantic model (ontological blueprint + FAIR data governance) and adopts IBIS as a core logical grammar to represent issues, positions and arguments (pro/con) in a traceable way. Building on this, the Knowledge Graph layer is complemented by a Multi-Agent RAG (“Cognitive Retrieval”) mechanism that translates natural-language questions into validated SPARQL queries, enforces safety and compliance checks, and returns evidence-based responses that remain anchored in the deliberation structure—supporting transparency, traceability and secure access to deliberation knowledge for both technical and non-technical stakeholders.

Finally, D4.1 presents the evolution of the Reference Architecture from the Technical Annex vision to an implementation-facing blueprint. Architecture v1 operationalised the end-to-end

workflow (data sources → preprocessing → sandbox services via unified APIs → outputs/insights → user interfaces) and clarified how compliance is enforced in practice. Architecture v2 further strengthens deployability and governance by organising the system into distinct layers (Interaction, Data Preprocessing, Intelligence, and an enveloping Compliance layer), making platform integration targets explicit (including the mobile app trajectory), formalising preprocessing “readiness gates” (including privacy-by-design anonymisation), and embedding compliance as an end-to-end property aligned with GDPR, AI Act considerations and FAIR principles. This refined architecture also makes the “virtuous cycle” explicit: toolkit services generate structured outputs that populate the Knowledge Graph, while the Knowledge Graph provides governed, traceable context that improves the robustness and reuse of toolkit services.

In terms of pilot uptake, D4.1 documents concrete integration patterns that will be exercised and validated further in subsequent sprints, including API-based integration into a Consul instance for the German pilot and plugin-driven integration via a WordPress host for the Greek pilot (connecting WP4 tools, topic modelling and Knowledge Graph components into pilot workflows). These integration approaches are deliberately lightweight and incremental, allowing Sprint 1 tools to be re-tested under Sprint 2 refinements and progressively embedded into platform workflows as the toolkit matures. In parallel, WP4 tracks progress against the Grant Agreement KPIs: foundations for the toolkit/sandbox and Reference Architecture are already in place, several core AI functionalities have been implemented and evaluated, while scale-dependent targets (e.g., Knowledge Graph volume, mobile app maturity, broader platform uptake) are explicitly scheduled for consolidation in the next sprints as integration depth and pilot data increase.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
ADU	Argumentative Discourse Unit
AGPL	Affero General Public License
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI Act	EU Artificial Intelligence Act
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AS-IS	Current (existing) state of a pilot/process before changes
ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BART	Bidirectional and Auto-Regressive Transformers (summarisation model)
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
BSL	Business Source License
BSN	Burgerservicenummer (Dutch citizen service number)
CPSV-AP	Core Public Service Vocabulary Application Profile
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile
DCTERMS	Dublin Core Metadata Terms
(D)KG	(Deliberation) Knowledge Graph
DOI	Digital Object Identifier

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (data principles)
FOAF	Friend of a Friend (Ontology)
GA	Grant Agreement
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
HMAC	Hash-based Message Authentication Code
IBAN	International Bank Account Number
IBIS	Issue-Based Information System (argumentation framework)
ID	Identifier
I/O	Input/Output
IP	Internet Protocol (used in personal data definition)
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation (data format)
JWT	JSON Web Token
KPI / KPIs	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LLM	Large Language Model
LMS	Learning Management System

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
LSA	Latent Semantic Analysis
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NPI	Personal data category label in moderation taxonomy
OS	Operating System
PDF	Portable Document Format
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
RDF	Resource Description Framework
POS	Part of Speech
PROV-O	Provenance Ontology
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
REGEX	Regular Expression (pattern matching)
REST	Representational State Transfer (API style)
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback
ROUGE	Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation
SEAB	Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board
SIOC	Semantically-Interlinked Online Communities
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSD	Solid State Drive
SSE	Server-Sent Events
TO-BE	Target (intended) state of a pilot/process after changes
UI	User Interface

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
Vid-LLM / Vid-LLMs	Video Large Language Model(s)
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package
xAIF	eXtended Argument Interchange Format (argument graph interchange format)

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Partners List Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
UNIS	UNI SYSTEMS SYSTMATA PLIROFORIKIS MONOPROSOPI ANONYMI EMPORIKI ETAIRIA - UNI SYSTEMS INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SYSTEMS COMMERCIAL S.M.S.A.
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT - TU Delft
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS CERTH
UBAM	OTTO-FRIEDRICH-UNIVERSITAET BAMBERG - UNI BA
KT	KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED - Konnekt-able Technologies
UNIVDUN	UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE - UNIVDUN
IK	INSTITUT ZA KRIMINOLOGIJO PRI PRAVNI FAKULTETI V LJUBLJANI - INSTITUTE OF CRIMINOLOGY AT THE FACULTY OF LAW LJUBLJANA
DEMB	DEMBRANE BV - BRANE
TG	THOUGHTGRAPH LTD - TG
GFOSS	ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA - GFOSS
AAIT	ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS - ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS
CBAM	Stadt Bamberg - Stadt Bamberg
UZH	UNIVERSITY OF ZÜRICH

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of D4.1

Deliverable D4.1 “AI Toolkit, Architecture and Knowledge Graph – first version” documents the first consolidated WP4 results that establish AI4Deliberation’s technical foundation for AI-assisted, multimodal and gamified digital deliberations, and provides an implementation-ready baseline that can be adopted and assessed in the pilots.

In line with the Grant Agreement, D4.1 reports on WP4’s technical infrastructure and the first versions of its core assets: (a) the AI toolkit and sandbox used to identify and test open-source AI tools and models (including LLMs and multimodal LLMs) for deliberation tasks and gamification experimentation, (b) the Deliberation Knowledge Graph work (semantic modelling and the transition towards a FAIR, open-source graph database setup), and (c) the Reference Architecture that ties together platforms, services, models, and the Knowledge Graph into a reusable and modular design.

Finally, D4.1 captures the feedback loop with WP5 that drives the shift from Sprint 1 outputs to second-sprint refinements: it summarises how the first pilot evaluation results inform model suitability and fine-tuning needs, the adoption of explainability/transparency/trustworthiness techniques, and the evolution towards a concrete set of AI services for pilots (e.g., deliberation summarisation), together with the corresponding update of the architecture (v2) and Knowledge Graph implementation approach.

1.2. WP4 Summary

WP4 Develop AI Toolkit, Architecture and Knowledge Graph to support Deliberative Processes (M7–M33, Lead: KT) develops the project’s core technical foundation: an **AI toolkit**, a **reusable and modular Reference Architecture**, and a **Deliberation Knowledge Graph** to support AI-enabled deliberative processes. In the Grant Agreement, WP4 is framed as the work package that delivers the technical infrastructure for AI-assisted deliberation, including the identification and testing of open-source AI models (LLMs and multimodal LLMs), the development of a Knowledge Graph with high-quality structured deliberation data, and the architecture that enables these capabilities to be integrated into deliberation platforms.

WP4 follows an **agile** approach implemented through **four sprints**. Sprint 1 establishes a **sandbox** for experimentation with existing AI models and a **test suite** for model evaluation, delivers the **semantic model** for the Deliberation Knowledge Graph, and produces the **first version of the Reference Architecture**. Sprint 2 refines these results based on the first pilot evaluation, introducing (where needed) **fine-tuned and explainable models**, deploying a first operational version of the Knowledge Graph, updating the architecture, and providing preliminary AI solutions as services for pilots. To ensure ethical compliance, every tool is evaluated from the perspective of all ALTAI principles.¹

¹ European Commission, “Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) for self-assessment”, last update 11 November 2025, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

From a system perspective, WP4's Reference Architecture comprises: **(i)** deliberation platforms where citizens contribute content (text/video) and which are enhanced with AI features, **(ii)** existing and/or fine-tuned AI models used within the sandbox, **(iii)** the Deliberation Knowledge Graph, **(iv)** cross-cutting components safeguarding **transparency, trustworthiness, explainability, security and privacy**, and **(v)** the sandbox exposing AI features as **services (APIs)** for integration. In parallel, the Knowledge Graph is designed to follow **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) principles** and to be implemented using open-source graph databases, populated primarily with pilot deliberation data to support deliberation services and, where relevant, model enhancement.

1.3. WP4 Objectives

WP4 develops the project's technical backbone by delivering an AI toolkit, a reference architecture, and a deliberation knowledge graph to support AI-enhanced deliberative processes. Within the Grant Agreement, WP4 is guided by four objectives that structure the work and frame the scope of this deliverable:

- **O4.1 – Identify and assess open-source AI tools and models (incl. LLMs and multimodal LLMs).**
WP4 identifies relevant open-source AI tools and models and tests them to determine whether—and to what extent—they can support deliberation activities. Where existing solutions are not adequate, WP4 considers fine-tuning existing models or training new ones.
- **O4.2 – Design a reusable and modular Reference Architecture for AI deliberations.**
WP4 designs a reference architecture that supports the integration and reuse of AI capabilities across deliberation settings and pilots, enabling a modular approach to deployment and evolution across project sprints.
- **O4.3 – Develop a Deliberation Knowledge Graph.**
WP4 develops a Deliberation Knowledge Graph to structure and interlink deliberation data and support the project's AI-enabled functionality, including the progression towards a FAIR-oriented implementation approach.
- **O4.4 – Enhance an open-source deliberation platform with multimodal AI and gamification, and develop a mobile app.**
WP4 contributes to enhancing an open-source deliberation platform by integrating multimodal AI features and gamification elements, and supports the development trajectory towards a mobile app for citizen-facing interaction.

1.4. Tasks covered in D4.1

D4.1 ("AI Toolkit, Architecture and Knowledge Graph – first version", due in Month 18) reports the WP4 technical results that focus on the technical infrastructure, the available open-source AI tools and models, the Deliberation Knowledge Graph, genAI tools for citizens, and analytical tools for administrators.

In terms of WP4 implementation, D4.1 consolidates work from the first two WP4 tasks/sprints:

T4.1 – Develop AI Toolkit, Architecture, and Knowledge Graph (first sprint, M7–M12)

This task covers: (1) identification of existing open-source AI tools and models and the setup of a sandbox for experimenting with AI-enhanced deliberation tasks (e.g., argument

extraction) and gamification elements (avatars, skill points, scores), (2) support to pilots for determining infrastructure needs, (3) development of the semantic model for the Deliberation Knowledge Graph, and (4) evaluation of AI models using a prompt engineering test suite to assess suitability and whether fine-tuning is required, alongside the assessment of explainability/transparency/trustworthiness and gamification techniques. It also delivers the first version of the Reference Architecture, aligned with T2.2 and T3.1 and feeding the first sprint backlog of pilots.

T4.2 – Develop AI Toolkit, Architecture, and Knowledge Graph (second sprint, M13–M18)

This task refines T4.1 based on the first pilot evaluation (T5.2), including (where needed) fine-tuning of AI models, adoption of explainability/transparency/trustworthiness techniques, and evaluation of the fine-tuned and explainable models. It further delivers a concrete set of AI tools/services for pilots (e.g., deliberation summarisation and gamification techniques) and deploys the FAIR Deliberation Knowledge Graph hosted on an open-source graph database (e.g., Virtuoso, AllegroGraph, Neo4j), populated primarily with data from pilot operation. It also provides the second version of the Reference Architecture, aligned with T2.3 and T3.2, feeding the second sprint backlog of pilots, and the results up to this point are reported in D4.1.

1.5. Relation to other WPs and alignment points

D4.1 is developed as part of the project’s sprint-based implementation cycle and is tightly coupled with the work produced in other work packages that define *what* should be supported (methods/processes and governance), *how* it should be assessed (pilots and evaluation), and *under which constraints* it should operate (legal/ethics and data management).

- **Alignment with WP1 (Demystify digital deliberations).** WP1 synthesises scientific literature and practice at the intersection of deliberation processes/platforms, AI/LLMs (including video LLMs), argumentation mining, and evaluation models, and elicits stakeholder needs. These outputs provide an evidence base that informs WP4’s initial tool/model scanning and the selection of deliberation-relevant AI capabilities addressed in the sandbox and toolkit.
- **Alignment with WP2 (AI-enabled deliberation methods).** WP2 specifies the deliberation processes and how AI can support them (first and final versions), while also addressing legal and ethics aspects. Based on the Product backlog (Annex B) which was developed under WP1, WP2 used this as a basis to analyse and develop the relevant functionalities for the toolkit. Additionally, WP2 sets the basis for the ethics approach the project needs to follow. WP4 uses these process definitions as functional requirements for the AI toolkit services, the Knowledge Graph semantic model, and the Reference Architecture, ensuring that technical components directly map to the deliberation stages and support needs described in WP2. In particular, D2.1 (WP2 Deliberative Process Guidelines) translates the core normative principles of deliberation—**equality, inclusion, plurality, authenticity, and reflection**—into concrete design interventions across the main stages of a deliberative process (Selection, Pre-Deliberation, Deliberation, Post-Deliberation). It further operationalises predictable scaling tensions and constraints through practical matrices (e.g., the Scaling Deliberation Matrix / AI-Process Matrix and the AI deliberation translation matrix), clarifying how AI, multimodality, and gamification

can support deliberative integrity when processes are large-scale, digital, and institutionally constrained. These WP2 outputs are used in WP4 as design inputs for prioritising toolkit functionalities, shaping evaluation criteria, and informing integration choices and safeguards².

- **Alignment with WP3 (Comprehensive framework).** WP3 delivers the governance- and institutional-context framework for AI-enabled deliberation (first and subsequent iterations). WP4 aligns its technical choices (e.g., modularity of services, roles such as citizens/admins, and deployment assumptions for pilots) with this framework so that the toolkit, Knowledge Graph and architecture can be operationalised consistently across pilot settings. During WP3 co-design activities, stakeholders also highlighted practical design expectations that directly inform WP4 implementation. In a co-creation session organised at the EGOV conference, co-creators emphasised that AI should **not actively intervene** in deliberative exchanges, but should function as a **supportive tool**—with deliberators retaining agency over whether and when to use AI features. They further raised concerns around **nudging and manipulation**, noting that AI-supported structuring of discussions could unintentionally (or strategically) influence opinions; participants therefore stressed the importance of providing **real-time insight** into what the AI tool is doing and why. Finally, co-creators expressed preferences for **bounded inputs**, arguing that AI tools should primarily use content generated within the same deliberative process (including parallel conversations in the same deliberation), rather than drawing on opaque or external sources without clear disclosure—an insight that directly informs how WP4 frames Knowledge Graph provenance and the use of retrieval mechanisms.
- **Alignment with WP5 (Pilots and evaluation) and the sprint feedback loop.** WP5 defines and executes the pilot evaluation cycles and explicitly builds pilot planning on sprint backlogs developed in WP2, WP3 and WP4, while evaluation outcomes feed refinements in subsequent sprints. In this context, D4.1 captures both the first WP4 results and the way the first pilot evaluation informs the ongoing refinements (e.g., suitability of models and implications for fine-tuning, and the evolution of WP4 assets).
- **Project-level alignment points (sprints and deliverables).** According to the Grant Agreement planning, D4.1 is the WP4 “first version” deliverable due in month 18 and is synchronised with other first-version outputs (notably the WP2 and WP3 first-version deliverables), while WP5 deliverables report pilot evaluation results that serve as key inputs for WP4’s refinement trajectory. This sprint structure is also reflected in the project milestones for completing and evaluating successive releases.
- **Links to WP6–WP8.** Later WPs build on WP4 outputs: sustainability/policy recommendations (WP6) and dissemination/exploitation activities (WP7) rely on stable, reusable technical assets, while the Data Management Plan (WP8) provides the broader framework within which data handling and Knowledge Graph population are managed.

² For more information, you can refer to D2.2 – AI-enabled Deliberation Processes – first version

1.6. Document Structure

This deliverable is organised into **seven chapters**, preceded by an **Executive Summary**, and concluding with the Annexes. It presents WP4 work as one coherent flow that consolidates the outcomes of **T4.1** and the ongoing refinements of **T4.2**.

- **Chapter 1 – Introduction** defines the purpose of D4.1, summarises WP4 and its objectives, clarifies the tasks covered in this deliverable, outlines cross-WP alignment, and explains the structure of the document.
- **Chapter 2 – Agile methodology** explains the agile ethics-by-design approach adopted in WP4, including the four-sprint structure and how evaluation and refinements are integrated into the development lifecycle.
- **Chapter 3 – Platforms Introduction** introduces the deliberation platforms targeted for integration (Consul, DebateGraph, dembrane, and Frankly) and explains their role and constraints in AI4Deliberation.
- **Chapter 4 – AI toolkit and sandbox for experimentation** presents the identification, selection and follow-up evaluation of tools/models, the sandbox setup (including infrastructure and the prompt engineering test suite), the first-sprint evaluation results and identified refinements, and the improvements implemented during Sprint 2.
- **Chapter 5 – Deliberation Knowledge Graph** describes the purpose, requirements, data sources and population strategy (including IBIS), and the semantic and FAIR-oriented implementation approach, including the Multi-Agent RAG layer.
- **Chapter 6 – Reference Architecture** presents the architecture (v1 and refined v2), its alignment across WPs, how it relates to the toolkit and Knowledge Graph, and the ethics and methodological compliance considerations, including the integration architecture for APIs and plugins.
- **Chapter 7 – Conclusions and next steps** summarises key accomplishments reported in D4.1 and sets out the next sprints and steps.
- **Annexes** provides supporting material referenced throughout the deliverable (e.g., internal planning artefacts and evaluation instruments).

2. Agile methodology

AI4Deliberation follows an **agile software development methodology** for WP4, implemented through **four sprints**. The rationale is to deliver WP4 outputs as **incremental, testable releases** that can be validated in pilot contexts, refined based on evaluation feedback, and progressively scaled towards the final toolkit and platform integrations, while ensuring that ethical and compliance requirements are embedded from the outset.

2.1. Sprint Structure

The Grant Agreement defines the four-sprint logic and the expected outputs per sprint as follows:

- **Sprint 1** delivers a **sandbox for experimentation** with AI functionality (including existing AI models), a **test suite** to evaluate these models, the **semantic model** for the Deliberation Knowledge Graph, and the **first version of the Reference Architecture**.
- **Sprint 2** delivers an **updated sandbox** (including, where needed, **fine-tuned and explainable AI models**), a **first version of the Knowledge Graph**, an **updated architecture**, and **preliminary AI solutions** ready to be tested in pilot settings.
- **Sprints 3 and 4** converge towards the **final toolkit**, the **final Knowledge Graph**, the **final architecture**, the **platform enhancements**, and the **mobile app**.

Figure 1: Four sprints of WP4 - AI Toolkit Development

This structure ensures that each sprint produces a concrete, reviewable release and that technical work remains aligned with pilot readiness and evaluation cycles.

2.2. Ethics-by-design governance

A defining element of the WP4 methodology is that ethical and compliance considerations are not treated as a final “check”, but as **continuous governance** across the entire development lifecycle. The Grant Agreement states that **all developments will be guided by the Ethics Manager (IK) and the SEAB** to ensure the ethical application of AI approaches. In practice, this means that the selection of tools, the design of sandbox services, the evaluation criteria, and the integration approach are all expected to remain consistent with principles such as transparency, accountability, privacy and data governance, and appropriate human oversight—particularly important in deliberation settings where outputs may influence civic participation and policy-facing processes.

2.3. Feature-driven development

The agile approach is guided by an indicative list of **AI and gamification features** to be considered for the enhancement of deliberation platforms, alongside the relevant **enabler technologies**. The features include, among others: summarisation (for understanding trends), argument mining and clustering, fact- and integrity-checking, content moderation, translation, consensus building, accessibility facilitation, recommender mechanisms, discussion facilitation, video understanding, deliberation monitoring, deliberation quality measurement, and gamification mechanisms to offer incentives for participation. Enablers include: LLMs and Vid-LLMs, video interfaces, Knowledge Graphs, prompt engineering, Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), RLHF, neuro-symbolic reasoning, explainable AI, argument mining frameworks, and APIs.

This list serves as a **design and prioritisation compass**: it allows the project to identify what to prototype in early sprints, what to refine based on pilot feedback, and how to structure the toolkit as modular services.

These candidate features were operationalised into Epics and User Stories in the project’s Product Backlog (Annex B), which served as the baseline for sprint planning and for prioritising WP4 technical developments across pilots.

2.4. Model development

To achieve the **desired** functionality, the GA specifies that WP4 will build on **existing AI models** (primarily LLMs and Vid-LLMs) to support the languages and modalities of the pilots, and then develop a **sandbox** that exposes deliberation-specific functionality as **services (APIs)** for easy integration into existing deliberation platforms. This approach ensures that platform partners can integrate AI capabilities without having to build bespoke AI stacks per platform, and it supports modularity: services can be updated, replaced, or configured across sprints without redesigning the whole integration.

Where existing models are not adequate to support deliberative activities, the GA foresees a structured set of improvement techniques, including: **fine-tuning** (e.g., prompt engineering, adapter fine-tuning), **language adaptation**, **RAG** (grounding responses in domain context, including the Deliberation Knowledge Graph), and **RLHF**, with less computationally intensive approaches prioritised.

2.5. Evaluation

Evaluation is embedded directly into the sprint methodology. The GA specifies a **model-agnostic evaluation approach** supported by a **rigorous prompt engineering test suite** to explore model capabilities on deliberation-specific benchmarks. This enables comparative evaluation across models and supports sprint-based refinement decisions: whether a capability can be delivered through prompting and pipeline design, or whether fine-tuning/adaptation is required.

In parallel, the GA stresses that special care will be paid to safeguards for **transparency, trustworthiness, explainability, security/privacy, and hallucination elimination**, acknowledging that LLM outputs can be presented confidently even when incorrect. The planned mitigation toolbox includes grounding methods (e.g., RAG) and **neuro-symbolic reasoning approaches** that combine neural models with Knowledge Graphs to improve factual reliability and explainability.

Finally, the methodology is underpinned by infrastructure planning to ensure that experimentation, evaluation, and (where needed) fine-tuning can be performed within project constraints. The GA allocates dedicated resources for WP4 technical infrastructure to support training and pilot needs (budgeted as equipment for the technical infrastructure of the project). This supports the agile principle of iteration: computational capacity is treated as an enabler for testing alternative models/configurations and improving services across sprints in response to evaluation findings.

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3. Platforms Introduction

A core design choice in AI4Deliberation is that the **WP4 AI toolkit is not developed as a standalone application**, but as a set of reusable AI services that can be **embedded into existing deliberation environments**. The Grant Agreement foresees that AI services will be integrated into deliberation platforms through **platform-specific plugins** that communicate with the WP4 services through **APIs**, so that the same toolkit can be reused across different technical and organisational contexts.

Integrating the toolkit into **three platforms** plus an additional external integration target (Frankly) via the dembrane bridge serves two complementary purposes. First, it ensures that the toolkit is validated in **heterogeneous real-world settings**—from an established open-source participation platform to a graph-based deliberation environment and an audio-first analysis tool—reflecting the diversity of the pilots and their maturity levels. Second, it supports the project’s longer-term objective of **transferability and adoption**: by demonstrating API-based integration on different platforms (including a widely used open-source platform), the toolkit can be taken up beyond the pilots without requiring organisations to replace their existing participation infrastructure.

The following sections introduce the three platforms - **Consul, DebateGraph, dembrane and Frankly** - and briefly outline their role in the pilots and the rationale for their selection as integration targets for WP4 AI services.

3.1 Consul

Consul³ is a mature, open-source participation platform that is particularly well-suited to public-sector deliberation because it operationalises core democratic principles—**transparency, inclusivity, accountability, and procedural clarity**—through standardised participation workflows. In practical terms, it supports key participation processes such as **citizen proposals, debates, collaborative legislation** (structured feedback on draft texts) and **participatory budgeting**, and it allows these to be combined into **multi-phase engagement journeys** (e.g., debate → proposals → voting), supported by configurable elements such as notifications and process customisation.

Beyond features, Consul’s importance for AI4Deliberation is also linked to its **maturity and adoption**. The platform was originally developed by the **Madrid City Council** and is now supported through a broader ecosystem (including the **Consul Democracy Foundation**), with reported deployment in **over 250 cities and organisations across more than 35 countries**.

This matters for WP4 because the project explicitly aims to develop reusable AI services that can be embedded into real deliberation environments; a widely adopted open-source platform reduces vendor lock-in, increases the likelihood of reuse after the project, and provides a realistic operational context for testing technical, organisational, and legal constraints of AI-enabled deliberation.

Consul is also a strong “integration host” because its core modules generate the kinds of **structured participation data** that WP4 tools are designed to process at scale: free-text contributions, threads and voting signals. In the Bamberg pilot, Consul is already used as the participation infrastructure, including authentication requirements to ensure that only

³ Consul Democracy, 2026, <https://consuldemocracy.org/>

residents participate, and deliberation data typically includes personal data (e.g., names of participants) and contributions stored on internal servers. Special categories of personal data (political opinions, religious beliefs, etc.) might also be processed.

This makes Consul an especially relevant platform for validating WP4’s approach under realistic public-sector conditions, where privacy, accountability, and safe operation are non-negotiable and where “manual processing” quickly becomes a bottleneck as engagement grows.

From an AI4Deliberation perspective, integrating the toolkit into Consul is directly aligned with the **reference architecture described in the Grant Agreement**, where deliberation platforms are enhanced through AI features and connected to the sandbox via **platform-specific plugins communicating through APIs**.

In this model, Consul becomes the citizen-facing environment where content is created, while WP4’s sandbox provides modular AI services—e.g., **trend detection and AI-generated summaries** to help policymakers understand the conversation, **AI-driven moderation** to maintain a respectful deliberative space, **recommendation/personalisation** to increase engagement, and **predictive/analytical insights** based on participation and voting behaviour.

This also creates a clean pathway for structured outputs to feed into downstream components such as analytics pipelines and (where appropriate) the Deliberation Knowledge Graph.

Consul is important to AI4Deliberation because it provides a proven, widely adopted and configurable deliberation platform that allows WP4 to demonstrate its core promise: **AI services that improve scalability and usability of deliberation without replacing existing democratic infrastructure**. Its real-world usage in the pilots (including municipal authentication, internal hosting, and personal data handling) ensures that the toolkit and sandbox are refined against authentic public-sector requirements—especially around trustworthy moderation, accountable summarisation, and safe integration—while the API/plugin approach provides a replicable blueprint for extending other platforms beyond the project.

3.2 DebateGraph

DebateGraph⁴ – created by AI4Deliberation partner, Thoughtgraph (TG) – is an award-winning, collaborative cloud-based platform designed to help people work together to identify, explore, visualise, understand and deliberate on complex public policy issues through the co-creation of large-scale deliberation graphs.

The deliberation proceeds as a live, continuous, evolution of a dynamic, interactive graph through new community contributions (including adding new nodes, comments, citations, cross-links, and ratings), with the graph acting as an open, structured, navigable, central repository of the community’s thought. Each unique idea is identified separately and interconnected with the other ideas to which it relates. And, as the graph grows, it embodies its own narrative output; a cumulative, evolving map of the community’s current understanding of the subject at hand.

The platform has been in continuous development since 2006 and has been used in projects for, among others, the UK Prime Minister’s Office, the UK Foreign & Commonwealth Office,

⁴ DebateGraph, 2026, debategraph.org

the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, the European Commission, CNN, and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation.

Thoughtgraph's social-entrepreneurial mission is to improve humanity's capacity to deliberate openly on complex public policy challenges, and its business model aims solely to generate sufficient funds – via project support – to sustain the evolving implementation of DebateGraph in its global freely available form (DebateGraph, 2025). The code has been closed-source to date and the platform has been freely available for anyone, anywhere in the world to use without charge from the start.

In the context of the AI4Deliberation project, Thoughtgraph is both leading the international pilot using DebateGraph and supporting the design and development of the AI Toolkit in WP4.

The International Pilot differs from the other pilots in that it (i) aims to create a global sensemaking resource to support other ongoing deliberative processes wherever and whenever they are occurring in the world rather than delivering an end-to-end deliberative and/or decision making process in a specific place at a specific time, and (ii) focuses on scaling the ideas that are guiding the deliberative processes rather than the quantity of people who are participating in the process directly.

The pilot aims to ground and support this process by (i) building a dynamically updated and collaboratively editable deliberation graph (focused on long covid) using DebateGraph, and (ii) using the graph to engage with international stakeholders – including patient groups, scientists, health professionals, and policy makers – in the places where public deliberative conversations about long covid are already in flux. Where participation includes the expression of opinions, the process involves the processing of special categories of data. For that reason, we have technical and organisational measures in place and consent will be obtained.

Figure 2: Overview of the Current Work in Progress on the Long Covid Graph

From a technical perspective, and in collaboration with the other WP4 partners, Thoughtgraph, primarily aims to explore whether AI tools (individually or in combination with the argument mining tools) can (i) accelerate the human curation of policy graphs (and,

associated with this, whether the human curated graphs have the potential to increase the signal-to-noise ratio outputs from the AI tools), and (ii) help deliberative participants engage productively with the knowledge represented and distilled in the policy graphs.

These aims are shaped by the practice-informed observation that the wider deliberative utility of the policy graphs, and the utility and adoption of graph-based tools like DebateGraph, is often constrained by (i) the reliance on the underlying layer of curators for creating and evolving the policy graphs (which is a painstaking, time- and labour-intensive process that requires significant, prolonged commitment), and (ii) the time and attention required from deliberators and decision makers to interpret the policy graphs.

WP4 offers an opportunity to test whether the current capabilities of the AI and argument mining tools can loosen or transcend these constraints, and, if this proves to be the case, for the AI4Deliberation AI toolkit to begin to offer policy graphs of this kind to other deliberative platforms as a collective sensemaking resource to support the full-sequence deliberative processes on those platforms aimed at decision making (or recommendations) in specific contexts at specific times.

Examples of the more granular, potential enhancements that may be explored in the context of WP4 and WP5 (depending on the observed capabilities of the AI and argument mining tools) include: enabling participants to use AI to add new structure (including ideas and citations) to the graph, question, expand, and deepen aspects of the graph, and automatically generate textual – and, possibly, visual – summaries of parts or the whole of the graph.

The stretch goal is to be able to use the AI and/or argument mining tools to rapidly and automatically generate large scale graphs – akin to those generated by expert curators – on any policy topic, so that these graphs can be deployed quickly and simply to support the collective sense-making processes in any informal or formal deliberative decision-making context.

3.3 dembrane

Dembrane⁵ is an audio-first deliberation platform for in-person group conversations. Audio is captured via participant smartphones, transcribed, and analysed in real time on EU-hosted infrastructure. The platform is intended for contexts in which person-to-person dialogue is the primary deliberative mode, with AI operating as an on-demand support layer during conversation (asking Socratic questions, summarising for participant verification) and as an analysis layer on the resulting data.

Unlike post-hoc analysis tools, dembrane produces intermediate outputs during the session itself, so participants can review AI-generated summaries, questions, or clusters in the moment and correct or extend them before the conversation concludes. This real-time feedback loop underlies the Verify and Explore features described below.

At the time of writing, dembrane has been deployed across more than 4,000 hours of recorded conversation in over 100 organisations, primarily in Europe — including citizen assemblies,

⁵ Dembrane, 2026, <https://www.dembrane.com/>. In the Grant Agreement, this platform was referred to as “Common Grounds”; however, throughout this deliverable, we use its current official name, 'Dembrane'. One specific functionality within the Dembrane platform is the ECHO component (the participant-facing feature described in this section), which is analysed in Section 4.4.7.

youth summits, peacebuilding dialogues, and organisational strategy sessions. The platform is ISO 27001 certified, and the codebase is source-available.

In the context of AI4Deliberation, dembrane serves the Italian pilot and contributes to the WP4 AI toolkit. Unlike the other platforms in this chapter, it is not only an integration target for the WP4 AI services — it also contributes its own analysis capabilities and builds the bridges connecting other tools (including Frankly, §3.4) to the shared AI infrastructure.

How it works

Dembrane⁶ is built around two core users: participants and hosts. The platform has two primary components accordingly: the participant portal and the host dashboard.

1. **Create a project.** In the host dashboard, configure your participant portal, set the language, and generate a QR code.
2. **Share the QR code.** Participants scan it with their own smartphone and tap once to start recording. No app downloads. Nothing is saved to their device.
3. **Start talking.** Conversations happen around a table, in breakout groups, or in plenary. The phone records; data is sent to EU-hosted servers where it is transcribed and analysed.
4. **ECHO.** When participants are ready, they press ECHO. The language model enters the conversation (see below).
5. **Make sense together.** Hosts see what is emerging in the dashboard while conversations are still happening. Participants interact with language model outputs at their table.

Project setup by a host is typically completed in under five minutes. Transcription is supported for over 100 languages; the host and participant interface is currently available in six languages (English, French, German, Spanish, Italian, and Dutch).

Technological and algorithmic approach

Dembrane's architecture follows a modular AI pipeline:

1. **Input Layer:** Multi-device audio capture from group dialogues, processed through multilingual speech-to-text models.
2. **Processing Layer:** Real-time transcription normalisation and speaker clustering.
3. **Analysis Layer:** A multi-model architecture running agentic AI workflows for semantic analysis, topic clustering, and consensus detection. The system routes tasks to different language models based on complexity: a multimodal model handles report generation, chat analysis, and verification (where it processes both transcript text and raw audio); a fast multimodal model handles real-time tasks such as conversation auto-selection and suggestion generation; and a lightweight text model handles conversation summaries and utility tasks. A LiteLLM Router manages load balancing, automatic failover, and EU region filtering across multiple model deployments.

⁶ Source code: <https://github.com/dembrane/echo>

4. **Insight Layer:** Dashboard visualisation for facilitators, enabling transparent review, correction, and reporting of AI-generated insights.

Mapping to WP2 and WP3 frameworks. The concerns above correspond to specific conditions in the WP3 framework for meaningful deliberation⁷ and to socio-technical risks in the WP2 guidelines. In particular: the sub-processor discussion maps to the WP3 requirement that deploying public organisations retain sovereignty over deliberation design with third-party dependencies kept explicit and bounded (Table 4.1; Table 4.5); two-pass ASR sits in the WP2 "supportive but biased" zone (low AI involvement, non-trivial inherent risk), for which the planned per-language benchmark is the traceability-and-audit response that framework prescribes; Verify is the design artefact through which dembrane attempts to keep AI in the low-involvement zone of the WP2 risk framing — a contestable input to human reasoning rather than a de-facto deliberative act — directly addressing the WP3 requirement to guarantee meaningful human control (Table 4.1) and to respond to concerns about AI among potential deliberators (same table); and downstream interpretation of dembrane outputs is shaped by WP2 concerns around perspective inclusion and plurality of reasons, with source-quoting and deep-dive modes operationalising the WP2 mitigation of layered summarisation with access to underlying arguments and verbatim excerpts.

Role in AI4Deliberation

For AI4Deliberation, dembrane provides the audio-first analysis platform for the Italian pilot. Its role is twofold. First, it serves as a citizen-facing deliberation environment where spoken dialogue is captured, transcribed, and made available for real-time analysis — filling a complementary niche alongside the text-based workflows of Consul and the graph-based structures of DebateGraph. Second, dembrane contributes to the WP4 AI toolkit by developing and exposing its own analysis services (semantic analysis, topic clustering, consensus detection, argument mapping) through APIs, following the plugin-based integration architecture described in the Grant Agreement.

This dual role also extends to bridging other deliberation tools into the AI4Deliberation infrastructure. In collaboration with Konnektable, dembrane is building the integration layer that allows Frankly (§3.4) to connect its video-based conversation data to dembrane's analysis pipeline, enabling the WP4 AI services to operate across both in-person and online modalities.

3.4 Frankly

Frankly⁸ is an open-source, video-based online deliberation platform developed by the Applied Social Media Lab at Harvard University's Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society. It is designed to facilitate constructive dialogue and collaborative decision-making across diverse groups in online settings.

The platform enables organisers to host structured video events where participants are matched into breakout rooms based on survey responses, ensuring a diversity of perspectives in each group. Key functionalities include integrated discussion guides that embed structured agendas directly within the video environment, flexible facilitation options for both hosted and hostless events, and deliberative tools for gathering feedback and crowdsourcing

⁷ For more information, please refer to D3.1 AI4Deliberation comprehensive framework – first version, Chapter 4.3, Tables 4.1-4.5

⁸ Frankly, President and Fellows of Harvard College, 2025, <https://frankly.org/>

solutions collaboratively. Frankly has been used for large-scale deliberative events in the United States, including citizen roundtables and cross-partisan dialogue initiatives, with events reaching over 600 participants.

Frankly is built as a Flutter application with a Firebase backend. The codebase was open-sourced in 2025, co-developed with Harvard Law Professor Lawrence Lessig, and builds upon a framework originally created by Lightning Rod Labs and acquired by the Berkman Klein Center in 2024.

As with dembrane above, the consortium-level ethics assessment of the AI tools Frankly's data passes through is in §6.4. The considerations raised here are specific to Frankly as a video-based online platform and to the Frankly–dembrane integration.

Video-specific privacy surface. Video-based deliberation produces materially more identifiable data than text or in-person audio: faces, backgrounds, shared screens, and non-verbal behaviour are all captured alongside speech. In the current integration, video files are retained only long enough for the bridge to extract audio and are then deleted (§7.4). However, the transient window during which the full video exists on dembrane's EU infrastructure constitutes a data-protection surface that does not exist in the text- or audio-only pilots, and it requires explicit operational treatment — particularly where participants' physical contexts (home environments, family members, visible documents) are incidentally recorded.

Algorithmic breakout-room matching. Frankly matches participants into breakout rooms on the basis of survey responses, with the design intent of ensuring diversity of perspectives. This is an algorithmic editorial decision about who speaks to whom in a deliberation, and its effects on the substance of dialogue are not neutral. The matching logic is inherited from Frankly's existing platform design rather than specified by the consortium; for AI4Deliberation pilots, the implications for deliberative quality and representativeness warrant explicit discussion in pilot evaluation.

Moderation in hostless events. Frankly supports hostless event formats, in which breakout rooms operate without a live human facilitator. In such configurations, harm mitigation within a room — in response to abusive language, disclosure of distress, or coercive dynamics — relies on platform-level automated moderation or post-hoc review rather than live human intervention. In the WP2 two-dimensional risk framing, this sits in the "automation risk" zone (high AI involvement, low-to-moderate inherent risk), for which the WP2 mitigation prescription (clear role separation, mandatory human validation, explicit non-binding status of AI outputs) and the WP3 requirement to address safety problems that undermine deliberative quality (D3.1 §4.3.1, Table 4.2) argue for either retaining human hosts at scale in AI4Deliberation pilots, or disclosing the hostless configuration to participants in advance and providing a documented post-hoc review path.

Accessibility and the digital divide. Online video deliberation requires stable broadband, a functioning camera and microphone, and a sufficiently private physical space — conditions that are not evenly distributed across populations a pilot may aim to include. This limits the comparability between in-person (dembrane) and online (Frankly) modalities within the same pilot and should be accounted for when pilot results are interpreted.

Current-phase integration limit. In the present integration phase (Phase 1, §7.4), AI analysis is applied after a Frankly session concludes: audio is extracted, transcribed, and processed

through the WP4 toolkit, and outputs are surfaced to hosts in the dembrane dashboard rather than within the Frankly session itself. Participants in a Frankly breakout room therefore deliberate without in-session AI support. This is an intentional phasing decision that defers the live-feedback question to Phase 2, but it means the "AI-assisted deliberation" label applies to the pilot's analysis phase rather than to the real-time participant experience in the current integration.

Role in AI4Deliberation

While Frankly is not a consortium partner, its inclusion as an integration target serves a specific purpose within the project: it extends the reach of the WP4 AI toolkit to online video-based deliberation. Where dembrane captures in-person spoken dialogue through smartphone microphones and Consul processes text-based citizen contributions, Frankly provides structured video conversations that generate a distinct type of deliberation data—spoken exchanges within moderated breakout rooms.

The integration is managed by dembrane and Konnektable, who are building the bridge between Frankly's video platform and dembrane's analysis pipeline. In practice, this means that conversation data from Frankly sessions can be processed through the same transcription, analysis, and insight-generation services described in Section 3.3, enabling hosts to apply the WP4 AI toolkit to online deliberations without replacing their existing video infrastructure.

This integration supports the Italian pilot and demonstrates a core ambition of the AI4Deliberation architecture: that the AI toolkit can operate across different deliberation modalities—text (Consul), graph (DebateGraph), in-person audio (dembrane), and online video (Frankly)—through a consistent API-based approach, without requiring organisations to adopt a single platform.

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Table 1: Pilot-to-platform mapping and priority WP4 services

Pilot	Primary interaction platform / channel	Main language(s)	Main modality	Priority WP4 services (Sprint 1 evaluation focus and/or integration targets)	Notes for integration planning
Greek pilot	Pilot data source for testing (public consultation data, e.g., opengov.gr)	Greek	Text	Summarisation; Argument extraction; Moderation & safety; Topic extraction/clustering	Strong emphasis on Greek-language consistency and public-sector suitability; outputs must be traceable and usable for administrative reporting.
German pilot (Bamberg)	Consul	German	Text (plus optional audio workflows)	Summarisation; Argument extraction; (ECHO report-style summaries evaluated as complementary in Sprint 1)	Consul is the core participation environment; AI services are integrated as modular features supporting facilitators/admins and (where appropriate) participants.
Italian pilot	dembrane (used for deliberation capture/analysis)	Italian	Audio → transcription → text (and potentially video/audio)	Transcription; Report/ask-style summarisation; Summarisation; Argument extraction	Sprint 1 relied on structured internal discussions/recordings; ECHO provides the key “audio-first” route, with AI services layered on top.
International pilot (Long Covid)	DebateGraph	Primarily English	Text / graph-structured content	Argument mining / structured extraction; Support for graph curation; Summarisation (supporting)	Strong link to Knowledge Graph-style structuring: outputs must be compatible with graph representations and support curation workflows.

The mapping is used to prioritise which services are integrated first per platform and to ensure the sandbox/API layer supports pilot-specific constraints (language, modality, governance). It will be updated as pilots progress and additional services become operational. The pilot-to-platform mapping and service priorities reflect the Target Sprint/Pilot planning captured in the Product Backlog (Annex B).

4. AI toolkit and sandbox for experimentation

Chapter 4 introduces the WP4 **AI toolkit and sandbox for experimentation** as the project’s practical environment for identifying, testing, and packaging AI tools and models (including LLMs and multimodal/video-capable models) into deliberation-specific services that can be integrated into pilot platforms through APIs. Because the toolkit lifecycle repeatedly touches topics such as human oversight, robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency/explainability and accountability, WP4 applies the **Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)** as the common reference framework for operationalising EU Trustworthy AI guidance throughout tool selection, evaluation, and integration activities. (Commission, 2025)

WP4 is also directly informed by WP2’s process-design guidance for scalable deliberation.

The WP2 guideline frames how deliberative quality can be preserved under common real-world constraints (e.g., asynchronous participation, flat discussion structures, and limited facilitation) and maps these constraints to design interventions and AI-supported functionalities. Importantly, WP2 explicitly anchors these recommended AI-supported functionalities in the WP4 toolkit and sandbox approach, treating the toolkit’s service categories (e.g., summarisation, argument/structure extraction, moderation and safety, translation/accessibility, and gamification) as modular building blocks that can be combined depending on stage-specific needs and risk profiles.⁹

WP4 implementation is also informed by WP3 co-design findings. In co-creation discussions, stakeholders stressed that AI features should remain **supportive rather than interventionist**, that deliberators should have clear **agency** over when AI is invoked, and that safeguards are needed to reduce risks of **nudging/manipulation** (including clear, real-time visibility on what an AI feature is doing and what inputs it uses). These expectations are reflected in WP4 design choices such as opt-in/triggered AI interactions, human-in-the-loop review patterns, and the emphasis on traceability, validation, and constrained pipelines when AI outputs feed into pilot-facing workflows.¹⁰

The chapter then walks the reader through the WP4 process end-to-end. **Section 4.1** presents the initial identification of candidate open-source tools and models, including the methodology used and the functionality categories considered. **Section 4.2** reports the follow-up evaluation and selection decisions, including down-selection and the rationale for not taking forward specific tools, and concludes with the set of tools carried into the sprint-based implementation. **Section 4.3** describes the sandbox setup that supports controlled experimentation, including gamification testing, the technical infrastructure, pilot infrastructure support, and the prompt engineering test suite. **Section 4.4** summarises the model evaluation results and the refinements identified (per functionality) to inform the second sprint. **Section 4.5** documents the improvements implemented during Sprint 2, and **Section 4.6** consolidates the pilot infrastructure requirements emerging from early pilot work to inform the next stages of deployment and integration.

⁹ For more information, you can refer to D2.2: AI-enabled Deliberation Processes – first version

¹⁰ For more information, you can refer to D3.1: AI4Deliberation comprehensive framework – first version

4.1 Identification of existing open-source AI tools and models

The identification and selection of tools for the WP4 toolkit followed a structured, consortium-wide process that started from the **functional needs** of AI4Deliberation and ended with an agreed portfolio of tools to be implemented and exposed through the sandbox. In line with the project plan, the starting point was the set of deliberation-related AI features derived from earlier work on deliberation methods and requirements, and the WP4 mandate to identify existing tools/models (including LLMs and multimodal capabilities) that can be packaged as services and integrated into deliberation platforms via APIs.

4.1.1 Methodology

The identification and selection of tools for the WP4 AI toolkit followed a structured, consortium-wide methodology designed to ensure that decisions were **requirements-driven, transparent, and aligned with the project's agile ethics-by-design approach**. Rather than selecting tools based on technological availability alone, WP4 partners translated deliberation needs into concrete functionality requirements, screened candidate tools in a consistent manner, and validated selections collectively before moving to implementation planning and sandbox integration.

Concretely, the consortium applied the following steps:

1. **Requirements-to-functionality mapping.** Based on the results from WP1 and the analysis of deliberation methods and needs, WP4 partners consolidated the core functionalities required for the toolkit (e.g., summarisation, deliberation/argument-related analysis, moderation and safety, translation and accessibility, and gamification elements). This ensured that tool selection was anchored in deliberation-process needs and pilot realities, rather than in model popularity or general-purpose capabilities.
2. **Tool scouting and long-list creation.** Technical partners researched and proposed candidate tools and models that could serve as building blocks for each functionality, prioritising open-source and self-hostable options where possible and ensuring relevance to the project's multimodal and deliberation-oriented scope. The goal of this step was breadth: to capture multiple viable options per functionality before narrowing down.
3. **Consistent evaluation using a common questionnaire (KT).** To harmonise decision-making across partners and functionalities, candidate tools were screened using a common Evaluation Questionnaire prepared by Konnektable (KT). This provided a shared basis for comparison and reduced the risk of ad-hoc, partner-specific selection criteria. For transparency and traceability, the questionnaire used for tool screening and tiering is provided in **Annex A**.
4. **Three-tier ranking and consortium validation.** Based on the questionnaire results, tools were grouped into a three-level tier list reflecting relative suitability. Partners then reviewed the ranking collectively and finalised the shortlist with minor adjustments. This step ensured shared ownership of the selection decisions and enabled pilots and platform partners to validate whether the proposed tools matched their operational constraints (e.g., language requirements, modality, expected outputs).

5. **Selection of multiple tools per functionality (risk mitigation, user choice, and ethics-by-design).** A deliberate design choice was to retain more than one candidate per functionality where feasible. This served three purposes. First, it reduced dependency on a single tool or provider and preserved continuity if external issues arise later (e.g., tool discontinuation, licensing/terms changes, reputational or ethical concerns). Second, it created practical flexibility for pilots, allowing alternative tools to be used when one option does not fit a given context (e.g., language performance, infrastructure constraints, user preferences, or platform integration limitations). Third—and importantly—it supported the project’s **ethics-by-design approach**, where multidisciplinary input (technical partners, pilots, and ethics expertise) informs selection and development choices. In practice, this meant that beyond technical performance, tools were also considered through cross-cutting criteria such as privacy and data governance, transparency/explainability potential, robustness, and operational accountability. Where concerns were identified, alternatives were intentionally preserved so that pilots could still progress without locking the project into a single solution.
6. **Partner assignment and implementation as reusable components exposed via APIs.** After the shortlist was agreed, tools were distributed among partners for implementation and packaging as reusable components. The shared integration approach is that partner-developed tools are exposed through APIs to KT and integrated into the sandbox for experimentation, enabling consistent testing, refinement, and platform-facing service delivery.

Building on the steps above, the shortlist was organised into core functionality areas that reflect deliberation needs and can be delivered as modular services through the WP4 toolkit and sandbox. The selection and prioritisation of these functionalities follows the project’s requirements-driven methodology and was also informed by the WP1 product backlog compiled as an internal result of Task T1.3. A summary of this product backlog is provided in **Annex B** to document the approach and ensure traceability, while noting that it remains a working planning artefact.

Important note for interpretation. The tools presented in the next subsection represent the **proposed shortlist** emerging from the scouting and questionnaire-based evaluation. They are not necessarily the final implementation set. Later sections of this chapter report the outcomes of sprint-based evaluation and integration work, explaining **which tools were eliminated and why**, and which tools and pipelines were ultimately taken forward for use in the pilots.

To strengthen this mapping step, WP4 also drew on the WP2 Scaling Deliberation Matrix / AI-Process Matrix, which translates deliberative principles into design considerations across the four stages of a deliberative process. This supported a requirements-driven and ethics-by-design prioritisation: features were not assessed only for task performance, but also for their contribution to protecting “capped” principles (e.g., equality and authenticity) and enabling scalable ones (e.g., reflection) through traceable, stage-appropriate interventions.¹¹

¹¹ For more information, you can refer to D2.2 AI-enabled Deliberation Processes – first version

4.1.2 Large Language Models (LLMs)

LLMs provide the backbone for several deliberation services in the WP4 toolkit (e.g., structured summarisation, analysis and classification tasks), and they enable rapid experimentation in the sandbox through prompt-based workflows. It is important to note that the **LLM landscape evolves quickly**, and the work reported in Section 4.1 reflects a **time-staged selection process**: the models listed there were **current and appropriate at the time of the initial proposals and screening**, based on the evidence and constraints available then. As the project progresses, newer releases within the same model families (and equivalent alternatives) are expected to offer **improved performance and robustness**, and WP4 anticipates updating model versions accordingly—while maintaining the core principles that motivated their original proposal (e.g., suitability for deliberation tasks, multilingual coverage, feasibility of deployment/self-hosting where relevant, and alignment with trustworthy-AI requirements). This ensures that the toolkit remains both **technically up-to-date** and **consistent with the project’s ethics-by-design and EU Trustworthy AI approach** as it moves through subsequent pilot sprints.

Proposed tools:

- **LLaMA-Krikri** — *Use*: specialised LLM variant; *Why selected*: identified as the **best Greek language LLM** for Greek-language deliberation needs.
- **Claude AI (Claude 4 Sonnet)** — *Use*: long-context analysis and careful drafting with a strong safety posture; *Why selected*: prioritised for its **extended context length** and **focus on responsible AI**, important for sensitive deliberation content.
- **Mistral Large** — *Use*: strong general LLM with EU-friendly self-host options; *Why selected*: preferred due to **open-source licensing, multilingual support**, and suitability for **GDPR-compliant deployment**.
- **LLaMA 3.3 (70B)** — *Use*: high-quality open-source baseline for on-prem deployment; *Why selected*: chosen for **stronger performance** among open models and **EU-compliance potential**, ensuring flexibility across pilot environments.¹²

4.1.3 Deliberation and Argument Mining

Argument and conversation analysis tools support the extraction and structuring of key positions, claims and conversational dynamics from deliberation content. This functionality is particularly relevant when deliberations scale up and manual analysis becomes infeasible, and it provides inputs that can also feed structured representations (e.g., for downstream analytics and Knowledge Graph population).

Proposed tools:

- **oAMF (Argument Mining Framework)** — *Use*: modular, end-to-end **argument mining pipeline** (from input text to an argument graph), with replaceable/upgradable modules; *Why selected*: documented, peer-reviewed, recently released, and designed to support a complete yet extensible pipeline.

¹² For more information regarding the Ethical assessment, you can refer to D2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects

- **Jigsaw Sensemaker** — *Use*: topic clustering and “common ground vs differences” summaries for civic dialogue; *Why selected*: purpose-built for **deliberation and consensus-finding**, rather than generic summarisation.
- **ConvoKit** — *Use*: conversation analytics (e.g., turn-taking, stance, politeness) and features relevant for deliberation analysis; *Why selected*: directly supports structured analysis needs and contributes building blocks relevant to a **deliberation knowledge graph**.

4.1.4 Summarisation and NLP components

Summarisation/NLP tools provide lightweight and/or complementary capabilities to LLM-based processing, supporting experimentation with different abstraction levels and pipelines (e.g., “fast overview” summaries versus more structured outputs). Maintaining these components alongside LLMs also supports robustness, benchmarking, and the option to deploy less resource-intensive approaches where appropriate.

Proposed tools:

- **BART** — *Use*: abstractive summarisation and text generation; *Why retained*: stable and lightweight for controlled summarisation tasks, even if modern LLMs may outperform it in many settings.
- **Sumy** — *Use*: extractive summarisation with simple algorithms (e.g., LSA); *Why retained*: reliable and very lightweight as a fallback summariser where resources are constrained.
- **Stanza** — *Use*: POS tagging, dependency parsing, named entity recognition; *Why retained*: robust, maintained NLP toolkit that can serve as a fallback for structured NLP outputs when needed.

4.1.5 Moderation and Safety

Moderation functionality targets the identification of toxic or harmful language to support safer deliberation environments and to assist administrators and facilitators in maintaining constructive discourse at scale. This is treated as a distinct functionality area because it has specific performance and risk requirements and often needs to be combined with procedural safeguards.

Proposed tools:

- **Detoxify (Tier 1)** — *Use*: open-source toxic speech classification (multi-label); *Why selected*: prioritised due to open-source availability, active maintenance, and GDPR-friendly deployment.
- **Mod-Guard (Tier 2 – backup)** — *Use*: text moderation/offensive language detection; *Why retained*: redundancy/baseline for comparison, although it is older and less maintained than priority options.

4.1.6 Translation and Accessibility

Translation and accessibility tools support multilingual participation and lower barriers to engagement. In WP4, this includes both text translation and speech-to-text capabilities, enabling participation across languages and modalities and supporting pilots that work with audio/video contributions.

Proposed tools:

- **LibreTranslate** — *Use:* self-hosted machine translation via REST API; *Why selected:* simple, reliable, and GDPR-compliant with minimal infrastructure overhead.
- **Whisper** — *Use:* robust multilingual speech-to-text (99+ languages); *Why selected:* widely adopted and robust, prioritised over less mature accessibility tools.

4.1.7 Gamification and Engagement

Gamification is treated as a dedicated functionality area because it relates to participation incentives and user experience elements (e.g., skill points, scores, and other engagement mechanisms). The sandbox is used to experiment with how such elements can be combined with AI-supported deliberation features while remaining compatible with the project’s ethics-by-design approach.

Proposed tools:

- **Chamilo LMS (Tier 1)** — *Use:* LMS with certificates, scoring, and gamification hooks; *Why selected:* practical for immediate pilot deployment as a full-featured LMS with active support.
- **Gamification-Engine / gengine (Tier 2 – backup)** — *Use:* modular gamification framework (points, leaderboards, achievements); *Why retained:* useful if Chamilo needs reinforcement or additional gamification hooks.

4.2 Follow-up evaluation and selection of tools

Following the structured scouting and tiering process described in Section 4.1, the consortium maintained a clear distinction between **(i) tools identified during the initial research/long-listing phase** and **(ii) tools that were ultimately selected for implementation, sandbox integration, and pilot-facing use**. While the initial mapping aimed to capture a broad set of candidate open-source tools and models for each functionality, Sprint 1 evaluation confirmed that **not all identified tools should be carried forward**, either because they did not meet minimum quality thresholds under pilot conditions, because they were not sufficiently mature for reliable integration, or because their outputs were not robust across languages and deliberation settings.

Down-selection was therefore an intentional step in the WP4 pipeline: tools were reduced from “possible candidates” to a smaller set of **deployment-ready or pilot-test-first components**, while alternative tools were retained only where they provided clear redundancy, benchmarking value, or niche coverage. This approach remains aligned with the WP4 mandate to identify and test tools in a sandbox before operational adoption, and it ensures that integration effort focuses on components that can deliver dependable results for deliberation support.

4.2.1 Moderation and Safety

Mod-Guard was reviewed as a potential moderation component, but it was not selected for use in the implemented moderation pipelines. The moderation work in WP4 requires not only classification performance but also operational suitability (e.g., explainable outputs, stable behaviour across inputs, and integration into layered moderation flows that reduce unnecessary reliance on costly LLM calls). Based on the comparative evaluation and

implementation trajectory, the consortium prioritised alternative moderation components and pipelines that better aligned with these requirements. Mod-Guard is therefore retained only as a backup reference option and was not used in the current implementation.

4.2.2 Translation and Accessibility

Whisper was considered for speech-to-text support, but it was not used in the final implementation. The project retains the ability to revisit alternative speech-to-text tooling if later pilot feedback or modality needs require it, but the current deployment focuses on the option that performed best in practice.

4.2.3 Summarisation and Supporting NLP components

During the initial tool mapping, the consortium also considered lightweight summarisation and NLP toolkits (BART, Sumy, Stanza). These tools were not selected as primary summarisation engines for the pilots because the summarisation requirements in AI4Deliberation (quality, coherence, topic coverage, multilingual consistency, and adaptability across contexts) are better served through LLM-based pipelines. In practice, the summarisation work in Sprint 1 and Sprint 2 relied on LLM (Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1, and Pixtral Large 25.02), which provided higher quality outputs for deliberation summarisation and supported the project's iterative refinement approach. BART, Sumy, and Stanza remain relevant only as potential baselines for controlled comparisons, but they were not used in the pilot-facing summarisation implementation.

4.2.4 Gamification and engagement

Gamification-Engine (gengine) was assessed as a potential component for implementing points/leaderboards/achievements, but it was not used as the primary solution. Given the sprint timelines and the need to prioritise implementable and pilot-relevant mechanisms, the consortium focused on the selected gamification approach and retained gengine only as a backup option. This ensures that alternative gamification tooling is available if later pilot feedback suggests the need for different mechanics, metrics, or integration patterns.

4.2.5 Argument Mining

Apart from oAMF, two additional tools were considered during the scouting phase as **complementary components** to the argument-mining pipeline. While they do not perform argument mining in the strict sense used in this deliverable (i.e., identifying positions and the supporting/rebutting reasons), they were reviewed for potentially relevant supporting functions such as grouping statements by topic and highlighting disagreement patterns. Ultimately, they were not taken forward for implementation, consistent with the project's pragmatic down-selection approach: WP4 prioritises tools that are sufficiently robust, feasible to deploy, and aligned with pilot needs and governance constraints, while retaining only a limited set of alternatives for resilience in later sprints.

Jigsaw Sensemaker¹³ is described as providing topic identification, categorisation of statements within topics, and summarisation. However, it is developed within Google's ecosystem and runs on Google's Vertex AI platform, which implies a dependency on a specific

¹³ <https://jigsaw-code.github.io/sensemaking-tools/>

commercial provider. To avoid introducing such platform lock-in for a core deliberation functionality, it was not included.

ConvoKit¹⁴ is a toolkit for representing and analysing conversational data. For the international pilot, transforming inputs into conversational-style data was not considered suitable, since the pilot focuses on curated, pre-prepared informative materials rather than interactive discussions. In addition, ConvoKit's analysis functions largely target interaction dynamics (e.g., how participation time is distributed), which are less applicable to the pilot's primary need to analyse static documents. For these reasons, ConvoKit was not adopted for the international pilot.

4.2.6 Selection of the tools to use in the Sprints

Building on the requirements-driven scouting and tiering process described in the previous sections, WP4 converged on a focused set of tools and model-based pipelines to be carried forward into Sprint-based experimentation and pilot integration. This selection was made to ensure traceability to the project's consolidated functional needs (WP1/T1.3 Product Backlog – Annex B) and to remain aligned with the socio-technical guidance emerging from WP2 (deliberation-stage requirements) and WP3 co-design feedback (e.g., AI as a supportive, user-steered capability with safeguards against manipulation and opaque intervention). For traceability, the selected tools and their intended usage per functionality follow the Epics/User Stories and sprint targeting described in the Product Backlog (Annex B).

At the same time, WP4's internal evaluation cycle (Sprint 1) and subsequent refinement work (Sprint 2) confirmed that not every tool identified during the initial long-listing phase was suitable for operationalisation. The consortium therefore down-selected to components that (i) performed sufficiently well under pilot-representative data and languages, (ii) can be deployed and integrated reliably via the sandbox/API approach, and (iii) remain compatible with the project's ethics-by-design and Trustworthy AI principles. The remainder of Chapter 4 then analyses these selected components in detail (evaluation findings and refinements).

Table 2: Tool selection for the sprints

Functionality area	Selected tool(s) / pipeline(s) carried into the Sprints
Summarisation	WP4 summarisation pipeline (batching + synthesis) using Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1, Pixtral Large 25.02
Argument extraction	LLM-based IBIS extraction pipeline (schema-guided) using Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, Pixtral Large 25.02 ; plus oAMF (xAIF-based modular argument mining, evaluated in the International pilot context)
Moderation	Moderation pipelines combining Detoxify + LLaMA Guard + an LLM moderation layer (gpt-oss:120b) , including an explanation step for transparency
Translation	Translation pipeline using LibreTranslate plus LLM-based translation comparisons with Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1

¹⁴ <https://convokit.cornell.edu/index.html>

Functionality area	Selected tool(s) / pipeline(s) carried into the Sprints
Topic modelling / topic extraction	Revised topic extraction pipeline with GPU backend Qwen/Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct and CPU fallback (MoritzLaurer/mDeBERTa-v3-base-mnli-xnli + intfloat/multilingual-e5-large-instruct)
Audio-first deliberation support (Italian/German sprint testing)	ECHO environment for audio-supported deliberation and rapid analysis (participant/host portals; “Explore/Verify” style interaction and reporting safeguards)
Gamification	opengov.gr WordPress gamification plugin (upvote/downvote + comment score + user reputation mechanism)

4.3 Sandbox setup for AI-enhanced deliberation experimentation

In AI4Deliberation, the **sandbox** is the practical execution environment where the consortium can **experiment with, compare, and operationalise** AI capabilities for deliberation before deploying them in live pilot settings. The Grant Agreement positions the sandbox as a core element of the WP4 reference architecture: it builds on **existing and (where needed) fine-tuned AI models**, is coupled with cross-cutting safeguards (transparency, trustworthiness, ethics, explainability, security and privacy), and exposes the resulting AI functionality as **services (APIs)** that can be integrated into deliberation platforms.

A key rationale for the sandbox is **controlled, repeatable testing**. The first pilot sprint (M7–M15) was explicitly designed as an **internal validation phase**, restricted to consortium members, to confirm that the socio-technical infrastructure is safe and functional before citizen-facing use. Within this evaluation setting, the sandbox enables technical and pilot partners to run candidate tools on curated pilot materials (e.g., role-play simulations and historical datasets) and **assess** output quality and functionality-specific performance in a comparable way across pilots and languages.

Operationally, the **sandbox** acts as a **common integration layer** across a heterogeneous platform landscape. AI services are designed to be “plugged into” the platforms through **platform-specific plugins** that communicate with the WP4 services via APIs, allowing the same deliberation functionalities (e.g., summarisation, argument-related analysis, moderation, translation/accessibility) to be reused across pilots without requiring each platform to implement its own AI stack. This also supports the project’s modularity goal: tools can be replaced, upgraded, or configured per pilot needs (e.g., language constraints, governance rules, infrastructure limitations) while keeping stable interfaces for integration.

At this stage, the sandbox is organised around three complementary roles:

- **Experimentation and benchmarking of deliberation services.** The sandbox provides a structured environment to test and compare tools/models for specific deliberation tasks, using shared inputs and evaluation criteria, and to identify what is sufficiently robust for pilot use versus what requires refinement.

- **Packaging and delivery of AI functionality as services.** Selected tools are integrated as reusable components and exposed through APIs, preparing their uptake into platform workflows and supporting iterative improvements across sprints.
- **Evidence generation for sprint-based refinement.** Results from the first internal evaluation cycle provide concrete feedback on model suitability, prompt and pipeline weaknesses, and infrastructure constraints; these findings feed directly into T4.2 updates (including explainability/trustworthiness techniques and fine-tuning decisions where justified).

In the remainder of this chapter, the sandbox setup is detailed through: **(i)** the experimentation of **gamification mechanisms** as required by WP4, **(ii)** the sandbox’s role in supporting pilots to clarify **infrastructure needs**, and **(iii)** the **prompt engineering test suite** used to evaluate models consistently and to guide refinements.

4.3.1 Gamification Elements

In AI4Deliberation, **gamification elements** are introduced as part of the project’s vision for *multimodal, AI-enabled, mass deliberations* that remain usable, accessible, and engaging—especially in an online context where participation is often low and citizens’ digital habits are increasingly shaped by social media and gaming. In line with the Grant Agreement, gamification is treated as a concrete set of mechanisms—such as **points/scores (incl. skill points/levels), missions, badges/achievements, leaderboards, and avatars**—that can provide *extra incentives for participation* while also supporting better understanding of complex topics and more inclusive participation for users with different cognitive and communication needs. Importantly, these mechanisms are not “added on” for competition, but are designed and tested under an **ethics-by-design** approach (with safeguards for equal opportunity, avoidance of manipulation, and support for non-dominant voices), and are experimentally validated in the **WP4 sandbox** before being deployed in pilot-facing platform integrations.

WP2’s guidance clarifies that gamification is most effective when it is **process-sensitive** (i.e., tailored to the needs and risks of each deliberation stage) and explicitly warns that poorly designed or uniform gamification can privilege activity over contribution quality, speed over comprehension, and competition over authentic exchange. In WP4, this is reflected in the decision to treat gamification as a supportive mechanism—used to sustain engagement and recognise constructive participation—while applying safeguards to avoid strategic behaviour, discouragement effects, or amplification of participation inequalities.¹⁵

The following subsections describe the core gamification elements that will be implemented during Sprint 2. An example from a first integration using a WordPress plug in on the opengov.gr platform (Greek Pilot) is described below.

Levelling System

The levelling system introduces a progression-based participation model, where users advance through predefined levels based on their contributions and interactions within the deliberation process.

¹⁵ For more information, you can refer to D2.2 AI-enabled Deliberation Processes – first version

Design Principles

- Merit-based progression: Advancement is tied to meaningful actions (e.g., contributing arguments, engaging constructively), rather than simple activity volume.
- Transparency: Users are informed about how levels are achieved, avoiding opaque scoring mechanisms.

Functional Role in Deliberation

The levelling system serves multiple purposes:

- Encourages long-term engagement, as users are incentivised to return and continue their progress.
- Promotes higher-quality contributions, particularly when progression is linked to validated or endorsed inputs.

Badges

Badges function as discrete recognitions of specific achievements or behaviours within the deliberation environment. Unlike levels, which reflect cumulative progression, badges highlight particular forms of contribution.

Design Principles

- Action-specific recognition: Badges are awarded for participation (e.g., “Top 10% Contributor”, “Most Helpful Comment”).
- Non-hierarchical visibility: Badges signal diversity of contribution rather than ranking users linearly.
- Contextual relevance: Badge types may vary depending on the deliberation phase or platform.

Functional Role in Deliberation

Badges support:

- Behavioural nudging, encouraging users to adopt desirable deliberative practices (e.g., increased participation, evidence-based arguments).
- Recognition of diverse contributions, ensuring that not only highly active users are rewarded.
- User identity shaping, allowing participants to build a visible profile of their deliberative strengths.

Knowledge Graph Interaction

Interaction with the Deliberation Knowledge Graph introduces a novel gamification dimension, where users engage not only with discussions but also with structured knowledge representations through the UI using natural language.

Design Principles

- Cognitive engagement: Gamification extends beyond participation to include exploration of knowledge.
- Users are encouraged to interact with the Knowledge Graph, so when they make a comment or a proposition, they are more informed about the deliberative process and existing discussion.

Functional Role in Deliberation

Gamified Knowledge Graph interaction enables:

- Active sense-making, where users explore connections between arguments, topics, and evidence.
- Improved comprehension, especially in complex deliberations with large volumes of content.

Leaderboards

Leaderboards provide a comparative view of user activity or contribution within the deliberation process. While common in gamification systems, their use in deliberation requires careful calibration to avoid counterproductive competition.

Design Principles

- Context-sensitive ranking: Leaderboards may be scoped (e.g., per topic, phase, or activity type) rather than global.
- Balanced metrics: Rankings consider quality indicators (e.g., validated contributions) alongside activity levels.
- Ethical safeguards: Mechanisms are implemented to prevent discouragement of lower-ranked users.

Functional Role in Deliberation

Leaderboards aim to:

- Increase engagement through visibility, highlighting active contributors.
- Provide feedback loops, helping users understand their relative participation.
- Encourage continued contribution, especially in early-stage engagement.

However, their role is intentionally limited to avoid:

- Over-competition that undermines deliberative collaboration.
- Reinforcement of participation inequalities.
- Strategic or low-quality contributions aimed solely at improving rank.

4.3.2 Technical Infrastructure

Since the project's inception, the infrastructure contributions have established a robust, multi-cloud foundation specifically engineered to support the rigorous demands of AI4Deliberation's development, experimentation, and pilot deployment cycles. On Amazon Web Services (AWS), a comprehensive environment was initially provisioned, offering

flexibility through its suite of services—including an EC2 instance for general-purpose computing, a Bedrock instance for API-driven access to foundation models, a SageMaker instance for custom model training, and persistent S3 storage buckets. Although this AWS subscription has since concluded, its early deployment provided valuable agility during the initial experimentation and model benchmarking phases.

Building on these foundations and recognising the intense computational requirements for training and refining large language models—a core necessity for deliberation summarisation and argument extraction—the infrastructure has been strategically expanded into the Google Cloud Platform (GCP), which now serves as the primary computational backbone for the second sprint. A high-performance A2 Ultra VM equipped with an A100 GPU has been deployed, and is pivotal for accelerating both the training of custom models and the low-latency inference required for responsive AI services. To support these intensive workloads, high-performance local SSD storage has been integrated for ephemeral training data, ensuring maximum I/O throughput, and a 1 TB regional SSD persistent disk has been provisioned for the reliable, long-term storage of fine-tuned models and curated datasets.

The current GCP setup supports ongoing pilot integration and refinement, and remains subject to change as sprint requirements evolve. Collectively, this infrastructure—anchored in the Google Cloud Platform and informed by early-stage experimentation on AWS—provides the project with a resilient, scalable, and high-performance backbone, seamlessly supporting everything from initial sandbox experimentation and model evaluation to the deployment of concrete, explainable AI services for the pilot platforms.

4.3.3 Pilot Infrastructure Support

Task 4.1 explicitly requires WP4 to **assist pilots in determining their specific infrastructure needs**, in parallel with tool identification and the setup of the sandbox for experimentation.

In AI4Deliberation, the sandbox is not only an experimentation environment for AI functionalities; it also acts as a **shared technical “test bed”** that helps pilots translate their deliberation processes and platform constraints into concrete infrastructure requirements (hosting, integration, data handling, security and operational workflows).

This support function is especially relevant because the pilots operate in **heterogeneous contexts** and the first pilot sprint (M7–M15) is designed as **internal testing and infrastructure readiness**, involving only consortium members as testers to validate feasibility before citizen contact. In practice, pilots used the sandbox to trial selected functionalities on representative material (e.g., simulations and historical datasets), and—through this process—clarify what is needed for stable deployment and integration in later sprints.

How the sandbox supports pilots in identifying infrastructure needs

(1) Standardised service interfaces to clarify integration effort.

The Grant Agreement frames the sandbox as a set of AI features delivered as **services (APIs)**, integrated into deliberation platforms via **platform-specific plugins**. By exposing tools behind stable interfaces, the sandbox allows each pilot to determine:

- which **platform integration points** are required (e.g., where in the user/admin workflow the AI feature is invoked),
- what data must be exchanged (input payloads, output formats),

- and whether the pilot needs **real-time** interactions (e.g., moderation) or **batch/offline** processing (e.g., periodic summaries and reports). This reduces ambiguity early and helps pilots estimate development and operational effort for their integration roadmap.

(2) Deployment profiling (central vs pilot-side) and compute sizing. Because WP4 evaluates multiple models and pipelines (including LLM-based services and multi-stage moderation), pilots need to understand how different choices translate into **compute and hosting requirements**. The sandbox supports this by enabling controlled runs of the same functionality using alternative tools/models, which makes visible:

- where GPU/accelerated compute is needed versus CPU-only feasibility,
- how workload grows with transcript length and deliberation volume,
- and how different configurations affect latency and cost. This “try-before-deploy” capability is central to Sprint 1’s goal of validating feasibility and preparing the artefacts needed for subsequent pilots.

(3) Data handling and governance checks aligned with pilot constraints. The first sprint evaluation is described as validating the project’s **socio-technical infrastructure** under internal testing conditions. Running tools through the sandbox provides a concrete way to check what data is required and how it should be managed, helping pilots define:

- what data must be **exported** from the platform for AI processing,
- whether **anonymisation** steps are required before processing,
- where results can be stored (pilot systems vs sandbox-side storage),
- and what logging/auditing is needed for accountable use in public-sector contexts.

These considerations align with the reference-architecture view in the GA, which includes safeguards for privacy, security, explainability and trustworthiness alongside the sandbox and services. To ensure these principles will be implemented technically in development, the project uses the ALTAI requirements as a basis for all its activities.

(4) Language- and context-specific configuration needs. Sprint 1 testing across pilots showed that output quality and usability are sensitive to **language compliance** and domain/context constraints. The sandbox helps pilots surface infrastructure-relevant implications of this sensitivity, such as:

- whether a pilot requires dedicated language models or specialised configurations,
- how to implement “validation gates” (e.g., reject outputs in the wrong language),
- and whether a pilot needs local processing options for sensitive datasets. This ensures that infrastructure planning is informed by actual tool behaviour rather than assumptions.

Sprint 1 process and outputs supporting infrastructure planning

During the first sprint, WP5 documents the “AS-IS” and “TO-BE” states of each pilot and reports results from internal infrastructure testing. The sandbox supported this process by providing a common environment where pilots could:

- test priority WP4 functionalities under controlled conditions,
- record integration constraints and operational requirements as part of the sprint lessons learned,
- and translate findings into concrete needs that feed the pilot sprint backlogs and the evolving WP4 architecture.

Overall, the sandbox’s infrastructure-support role is therefore twofold: it **de-risks integration** (by clarifying technical and data interfaces early) and it **enables realistic deployment planning** (by revealing compute, governance, and operational needs through hands-on testing). The consolidated infrastructure requirements derived from this process are presented in Section 4.4, where pilot needs are synthesised and mapped into cross-pilot baseline requirements and pilot-specific constraints.

4.3.4 Prompt Engineering Test Suite

As specified in the Grant Agreement, WP4 adopts a **model-agnostic evaluation approach** and develops a **rigorous prompt engineering test suite** to explore the capabilities of candidate language models on **deliberation-specific benchmarks** (e.g., **DebateSum, IAM, AQE, XNLI, XQuAD**). This approach allows the consortium to compare models fairly and consistently across tasks, languages, and pilot contexts, and to make evidence-based decisions on (i) which model/tool is most suitable per functionality and (ii) where further refinement (prompting, pipeline changes, or fine-tuning) is justified.

The underlying logic of the test suite is intentionally “lightweight” and operational: instead of modifying model weights as a first step, the evaluation probes model behaviour through **carefully designed prompts**, i.e., it stress-tests what a model can and cannot do through controlled inputs. This makes evaluation repeatable within the sandbox environment and supports agile iteration (e.g., comparing successive model versions, prompt variants, or configurations) without locking the project into a single vendor or architecture.

Beyond functional correctness, Sprint 1 evaluation also considered socio-technical risks highlighted in WP2. In particular, WP2 stresses risks of **automation bias** and “epistemic closure”, where fluent AI outputs may be perceived as correct or consensual even when uncertainty or disagreement exists; it therefore recommends explicit uncertainty signalling, visibility of disagreement, and human validation loops. Sprint 1 refinement priorities such as stronger grounding/traceability, predictable structured outputs, and human-in-the-loop review patterns align with these WP2 recommendations, ensuring that AI supports deliberation without replacing human judgement or narrowing plurality through hidden framing effects.

Evaluation workflow. The test suite is organised as a standardised workflow that can be applied to any candidate LLM:

1. **Define capabilities and task types.** The evaluation starts by defining the deliberation-relevant capabilities to be tested (e.g., summarising arguments, identifying claims vs.

evidence, recognising entailment/contradiction across languages). Each capability is translated into one or more task types.

2. **Select or assemble benchmarks (ground truth).** For each task type, the suite uses labelled datasets as ground truth—where each benchmark provides inputs (text, pairs of texts, dialogue segments) and expected outputs (labels, summaries, or ratings). The suite is grounded in deliberation-relevant datasets such as DebateSum, IAM, AQE, XNLI and XQuAD, and may be complemented with project-specific examples where needed.
3. **Design prompt templates.** For every task type, one or more prompt templates are created that wrap benchmark inputs in a consistent instruction format. Multiple prompt variants are used to test sensitivity to phrasing and improve robustness.
4. **Run models against the suite.** Each model is executed over the same set of (prompt, input) pairs, and outputs are collected in a comparable format. This is the core model-agnostic mechanism: the same suite is reused unchanged across candidate models.
5. **Score outputs using task-appropriate metrics.** Outputs are compared to ground truth using metrics appropriate to the task category, for example:
 - **Classification tasks** (e.g., XNLI): accuracy, F1
 - **Generation tasks** (e.g., summarisation): ROUGE, BERTScore, and/or human evaluation
 - **Ranking/quality estimation tasks** (e.g., AQE): correlation with human ratings (e.g., Spearman)
6. **Analyse results and iterate.** The suite supports systematic error analysis (e.g., prompt phrasing that consistently confuses a model, performance drops for non-English inputs, or task types where all models underperform). These findings are then used to refine prompts, adjust pipelines, select the most appropriate model per task, or flag cases where fine-tuning may be required.

In summary, the prompt engineering test suite functions as a **standardised test harness** for deliberation-oriented LLM behaviour: it operationalises the project’s requirement for comparable model evaluation, supports rapid iteration inside the sandbox, and provides the evidence base for model selection and refinement decisions in subsequent sprints.

4.4 Model evaluation results and identified refinements

The first evaluation of the WP4 AI toolkit took place during the project’s **first pilot sprint (“Think big and prepare”, M7–M15)**, which is explicitly framed as an **internal validation phase**. At this stage, the objective was to ensure that the project’s socio-technical infrastructure is safe, functional, and sufficiently mature before any citizen-facing deployment, and to generate early evidence that can steer subsequent technical iterations. In WP5 terms, this sprint corresponds to **T5.1 (planning)** and **T5.2 (operation and evaluation)**, with results documented in D5.1.¹⁶

¹⁶ For more information, you can refer to D5.1 Pilots plan, operation and evaluation - first sprint

Within this overall agile evaluation strategy, the WP4 contribution focused on an **initial, structured appraisal of the AI tools' outputs and functionality-specific performance**. The evaluation scope covered the toolkit functionalities already prioritised for pilot relevance (e.g., **summarisation, argument extraction, moderation**, and in pilot-specific cases **translation, topic modelling, and the ECHO environment**). Importantly, the purpose of Sprint 1 was not to validate full operational integration into production platforms; rather, it aimed to provide an **evidence-based first view on output quality, usefulness, and fitness-for-purpose**, under different pilot conditions and datasets, and to identify concrete gaps and refinements to address in the next sprint.

A key characteristic of this first evaluation round was the **controlled setting and restricted stakeholder group**. The sprint evaluation was conducted by **consortium members only**, with pilot partners and technical partners acting as testers in order to validate feasibility and readiness before engaging citizens. In practice, this internal testing was implemented through two complementary approaches: **role-play simulations** (German and Italian pilots) to generate comparable “ground truth” discussion data for tool testing, and **historical dataset analysis** (Greek and International pilots) to benchmark core functionalities against real-world deliberative material already available to the pilots.

Methodologically, the evaluation combined **standardised questionnaire-based assessment** with qualitative feedback and, for selected functionalities, automated measures. The central design principle was **granularity**: pilots completed **one questionnaire per tool output**, and where tools were run in multiple configurations (e.g., different LLMs for the same task), each variation was assessed separately to support comparison. Alongside structured ratings, evaluators provided **qualitative comments** capturing strengths, weaknesses, missing elements, and practical usability in deliberative settings. To ensure consistent interpretation across partners, technical teams presented each tool using a **common template** (including tool description, functionality overview, input/output examples, limitations, and expected behaviour). For some tools (including moderation, translation, and summarisation), the consortium complemented human assessment with **automated evaluation**, using either **annotated datasets** or **LLM-as-a-judge** approaches.

The questionnaire itself assessed each output against (i) **general quality criteria** and (ii) **functionality-specific criteria**, rated on a **1–5 Likert scale** (strongly disagree to strongly agree), and complemented by optional open comments. Quality criteria captured whether the output was **coherent, complete, accurate, factually correct**, and **useful for understanding the deliberation**. Functionality-specific items assessed whether the output matched the purpose and expected behaviour of the tool and whether it would be useful in real-world deliberation scenarios.

Finally, although the evaluation approach was common across the consortium, the **execution reflected pilot-specific contexts and constraints**, ensuring the results were meaningful for the different deliberation environments:

- The **Greek pilot** tested selected WP4 functionalities using Greek public consultation data (opengov.gr) and an annotated comment set for moderation, with an explicit focus on whether outputs were sufficiently accurate, usable, and **language-consistent** for Greek administrative use.

- The **International pilot** evaluated argument mining and LLM tools in the context of curating a Long Covid policy graph, using a pilot-selected illustrative corpus and treating the first round as exploratory and context-specific.
- The **Italian pilot** organised an internal evaluation using a structured Italian-language role-based discussion (approx. 20 minutes) to test summarisation and argument extraction, and separately assessed ECHO’s transcription and “report/ask” functions using recordings of role-based discussions.
- The **German pilot** conducted a simulation with municipal staff to understand tool behaviour and limitations prior to citizen-facing deployment, explicitly considering requirements around procedural accountability and legal certainty.

Taken together, this first sprint evaluation established a practical baseline for WP4: it validated what already performs robustly under controlled conditions, documented where outputs remain inconsistent or context-sensitive, and produced a prioritised set of refinements to guide **T4.2 developments** (including configuration adjustments, robustness improvements, and—where justified—fine-tuning and explainability measures) before the project moves to small-scale citizen pilots in the next sprint.

Below is a structured set of **fine-tuning / refinement suggestions per evaluated tool**, based on what emerged from the **1st sprint pilot evaluations** and the cross-cutting lessons learned (grounding, language compliance, robustness, and clearer constraints).

4.4.1 Summarisation

For the Summarisation task, we developed and evaluated a pipeline that took as input the context of the deliberation, along with a list of deliberation comments in a csv form. The comments were filtered based on their relevance to the given context and they were divided into batches that can fit the LLM context window. From that, a summary was generated for each batch which were combined to produce a coherent overall summary. Through this method we used the LLM **Claude 4 Sonnet**, **LlAMA 3.3 70B**, **DeepSeek R1**, and **Pixtral Large 25.02**. The LLMs were accessed through the Bedrock API.

Figure 3: Flow diagram for summary pipeline (v1)

In this pipeline, as a first step, we clean the dataset by removing comments that are not relevant to the specific context (e.g. legal article) (if they exist) and are monosyllabic. This is done by comparing the comments with the context. To achieve that, we use LLM-based prompting, providing the model with specific guidelines that define which comments are considered irrelevant or unsuitable for use. The LLM returns a score based on how closely the comments adhere to the guidelines. For this, we used the following prompt:

Prompt 1: Relevance Check

1. ****Topical Focus (0–30)****

- +points for precision and depth on the article’s topic.
- +bonus if it introduces a related subtopic.
- –penalty if off-topic or irrelevant; mark “Remove” if completely unrelated.

return only the total score without any comments or explanations. If the comment is completely irrelevant, score it with 0.

...

1st Example of output:

0

2nd Example of output:

29

After removing irrelevant comments, a solution was needed to address the limited context window of LLMs. In some cases, the number of comments was too large for the LLM to process them all at once. To address this challenge, we divided the comments into batches by token count. Each batch was then processed individually using a summarisation prompt. For this, we used the following prompt:

Prompt 2: Summaries of Batches

Read the following comments carefully.

1. Identify the main topics discussed and group them into categories (e.g., criticism, personal experiences, positive points).
2. From each category, keep the most representative arguments without repeating details.
3. Present the summary in a logical flow:
 - first the general tone (e.g., positive/negative),
 - then the main topics discussed,
 - and finally a brief conclusion about the overall tone of the comments
4. Be neutral and objective, without emotional expressions from commenters (e.g., "get serious" → "criticism of the government").
5. The summary should be in the input language and as many paragraphs as necessary to cover all topics.

After generating the summaries for each batch, we combined them by sending all partial summaries back to the model, which produced a coherent, unified summary suitable for the end user. For this, we used the following prompt.

Prompt 3: Final Summary

Based on the following paragraphs, please generate a coherent text of as many paragraphs you need in input language. Without changing the original content or introducing new ideas.

The models that we used are LLaMA 3.3 (70B parameters), DeepSeek R1, Claude 4 Sonnet and Pixtral.

In simple terms, the summarisation tool is a pipeline that:

- Takes as input the context of the deliberation, along with a list of deliberation comments in a CSV form.
- The comments are first filtered based on their relevance to the given context (the step uses LLMs).
- Then they are divided into batches that can fit the LLM context window.
- Then a summary is generated for each batch (the step uses LLMs).
- Finally, the batch summaries are combined to produce a coherent overall summary (the step uses LLMs).

We evaluated the above pipeline during WP5 and the findings suggest the following decisions

Claude 4 Sonnet

Why refine: Claude was consistently best in pilot ratings (e.g., **Greek avg 4.43/5, German avg 3.50/5**) and produced topic-specific, structured summaries, but pilots still highlighted gaps around (i) **minority/weaker arguments** and (ii) missing **quantitative signals** that would improve reporting.

Refinement focus (rather than model fine-tuning):

- Add explicit prompt constraints to **force inclusion of minority viewpoints/objections** (Claude sometimes under-represents them).
- Add an optional **“light quant layer”** (e.g., frequency of themes/positions) as requested by pilots.
- Increase **grounding/traceability**: require **source anchors** (quotes or segment references) and an explicit **uncertainty flag** when coverage is incomplete.

- Implement “**multiple summary modes**” (supporting ongoing facilitation vs retrospective reporting), because pilots stressed that one generic summary style is insufficient.

LLaMA 3.3 70B (open-source candidate for improvement)

Why fine-tune: LLaMA performed weakly in pilots, especially where **language stability** is a hard constraint (Greek noted mixed-language artifacts and credibility issues; summarisation Greek avg 1.43/5).

Fine-tuning priorities:

- **Language adaptation (Greek-specific):** reduce mixed-language and corrupted hybrid terms; treat language compliance as a threshold requirement.
- **Deliberation-domain tuning:** reduce “generic templating” and improve topic grounding (a key failure mode reported in summarisation and argument extraction).
- Pair with stronger grounding constraints (RAG-style context injection is explicitly part of the project’s improvement strategy when base models are inadequate).

Pixtral Large 25.02 (open-source candidate for improvement)

Why fine-tune: Pixtral showed **strong structure/readability** in some settings (notably Italian), but was uneven and vulnerable to **verbosity, hallucinations, and topic drift** (especially Greek/German).

Fine-tuning priorities:

- **Anti-hallucination + topic adherence tuning:** tighten alignment to the deliberation context to avoid drift/padding.
- **Length/abstraction control:** pilots explicitly requested better calibration between near-verbatim redundancy and overly generic synopses.
- Strengthen multilingual robustness (prevent English output/mixed language in Greek administrative settings).

DeepSeek R1

Status: Used in the summarisation set and in translation benchmarking.

Refinement suggestion: Treat it as a **comparative baseline** and continue evaluating against pilot-specific criteria (pilot feedback highlights that automated “LLM-as-judge” scoring can be subjective and inconsistent).

If retained as a candidate, apply the same two levers as above: (i) strict language safeguards and (ii) stronger grounding/traceability requirements.

System Implementation (Wordpress Plugins)

As part of the system implementation, we developed three plugins for WordPress, each corresponding to a core functionality of the platform: moderation, summarisation, and information extraction. These plugins enable integration between the proposed pipelines through the API endpoints into a real-world content management environment.

4.4.2 Argument Extraction

For the LLM-based argument extraction task, CERTH and UNIS developed and evaluated a modular pipeline for structured argument extraction grounded in the Issue-Based Information System (IBIS) model. The IBIS model comprises three main concepts: i) Issues, ii) Position, and iii) Argument. Additionally, UNIVDUN worked with oAMF for argument mining in the International pilot.

For the LLM-based argument extraction task, we developed and evaluated a pipeline that comprises the following steps:

- It takes as input a list of comments from a csv.
- For each comment we extracted information based on the IBIS model using a relevant prompt at an LLM. The pipeline focuses primarily on the extraction of positions (proposed answers to an issue) and relative supporting or opposing arguments of each position.

To ensure schema-conformant outputs, the pipeline integrates the following components:

- Pydantic: Provides a structured way to represent the IBIS model and enables the extraction of structured information from each comment.
- Instructor: A library used to enforce structured Pydantic outputs from LLMs.

This design follows recent trends in LLM-based structured information extraction, where schema-guided prompting improves reliability and consistency of outputs.

The aim of this component is to also feed the Knowledge Graph of the project with IBIS structured information when applied to the pilot data.

For the argument extraction task, we used the LLM models **Claude 4 Sonnet**, **LLaMA 3.3 70B**, **Pixtral Large 25.02**, and also evaluated **oAMF** (International Pilot). The oAMF is a collection of open-source modules for argument mining tasks. It is designed as a modular pipeline with swappable components which can be accessed as web services or run locally as Docker containers. Input and output for almost all modules is a JSON file in the eXtended Argument Interchange Format (xAIF): an initial module can be used to convert plaintext into xAIF. For the evaluation, this conversion was done locally using python and standard NLP libraries (Natural Language Toolkit (nlk), BeautifulSoup). This converted the text into an xAIF file populated with potential Argumentative Discourse Units (ADUs). This version of initial processing can be made available as a new module to users.

Claude 4 Sonnet (argument extraction)

Why refine: Claude was strongest overall (e.g., **Greek avg 4.29/5**), but still failed key requirements in some pilots: incomplete capture of positions, unreliable stance judging, and insufficient filtering of non-arguments (e.g., “this.. is trash”).

Refinement focus (rather than model fine-tuning):

- Enforce a stricter “**argument vs attitude/remark**” distinction (a core weakness across pilots).
- Add explicit instructions to prioritise **propositional content** over affective wording, because misclassification was linked to “negative phrasing → negative stance” shortcuts.
- Improve capture of **deliberation dynamics**: disagreements, evolution of positions, and final outcomes were often missing.

Pixtral Large 25.02 (argument extraction)

Why fine-tune: Pixtral was a strong secondary option in some contexts (e.g., **Greek avg 4.00/5**), but showed variability: stance misinterpretations, occasional hallucinations, and inconsistent guideline alignment (notably German).

Fine-tuning priorities:

- **Stance calibration tuning:** reduce errors where sentiment polarity overrides the actual propositional stance (explicitly noted as a fixable failure mode).
- **Schema/format reliability:** train toward consistent structured outputs for positions/arguments (needed for downstream use and curation).

LLaMA 3.3 70B (argument extraction)

Why fine-tune: LLaMA was weakest across pilots for argument extraction (e.g., **Greek avg 2.00/5**, **German avg 2.29/5**), with recurring issues: language instability, hallucinations, and stance errors driven by negative wording.

Fine-tuning priorities:

- **Deliberation-argument tuning:** explicitly train to separate (i) positions, (ii) supporting/rebutting arguments, (iii) examples/illustrations, (iv) attitudes/remarks.
- **Multilingual stabilisation** (especially Greek): eliminate English leakage and corrupted characters.
- **Prompt + model iteration:** even within sprint 1, pilots recommended iterative prompt refinements and using latest model versions to explore achievable improvements before heavier interventions.

oAMF (Open Argument Mining Framework)

Why refine (configuration + potential re-training): In the International Pilot, oAMF scored lowest (**avg 1.57/5**) and produced noisy output with limited utility in the first round.

Refinement priorities (as identified by the pilot):

- **Align configuration to corpus/objectives** via close collaboration with University of Dundee; the pilot explicitly flagged that results may be test-specific (corpus size/type).
- **Explore integration scenarios with LLMs** (e.g., feeding LLM outputs into argument mining) to exploit complementary strengths.
- Where relevant, consider **domain re-training** of relation identification components (the evaluated setup includes a fine-tuned RoBERTa classifier, and parameters like window size are configurable).

4.4.3 Moderation

For the moderation tool, we developed and evaluated three pipelines that combined three different tools: LLM, LLaMA Guard (the third pipeline integrated Detoxify, LLaMA Guard and an LLM).

- **Pipeline 1:** LLM. The first pipeline relied completely on an LLM.
- **Pipeline 2:** LLaMA Guard → LLM. The second pipeline integrated Detoxify (a moderation tool), LLaMA Guard, and an LLM.
- **Pipeline 3:** Detoxify → LLaMA Guard → LLM. The third pipeline combined LLaMA Guard (a locally hosted LLM fine-tuned for moderation) with an LLM.

All pipelines consist of three main phases: i) the data collection and cleaning phase, ii) the main moderation – inappropriate content identification phase and iii) the explanation phase. The data collection and the explanation phases are common among all three pipelines and they only differ in the main moderation phase.

Regarding the data collection and cleaning phase, the pipelines support multimodal input including audio, video and text data. The audio and video data are first transcribed into text. Then all text (either transcribed or originally entered as text) is cleaned and translated into English before entering the main moderation phase. Translation is necessary because not all moderation components support languages other than English (i.e., Detoxify supports only English).

Regarding the main moderation phase, we developed three different alternative pipelines. The design of the three pipelines follows a progressive filtering strategy, aiming to balance moderation performance, computational cost, and explainability. Each pipeline introduces an additional moderation layer to reduce reliance on costly LLM calls while maintaining or improving classification accuracy. The pipelines use different combinations of the tools: LLM, LLaMA Guard and Detoxify. The overall logic is as follows: if a tool classifies a comment as inappropriate (flagged), then the process proceeds directly to the explanation phase. If a comment is classified as appropriate (un-flagged), it is passed to the next moderation component (if any). The main idea of this logic is to reduce the number of comments that reach the LLM in order to also reduce costs.

Finally, regarding the explanation phase, all pipelines include an extra final step in which the LLM is explaining why the specific input was flagged or un-flagged by the system. This phase is very important since we are moderating content in deliberations where transparency and explainability are crucial.

The tools used in the pipelines are:

- gpt-oss:120b
- LLaMA Guard: a specialised large language model designed for safety and content moderation.
- Detoxify: machine-learning–based toxicity detection tool used to identify offensive, abusive, or toxic language

Figure 4: Flow diagram for Moderation

Pipeline 1: For the first pipeline, we used only an LLM (gpt-oss:120b) for the moderation task. The process was straightforward, each comment was provided to the model as input through a prompt, and the model returned a classification result indicating whether the content should be flagged. Although the results were satisfactory in terms of performance, this approach resulted in high operational costs, primarily due to the large number of continuous API calls required to process all comments through the model.

Pipeline 2: To reduce both operational and API costs, we introduced a second pipeline that incorporates a locally deployed moderation model, i.e., a locally hosted model, LLaMA Guard, fine-tuned for moderation tasks. In this approach, each comment is first processed by the local moderation model. If the comment is classified as flagged, the system immediately returns a Flagged result without forwarding the input to the external LLM. This step avoids unnecessary API calls and therefore reduces overall cost. If the comment is classified as unflagged, it is then passed to the LLM for further evaluation and final classification. This pipeline significantly reduced the number of external API calls. However, based on the evaluation results, we observed that the system’s performance could still be further improved, suggesting that additional optimisation or filtering strategies may enhance its effectiveness.

Pipeline 3: As an additional filtering step, we incorporated Detoxify into the pipeline. In this third pipeline, each comment first passes through Detoxify for an initial toxicity check. If the comment is classified as flagged, the system immediately returns a Flagged result without further processing. If the comment is not flagged, it is then passed to LLaMA Guard for a second moderation check. Finally, comments that remain unflagged after this step are forwarded to the LLM for the final evaluation. Since Detoxify does not support Greek and German, the comments from the Greek pilot dataset were translated into English before being processed by the model. Overall, this pipeline achieved the best performance in terms of recall, indicating that the system was more conservative in its moderation decisions and minimised the likelihood of allowing harmful content to pass through unflagged.

From the evaluations of WP5 the following results emerged.

Why refine: This pipeline had the **lowest error rate in Greek (26%)** and better coverage for harmful content, but pilots still noted weaknesses (spam/ads/off-topic) and a specific **Greek profanity blind spot**.

Fine-tuning / improvement priorities:

- Extend moderation taxonomy beyond toxicity/hate to include **spam/ads/off-topic**, since these were recurring failure points.
- Add Greek-specific coverage (slurs/personal attacks) through **language adaptation** of the moderation layer (either by tuning a model component or adding targeted lexicons/guards).

LLaMA Guard → LLM (Pipeline 2)

Why refine: Quantitative evaluation suggests Pipeline 2 offers a more **balanced precision/recall** profile for automated moderation, while Pipeline 3 maximises recall at the cost of more false positives—so selection depends on risk tolerance and policy priorities.

Fine-tuning / calibration priorities:

- **Threshold calibration** for FP/FN trade-offs per pilot context (human-in-the-loop vs automated moderation).

- Improve transparency/operational logic: pilots emphasised that moderation scope and explainability need expansion for deliberative settings.

LLM-only moderation (Claude)

Why refine: Error rates were higher than multi-stage approaches in Greek testing, reinforcing the pilots' conclusion that **layered pipelines outperform standalone LLM moderation**.

Refinement focus: Keep as a fallback/secondary step, but rely on layered detection and add clearer “reason codes” and uncertainty handling to avoid overconfident decisions.

4.4.4 Translation

For the translation tool, we developed and evaluated a pipeline that takes as input the text to be translated, as well as the source and target languages. These are then passed to an LLM for the translation. The LLM models used are the **Claude 4 Sonnet**, **LLaMA 3.3 70B**, and **DeepSeek R1**, as well as the **LibreTranslate tool**. The generated output was then evaluated against the reference text to assess its correctness.

Figure 5: Translation Flow

LibreTranslate

Why keep / refine: Pilots highlighted that non-LLM translation components may be **more stable for some language pairs**, supporting a flexible, per-language selection strategy.

LLaMA / Claude / DeepSeek (LLM translation)

Why refine: Benchmarking shows performance differences based on language; the key operational requirement is **stable language compliance end-to-end** (input → processing → output), especially for Greek.

Fine-tuning strategy (if pursued for open models):

- For LLaMA: consider language/domain adaptation using the same kind of parallel corpora used for evaluation, to reduce instability and improve consistency.

4.4.5 Topic Modelling

For topic extraction, two initial methods were used:

- Zero-shot classification, using the pre-trained multilingual language model joeddav/xlm-roberta-large-xnli. Zero-shot classification is an emerging technique which makes predictions about specific knowledge that models may not have seen during training. Larger models tend to perform better than smaller ones.
- Classification with text embeddings, using the model sentence-transformers/paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base-v2, which maps sentences and paragraphs to a vector space. This method analyses text to produce representations of data (embeddings), in order to label text based on semantic meaning. Both methods are classified as on-the-fly, meaning that they have no prior knowledge of an existing corpus and act on a single text entity. Furthermore, both methods used an initial list of pre-determined topics relative to deliberation, in order to assist the models in topic extraction.

Topic extraction was evaluated with (i) **zero-shot XLM-Roberta XNLI** and (ii) **multilingual MPNet embeddings**; outputs were problematic, including **English output instead of Greek** and poor topic relevance (scores as low as **2.25/5**).

Refinement / fine-tuning priorities:

- Treat **language compliance** as a blocking fix (outputs must be Greek in the Greek pilot).
- Replace static taxonomy behaviour: the pilot perceived outputs as applying a predefined topic list rather than extracting themes from text, making results unusable/misleading.
- Practical next step is to move from “on-the-fly” zero-shot to a **pilot-grounded topic scheme**, then train/classify against it (i.e., a corpus-anchored approach).

4.4.6 Gamification Plugin (opengov.gr)

This subsection presents Sprint 1 implementation and initial assessment of the opengov.gr gamification plugin, developed as an early, pilot-oriented example of how gamification can be embedded into a deliberation platform. The plugin was designed to operationalise simple, transparent engagement signals—through voting and reputation—so that participation incentives can be tested in practice and refined based on pilot feedback, while remaining consistent with the project’s ethics-by-design and trustworthy-AI principles.

This plugin introduces a voting and reputation mechanism. It enables users to upvote or downvote comments, providing a way to evaluate the quality and relevance of user contributions.

Each upvote assigns positive feedback to a comment, while each downvote assigns negative feedback. Based on these interactions, each comment is assigned a score that reflects the overall community evaluation.

In addition, the system maintains a user-level reputation score, calculated as the aggregate of all comments submitted by that user. This mechanism encourages constructive participation and highlights valuable contributions on the platform.

Figure 6: Gamification Plugin Admin Dashboard (Greek Language)

Figure 7: Gamification plugin user interface (Greek Language)

Overall, gamification in AI4Deliberation is treated as a **support mechanism for participation and deliberation quality**, not an end in itself: the selected elements (e.g., points/levels, badges, missions, leaderboards, avatars) are intended to encourage sustained engagement while remaining aligned with the project's ethics-by-design and trustworthy-AI principles. As the project moves through the **second sprint of pilots**, gamification will be reviewed through the same iterative feedback loop that governs the WP4 toolkit and architecture: pilot outcomes and stakeholder feedback will be used to assess whether the current gamification approach effectively supports deliberation goals, and whether **adaptations are needed** in either the **design choices** (e.g., which elements are emphasised or constrained) or the **metrics** used to operationalise them (e.g., how participation, contribution quality, or progression is measured).

4.4.7 ECHO

During Sprint 2, dembrane developed and deployed four core AI service improvements on its platform, responding directly to Sprint 1 evaluation findings and the cross-cutting refinement priorities identified in Section 4.3. The work described below was predominantly carried out within the AI4Deliberation dedicated effort; however, as dembrane's platform development runs in parallel with its commercial operations, some underlying infrastructure improvements that these features build on were developed outside the project's dedicated time allocation.

For the Italian and German pilot, ECHO was used as a practical environment to run and demonstrate audio-supported deliberation and rapid analysis. ECHO is presented as an accessible flow for “scaling small-scale deliberation”, supporting physical conversations, multilingual support (50+), and real-time analysis through three custom AI tools, with separate participant and host portals. In the demo format, it is shown as a short sequence (introduction → deliberation → joint analysis).

ECHO scored very strongly (e.g., **German avg 4.86/5**) and was described as the “best summary” in the German pilot, but with specific risks: mixing tool/process commentary into substantive content, flattening behavioural nuances, and concerns about anonymity/quotations.

Refinement focus (configuration/prompting rather than fine-tuning):

- Add a rule to **separate meta-comments about ECHO performance** from deliberation content.
- Add an optional “**interaction dynamics**” section so tone/intensity patterns aren’t lost in a balanced synthesis.
- Add handling rules for **anonymity** and for quoting inappropriate language in reporting outputs.

4.4.8 Refinements to carry into Sprint 2

Across tools, pilots repeatedly converged on three upgrade targets: **(1) stronger grounding/traceability**, **(2) strict multilingual compliance**, and **(3) structured outputs + uncertainty handling**, particularly because hallucinations/omissions and language instability make outputs unusable in official settings.

This is consistent with the project’s intended improvement toolbox (prompt engineering, adapter fine-tuning, language adaptation, RAG, RLHF—prioritising less computationally intensive approaches first).

Overall, the first-sprint evaluation confirms that the second sprint refinements should be driven less by “adding more tools” and more by making the selected set **reliable, traceable, and deployment-ready** across real pilot conditions. Three requirements cut across almost all evaluated tools and should be treated as **baseline acceptance criteria** in Sprint 2: **(i) strict language compliance** (especially for Greek and other non-English contexts, avoiding mixed-language output), **(ii) stronger grounding and traceability** (clear linkage between outputs and the underlying deliberation content, with safeguards against hallucination and over-interpretation), and **(iii) predictable structured outputs** (stable schemas for downstream use,

plus explicit uncertainty handling when evidence is insufficient). In practice, this implies prioritising iterative **prompt and pipeline improvements** (e.g., layered moderation, source-anchored summarisation, stance/argument disambiguation rules) before heavier interventions, and applying **targeted fine-tuning** only where repeated pilot evidence shows that open models remain below threshold—most notably for language adaptation and deliberation-specific argument/stance reliability. Finally, refinements should be validated against pilot-specific constraints (legal/administrative sensitivity, moderation scope, privacy/quoting rules, and resource limitations), ensuring that Sprint 2 delivers not only better raw performance, but also clearer operational behaviour and safer integration into the platforms.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

4.5 Improvements in the tools during Sprint 2

To support testing and deployment of the tools, **Moderation**, **Summarisation**, **Argument Extraction**, and **Translation**, for the Greek pilot, we designed an integrated modular system that consists of:

- Containerised solution using Docker to simplify deployment. The Docker container includes:
 - Frontend (standalone UI): Built with React.js. This is a standalone UI for each of the developed tools
 - Backend: Developed in Python using FastAPI. Each tool provides an API
 - Auxiliary Services:
 - Whisper (for speech-to-text processing)
 - LibreTranslate (for translation services)
- WordPress plugins that integrate the functionality of each of the tools.

Whisper and LibreTranslate are currently included in the Docker setup for convenience but can be installed directly on the server in future deployments and removed from the Docker Compose configuration.

The backend is built using FastAPI, exposing RESTful endpoints that power both the standalone Frontend and the WordPress plugins.

All models are hosted on a virtual machine using Ollama, which provides an efficient framework for managing and serving large language models via a local API. Hosting the models locally enables faster inference and reduces reliance on external API calls, helping to minimise operational costs and improve data privacy.

The deployed environment includes a variety of models used for different tasks such as moderation, translation, embeddings, reasoning, and multimodal processing. Examples include models from the LLaMA, Qwen, Mistral, and Gemma families. Additionally, specialised models are used for specific tasks, such as LLaMA Guard for moderation and embedding models like BGE-M3 and MXBAI Embed Large for semantic representation.

Overall, this infrastructure allows the system to support multiple AI capabilities, including text moderation, multilingual processing, document understanding, and multimodal analysis, within a single scalable environment.

4.5.1 Summarisation

Figure 8: Flow Diagram for summary pipeline (v2)

The new version of the pipeline has been improved in various ways:

- The first improvement is the addition of multimodal input support. In addition to text comments, users can now submit audio messages or video messages. These inputs are automatically converted to text via speech-to-text processing (Whisper small), allowing them to be analysed by the same summarisation pipeline as textual comments.
- The second improvement concerns the methodology used to generate the summary of user feedback. Instead of separating the comments into batches based on their order, the system now performs a multi-step semantic analysis. First, embeddings are computed for both the context (article content) and the user comments using embedding models. Then, cosine similarity is used to identify comments that are semantically relevant to the article.
- From these relevant comments, the system extracts the positions or segments of interest, which are subsequently clustered based on their semantic similarity.
- Summaries can be produced using two different logics:
 - The logic of the 1st Sprint where the LLM is instructed to identify main topics
 - The new prompt logic is based on four categories: i) What should be added in the context (e.g., article) – New ideas, features, or suggestions proposed by users. ii) What should be removed from the context (e.g., article) – Points of disagreement or proposals explicitly rejected by users. iii) General proposals – Broader suggestions, conceptual ideas, or meta-level comments related to the topic. iv) What should change in the current context (e.g., article) – Specific corrections, edits, or improvements suggested for the existing content.
- Finally, the system synthesises the reports from all clusters into a coherent summary, providing a structured overview of the community feedback and the main points raised by users.

The new prompt to generate summaries (based on the four categories):

You are the Lead Synthesis Officer of the AI4Deliberation group.

Your task is to take multiple sub-reports and merge them into one final, comprehensive, and coherent executive summary.

Please analyse the following comments from a discussion cluster and provide a detailed report structured strictly into the following four sections.

Use formal language and bullet points for each section. If there is no information for a specific section, write 'None identified'. The language must be

the same as the comments (e.g Greek Comments -> Greek Report)

1. ****What should be implemented to the article****: (List new ideas or features suggested by the users).
2. ****What shouldn't be implemented to the article****: (List points of disagreement or things users explicitly rejected).
3. ****General proposals****: (Broad suggestions, conceptual ideas, or meta-comments about the topic).
4. ****What should change to the current article****: (Specific corrections, modifications, or updates to existing content).

Comments to analyse:

{comments_text}

Report:

Prompt to synthesise partial summaries:

You are the Lead Synthesis Officer of the AI4Deliberation group.

Your task is to take multiple sub-reports and merge them into one final, comprehensive, and coherent executive summary.

Below are several reports generated from different comment clusters.

Your goal is to synthesise them into a single, unified, and formal document.

Instructions:

1. **Consolidate & Deduplicate**: If the same suggestion appears in multiple reports, merge it into one point. Do not repeat the same information.
2. **Structure**: Organise the final text strictly under the following 4 headers:
 - a **Implementation Recommendations** (What should be implemented)
 - b **Points of Rejection** (What shouldn't be implemented)
 - c **General Proposals & Strategic Ideas**
 - d **Required Modifications to Current Content** (What should change)
3. **Format**: Use a mix of professional prose for introductions and bullet points for clarity. You may use tables if it helps compare different viewpoints.
4. **Language**: The entire output **MUST** be in the same language as the input reports.
5. **Tone**: Maintain a neutral, formal, and objective tone.

Reports to synthesise:

{all_reports}

Final Coherent Report:

Summary API Endpoint

Route: /summary

Inputs:

- LLM (user-selected model)
- Context Text (e.g., article, legal document. The context is used to check the relevance of a comment)
- Context File (optional, the context as a file)
- Comment File
- Media File (optional)

Output:

- String containing the generated summary

Screenshots of the Summarisation standalone UI

Summarization Service

For the Summary, you must include:

1. The context to which the comments refer, this can be provided either as text or as a PDF.
2. A CSV file containing the comments.

The CSV file **must** be structured as in the following **csv example**
 The first column of the CSV contains the article's title, and the second column contains the comments for that specific article.

gemini-3-flash-preview:cloud

Step 1: Provide Context

Enter Context as Text

που διεξάγουν προγράμματα έρευνας και διαχείρισης της βιοποικιλότητας διαθέτουν προς το κοινό όλα τα διαθέσιμα επιστημονικά δεδομένα που προκύπτουν από το έργο τους. Ως πλέον πρόσφορο μέσο για τη διάθεση της επιστημονικής πληροφορίας προκρίνεται το διαδίκτυο. Από την υποχρέωση δημοσιοποίησης της επιστημονικής πληροφορίας που προκύπτει από τα προγράμματα έρευνας και διαχείρισης εξαιρούνται ως «ευαίσθητα δεδομένα» οι συντεταγμένες κρίσιμων σημείων των ενδιαιτημάτων των απειλούμενων ειδών (φωλιές, τόποι διατροφής, τόποι αναπαραγωγής κ.λπ.). Σε περιοχές όπου υπάρχουν κέντρα ενημέρωσης ή πληροφόρησης για προστατευόμενες περιοχές και τα οποία κρίνονται λειτουργικά, προβλέπεται η συντήρησή τους και η επικαιροποίηση των διαθέσιμων από αυτά πληροφοριών.

OR

Upload Context as PDF

Επιλογή αρχείου Δεν επιλέχθηκε κανένα αρχείο.

Step 2: Upload Comments

Select a CSV file with comments

Επιλογή αρχείου minenv_comments_40.csv

Selected Comments: minenv_comments_40.csv

OR upload audio/video

Audio / Video File (optional — transcript added as a comment)

Επιλογή αρχείου Δεν επιλέχθηκε κανένα αρχείο.

C Processing...

Figure 9: Summary screenshot of the Summarisation standalone UI

Figure 10: Summary Result

4.5.2 LLM-Based Argument Extraction

The argument extraction pipeline was extended to support multiple input modalities, including audio, video, and text. As with other modules, audio and video inputs are first converted to text via speech-to-text processing (Whisper Small), enabling a unified processing pipeline.

An additional extension includes the clustering of position and arguments. The aim of this step is to group semantically similar positions expressed in different wording, and then group the arguments of each position. This enables a more concise and unified overview of the discussion space.

The clustering process operates as follows:

- Embeddings are computed for each position and arguments
- Cosine similarity is calculated between positions and arguments.
- Positions/arguments are grouped into clusters when their similarity exceeds a predefined threshold

The overall argument extraction pipeline is as follows:

Figure 11: Flow Diagram for LLM-based Argument Extraction

There are also several refinements introduced to improve performance and consistency. Specifically, updates were made to both the prompt design and the structured output schema, enabling more accurate and standardised information extraction.

The updated prompt used for the argument extraction task is presented below:

You are an expert in argument mining. Your task is to extract positions and arguments from a public consultation comment. Using the IBIS (Issue-Based Information System) model.

****IBIS structure****

- Issue: the policy question under discussion.
- Position: a proposal, amendment, recommendation, or stance responding to the issue.
- Argument: a reason supporting or opposing a position.

****Context****

The comments come from a legislative consultation about a draft law article.

Comments often propose:

- additions to the law
- removals from the law
- modifications to the law
- general policy suggestions

These proposals correspond to IBIS Positions.

Definitions**Issue in this task**

The issue is predefined and corresponds to the article under consultation.

****Issue**:**

"What changes, if any, should be made to Article X?"

Positions correspond to proposed amendments or suggestions related to the article.

All extracted positions must respond to this issue.

The model should NOT generate or modify the issue.

****Position****

A Position is a distinct proposal or amendment expressed in the comment.

****Typical positions include**:**

- adding a paragraph or provision

- removing a paragraph or provision
- modifying an existing rule
- introducing a new policy suggestion

****Rules for Positions**:**

- Each position must represent ONE proposal only.
- Use a short descriptive label (max 20 words).
- Preserve the meaning of the comment without adding interpretation.
- If the comment contains multiple proposals, extract multiple positions.

****Argument****

An Argument is a reason explaining why the position should or should not be accepted.

****Rules for Arguments**:**

- Arguments must justify or oppose a position.
- Arguments must not contain new proposals.
- Arguments must be derived strictly from the text.
- Use a short descriptive label (max 20 words).

****Argument polarity****

- positive → supports the position
- negative → criticizes or challenges the position

****Extraction rules****

1. Extract all distinct positions mentioned in the comment.
2. Each position must contain exactly one idea.
3. Attach arguments to the position they refer to.
4. Do NOT invent positions or arguments.
5. If the comment only contains justification without a proposal, return no positions.
6. If multiple proposals exist, create multiple positions.

7. If no positions exist, return an empty list.

****Language rule****

All labels MUST be written in the same language as the comment.

****Output rules****

Return ONLY the structured output.

Do NOT include explanations, markdown, or additional text.

****Reasoning process****

Before producing the final output:

1. Identify explicit proposals or amendment suggestions.
2. Convert each proposal into a Position label.
3. Identify sentences that justify the proposal.
4. Convert them into Argument labels.
5. Attach arguments to the correct position.

****Comment****

{comment}

The structured schema used to represent the extracted information is defined as follows:


```

class Polarity(str, Enum):
    positive = "positive"
    negative = "negative"

class AmendmentType(str, Enum):
    addition = "addition"
    modification = "modification"
    removal = "removal"
    suggestion = "suggestion"

class Argument(BaseModel):
    label: str = Field(description="Short summary of the argument (max 20 words)")
    polarity: Polarity = Field(description="Whether the argument supports or opposes the position")

class Position(BaseModel):
    label: str = Field(description="Short summary of a single proposal or stance (max 20 words)")
    amendment_type: Optional[AmendmentType] = Field(default=None, description="Type of amendment proposed")
    arguments: List[Argument] = Field(default_factory=list, description="Arguments supporting or opposing the position")

class Positions(BaseModel):
    positions: List[Position] = Field(description="All distinct positions extracted from the comment")

```

Argument Extraction API Endpoint

Route: /information_extraction

Inputs:

- LLM (user-selected model)
- Comment File (used to extract positions/arguments from)

- Media File (optional - alternative to text comments)

Output (example):

JSON-formatted string containing structured extracted information positions/arguments. The JSON includes at first level the positions (e.g., "Avoid creating a new portal by EKPAA due to the existence of the HELBIONET portal") and then the supporting/opposing arguments (e.g., "There will be redundancy if two organisations perform the same task"). The arguments are categorised as additions, modifications, removals or suggestions.

```
{
  "Avoid creating a new portal by EKPAA due to the existence of the HELBIONET portal": [
    {
      "label": "HELBIONET has already established the portal www.helbionet.org",
      "polarity": "positive",
      "amendment_type": "modification"
    },
    {
      "label": "There will be redundancy if two organisations perform the same task",
      "polarity": "positive",
      "amendment_type": "modification"
    }
  ],
  "Development of a national strategy for the provision of scientific data by all organisations": [
    {
      "label": "Agreement among all stakeholders is required for data sharing",
      "polarity": "positive",
      "amendment_type": "suggestion"
    },
    {
      "label": "The national strategy can be implemented within the HELBIONET framework",
      "polarity": "positive",
      "amendment_type": "suggestion"
    }
  ]
}
```


Screenshots of the Argument Extraction standalone UI

Information Extraction Service

For the Information/ Argument Extraction, you must include a CSV file with comments. The CSV file **must** be structured as in the following **csv example**.
 The tool will extract positions and arguments.
 The positions are the ideas or answers to a specific issue raised by the user.
 The arguments are the reasons that support or oppose those positions.

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Upload a CSV file

Επιλογή αρχείου Δεν επιλέχθηκε κανένα αρχείο.

OR Upload audio/video

Audio / Video File (optional — transcript added as a comment)

Επιλογή αρχείου Δεν επιλέχθηκε κανένα αρχείο.

Information Extraction →

✓ ΑΠΟΤΕΛΕΣΜΑΤΑ ΕΞΑΓΩΓΗΣ (0)

Figure 12: Session for the Argument Extraction UI

✓ ΑΠΟΤΕΛΕΣΜΑΤΑ ΕΞΑΓΩΓΗΣ (16)

Διόρθωση της λανθασμένης παραγραφοποίησης του κειμένου του άρθρου 11.

① Η συνεχής επανάληψη της παραγράφου 1 καθιστά δύσκολη τη διαδικασία σχολιασμού του άρθρου. Fact-check

Αποκατάσταση των τεχνικών σφαλμάτων και των ελλείψεων στο κείμενο μορφής pdf.

① Το κείμενο στην τρίτη παράγραφο διακόπτεται απότομα, εμποδίζοντας την πλήρη κατανόηση της διάταξης. Fact-check

Ρητή αναφορά στον νόμο για την ελεύθερη διάθεση περιβαλλοντικών πληροφοριών χωρίς περιορισμούς χρήσης.

① Διευκόλυνση του έργου των ενδιαφερόμενων πολιτών και οργανώσεων μέσω της παροχής συγκεκριμένων γεωγραφικών στοιχείων. Fact-check

① Αποτροπή ασάφων δημοσιεύσεων για περιβαλλοντικά προβλήματα μέσω της διάθεσης λεπτομερών γεωχωρικών δεδομένων και μεταδεδομένων. Fact-check

① Αντιμετώπιση της συστηματικής αποφυγής δημοσίευσης γεωαναφερόμενων δεδομένων για περιβαλλοντικά προβλήματα από την πολιτεία. Fact-check

① Διασφάλιση της ενημέρωσης για κρίσιμα ζητήματα που αφορούν την υγεία των πολιτών και του οικοσυστήματος. Fact-check

Figure 13: Argument Extraction results (in Greek)

4.5.3 Argument Extraction Plugin

The argument extraction plugin extends the functionality of the WordPress admin panel by introducing a dedicated dashboard for position and argument extraction.

From this dashboard, the administrator selects a specific article and initiates the extraction process. The system then analyses the associated comments and generates positions and arguments for each comment, providing a structured representation of user opinions.

Following this step, the administrator has the option to cluster the extracted positions and arguments, grouping similar viewpoints together to facilitate better analysis and interpretation.

Once the extraction and clustering processes are completed, the results become available on the frontend. End users can view the extracted information either per individual comment or in its clustered form, offering both detailed and aggregated perspectives on the discussion.

Figure 14: Argument Extraction plugin Admin Dashboard

admin says:

March 17, 2026 at 7:40 am Edit

Οι κυνηγητικές οργανώσεις απελευθερώνουν θηράματα σύμφωνα με αυτά της αρεσκείας τους χωρίς καμία ενδυμική μελέτη. Μήπως θα έπρεπε αυτό να πραγματοποιείται απο κρατικά εκτροφεία σύμφωνα με κάποια έρευνα;

Reply

Figure 15: Argument Extraction plugin User Interface, post's page

4.5.3.1 oAMF

The use of oAMF was updated from the off-the-shelf modules used in the first-sprint evaluation in two main ways:

1. Update to language model usage

2. Adaptation to an IBIS model of argument

An IBIS-focused oAMF module was developed for end-to-end IBIS-compliant argument mining on input PDFs. This is deployable as a Docker container in conjunction with a local language model served by a vLLM Docker container.

In addition to being run as an end-to-end process, the internal pipeline stages can be accessed independently through the API. Initial results from other tools can consequently be used as input for the later pipeline stages, provided they are converted to IBIS-compliant XAIF, the format required by the module. These stages can in future be split into distinct modules for true modularisation of the process.

Model changes

The originally-evaluated oAMF modules used finetuned transformer models from the BERT family (e.g. RoBERTa). In evaluation, these produced noisy output with limited utility when applied to the out-of-domain data of the pilot. The models therefore required better alignment to project objectives. The evaluation also suggested integration of LLMs into the process.

For these reasons, the new module uses current LLMs for language modelling tasks, which are more generalisable due to their extensive training data. This approach was chosen over fine-tuning the existing classifiers for the pilot topic, as (in addition to a lack of training data) models fine-tuned for the topic could again fail to generalise when applied beyond the pilot. The use of LLMs is restricted to those which can be hosted locally, partly to retain complete control over data, and partly to avoid reliance on (paid) services beyond control of the project.

The module accesses a local LLM as served by vLLM in an additional Docker container.

Structured output is constrained using the pydantic library.

4.5.3.2 IBIS specialisation

oAMF uses the Argument Interchange Format in which all argument components are *propositions*, and with little constraint on relation structures (e.g. allowing circular paths, relations in any direction between propositions). IBIS places stricter constraints on which propositions can be connected and how (e.g. only propositions designated as *arguments* may be the antecedent of positive or negative relations, and they cannot be connected directly to *issues*). A schema for including IBIS information in XAIF was created to associate IBIS types with proposition nodes. As no prior oAMF modules were specialised for the use of IBIS, updates were also required at each stage to respect the requirements of a well-formed IBIS graph. The IBIS-related adaptations for affected stages are described below.

Component identification

Propositions must be labelled with an IBIS type and can only be related in the combinations and structure permitted by IBIS for their type. As they must be understood out of context, paraphrase may be required. *Issues* should be presented in the form of questions.

XAIF merging

Additional fields of *IBIS* and *source_info* must also be combined.

Proposition merging

Only propositions of the same IBIS type can be considered for merging. Potential merge candidate combinations are constrained by their position in the IBIS graph. Due to the tree-like IBIS structure, any successful merges are followed by checking the newly-combined set of children of the merged nodes for further potential merges.

Proposition linking

Linking is limited to propositions of the same IBIS type.

Other module aspects

The module accepts PDF files or text files as input. The output XAIF also includes source information for IBIS components so that this may be surfaced to users downstream for increased transparency.

oAMF module API Endpoints

Route: /

Inputs: one or more PDF files

Outputs: an IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON

The default use of the module, and includes PDF intake and all later stages.

Route: /argmine-ibis

Inputs: one or more text files

Outputs: an IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON

Runs all stages but requires text files instead of PDF.

Route: /merge-files-only

Inputs: one or more IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON files

Outputs: an IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON

Combines files simply without any node linking or merging.

Route: /argmine-ibis-merge

Inputs: an IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON

Outputs: an IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON

Attempts node merging on the provided file.

Route: /argmine-ibis-link

Inputs: an IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON

Outputs: an IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON

Attempts node-linking on the provided file.

The entire pipeline can be run using the route at / (for PDF) or /argmine-ibis (for txt). If an initial set of IBIS-compliant XAIF JSON is available, this can be processed by the rest of the pipeline by using the other routes in the following order:

merge-files-only → argmine-ibis-merge → argmine-ibis-link

4.5.4 Moderation

During Sprint 2 we enhanced the moderation pipeline in order to be explainable and also moderate some new categories and context that contains users' personal data.

The following prompt is used for the LLM to identify harmful content:

You are a moderation assistant. Your primary role is to evaluate online comments in forums and debates. You must analyze user comments for ****deliberation quality and moderation concerns****. You must be unbiased, transparent, and consistent. Your score should reflect both civility and contribution to meaningful deliberation.

Each comment must be labeled ('safe' or 'unsafe') as follows:

Comment Evaluation

Comments are considered unsafe if they belong to one of the following categories.

Category	Label	Definition
sexual	S	Content meant to arouse sexual excitement, such as the description of sexual activity, or that promotes sexual services (excluding sex education and wellness).
hate	H	Content that expresses, incites, or promotes hate based on race, gender, ethnicity, religion, nationality, sexual orientation, disability status, or caste.
violence	V	Content that describe, promotes or glorifies violence or celebrates the suffering or humiliation of others.
harassment	HR	Content that may be used to torment or annoy individuals in real life, or make harassment more likely to occur.
self-harm	SH	Content that promotes, encourages, or depicts acts of self-harm, such as suicide, cutting, and eating disorders.
sexual/minors	S3	Sexual content that includes an individual who is under 18 years old.

| hate/threatening | H2 | Hateful content that also includes violence or serious harm towards the targeted group. |

| violence/graphic | V2 | Violent content that describe, depicts death, violence, or serious physical injury in extreme graphic detail. |

##New in Sprint 2##

| spam / scam bait | C | Clickbait/ promotional/ scam or any message. In this Category goes everything that encourage the user to click a specific link. Also Ads ****must**** be flagged with this category |

| expressive/ activist/ confrontational | E | pro-LGBTQ+ solidarity statement mixed with political rhetoric or any emotionally charged statement |

| Personal Data | NPI | Any direct or indirect identifier of a natural person, such as full name, home address, phone number, email, government ID, IP address, or precise location. Excludes public organisations and generic non-identifiable references. |

##New in Sprint 2##

Examples:

{Examples}

COMMENT

{comment}

###OUTPUT

Return only the word 'safe' or 'unsafe' depending on your choice and situation! Without thinking or any other words.

The following prompt is used to create explanations:

You are an expert moderator analyzing public discussion comments.

Your task is to explain why a moderation decision was made.

Important rules:

- ALWAYS assume the moderation result is correct.
- Do NOT question or overturn the result.
- Provide a concise explanation that justifies the result based on the content of the comment.

Result (the correct moderation outcome):

{result}

Comment:

{comment}

Explain why this comment would lead to the given moderation result.

Moderation API Endpoint

Route: POST /moderation

Inputs:

- Pipeline (moderation configuration, i.e., the pipeline to be used)
- Comment (text input)
- Media File (optional - multimodal input to be moderated)

Output:

```
{
  "is_it_flagged": <true/false>,
  "moderated_text": "<processed_text>",
  "detected_language": "<language_code>",
  "explanation": "<moderation_reasoning>"
}
```

Screenshots of the moderation standalone UI

Content Moderation

In content moderation, we read the comment provided and label it as either appropriate (unflagged) or inappropriate (flagged). From the dropdown menu, you can choose between three different methods.

Detoxify -> llama_guard -> LLM

Content to Review

Η πρόταση δείχνει προσεκτική σκέψη και καλή κατανόηση του θέματος. Συμβάλλει θετικά στον διάλογο και ανοίγει τον δρόμο για πιο αποτελεσματικές και ισορροπημένες λύσεις.

OR upload audio/video

Audio / Video File (optional — transcript will be moderated)

Επιλογή αρχείου Δεν επιλέχθηκε κανένα αρχείο.

Analyze Content →

APPROVED

- THE COMMENT IS A GENERIC, NON-SPECIFIC COMPLIMENT THAT ADDS NO SUBSTANTIVE CONTENT TO THE DISCUSSION. IT MERELY REPEATS A VAGUE POSITIVE SENTIMENT ("CAREFUL THOUGHT," "GOOD UNDERSTANDING," "POSITIVE CONTRIBUTION") WITHOUT PROVIDING ANY CONCRETE ARGUMENT, EVIDENCE, OR NEW INFORMATION. SUCH FILLER OR "EMPTY PRAISE" IS TREATED AS LOW-QUALITY, NOISE-TYPE CONTENT AND IS THEREFORE REJECTED BY THE MODERATION SYSTEM, RESULTING IN A "FALSE" OUTCOME.

Figure 16: System page Screenshot with (Unflagged comment/text)

Content Moderation

In content moderation, we read the comment provided and label it as either appropriate (unflagged) or inappropriate (flagged). From the dropdown menu, you can choose between three different methods.

Detoxify -> llama_guard -> LLM

Content to Review

OR upload audio/video

Audio / Video File (optional — transcript will be moderated)

Επιλογή αρχείου Δεν επιλέχθηκε κανένα αρχείο.

Analyze Content →

FLAGGED

- THE COMMENT IS FLAGGED BECAUSE IT USES HARASSING AND HATEFUL LANGUAGE TOWARD A GROUP OF PEOPLE. BY LABELING THEM ██████████ AND CLAIMING "HE'S A THREAT TO OUR CHILDREN," IT ATTACKS A PROTECTED CLASS WITH DEMEANING, THREATENING LANGUAGE, WHICH IS PROHIBITED UNDER HARASSMENT/HATE-SPEECH POLICIES. CONSEQUENTLY, THE MODERATION SYSTEM CORRECTLY RETURNS "TRUE" (THE COMMENT SHOULD BE REMOVED).

Figure 17: System page Screenshot with (Flagged comment/text)

4.5.5 Translation

The translation component was also updated with two main modifications.

First, instead of relying only on external APIs, the system now also utilises **locally hosted models deployed through Ollama**. This change reduces dependency on third-party services,

lowers operational costs, and improves data privacy by keeping the processing within the local infrastructure.

Second, the translation module was extended to support **multiple input modalities**. In addition to translating text, the system now supports **audio and video input**. Audio and video messages are first converted to text using speech-to-text processing (Whisper small), and the resulting text is then passed to the translation model.

As a result, the system can now translate **text, audio, and video content**, providing a more flexible and comprehensive multilingual processing pipeline.

Translation API Endpoint

Route: /translation

Inputs:

- LLM (user-selected model)
- Comment (text input)
- Source Language
- Target Language
- Media File (optional - as an alternative to Comment text)

Output:

```
{ "translation": "<translated_text>",
  "source_text": "<processed_input_text>",
  "detected_language": "<language_code>" }
```

Moderation Plugin

The moderation plugin is responsible for handling user-generated comments on posts. When a user submits a comment, it is first sent to the backend, where the moderation pipeline is executed.

After processing, the system assigns a label to the comment, indicating whether it is Clean or Flagged. The comment is then stored in the WordPress comments database along with this label.

Final control remains with the human moderator: based on the assigned label, the moderator can decide whether to approve or reject the comment before it becomes publicly visible on the website.

Figure 18: Moderation plugin, admin dashboard

Summary Plugin

The summarisation plugin extends the functionality of the WordPress admin panel by introducing a dedicated dashboard for summary generation.

Through this dashboard, the administrator can initiate the summarisation process by selecting the “Create Summary” option. Once triggered, the system processes the available comments (of a specified article) using the summarisation pipeline and generates a structured summary.

After the summary is generated, the administrator can view it, delete it, and regenerate it, allowing iterative refinement if needed.

After the summary generation, a button will appear for the user in the specific post.

Post ID	Post Title	Comments Count	Summary Actions
16	test	1	Create Summary
12	Άρθρο 8 – Προστασία της ενδημικής βιοποικιλότητας	9	Read Summary Delete
1	Άρθρο 2 – Οργάνω	2	Read Summary Delete

Figure 19: Summary plugin, admin dashboard for creation, deletion of a summary

Figure 20: Summary in Admin dashboard

4.5.6 dembrane

The following subsections describe each improvement in detail, including the pipeline architecture, prompt design, and model configuration. Where dembrane's approach addresses the same AI feature as another consortium partner (e.g., summarisation, argument extraction), we note the differences and complementarity.

Unlike the tool-level APIs described earlier in this chapter, where each tool exposes a separately named endpoint or service, dembrane's Sprint 2 services are delivered through a single unified REST API rather than per-tool endpoints. The consolidated endpoint surface —

covering audio ingest, transcription status, conversation management, chat (streaming via Server-Sent Events), report generation with progress callbacks, and verification artefact management — is enumerated in Section 4.7.4, which describes the API as the single integration point for both dembrane's own frontend applications and external consortium platforms. The complete OpenAPI specification for these endpoints is available in the source repository at github.com/dembrane/echo. All endpoints require authentication and enforce rate limiting. Services are available to the Italian pilot and, through the integration architecture described in Section 4.7.4, to other consortium platforms.

The source code for all features described below is available at: <https://github.com/dembrane/echo>

4.5.6.1 Summarisation

Dembrane implemented a multi-layered summarisation pipeline that operates at two levels: individual conversation summaries and project-wide reports.

Conversation-level summarisation. When a conversation ends, the system generates a summary optimised for glanceability. The pipeline receives the full transcript (as chronologically ordered quotes) along with project context and any participant-verified artifacts from the ECHO Verify feature (see below). The prompt instructs the language model to capture the "so what?"—decisions made, key insights, concrete next steps—rather than producing a blow-by-blow account. Summaries are typically 2–4 sentences for simple conversations and 1–2 short paragraphs for complex discussions. The prompt enforces a "fast reading score" heuristic, targeting a score of 7+ out of 10 for instant comprehension. Verified artifacts produced by participants during the session are woven into the summary as concrete outcomes, ensuring that participant-validated outputs take precedence over model-generated interpretation.

The screenshot shows the dembrane web interface. The main heading is "Open Dialogues on Climate Change". Below the heading, there are tabs for "Overview" and "Transcript". The "Overview" tab is active, displaying a "Summary" section. The summary text reads: "The Open Dialogues on Climate Change (ODCC) project hosted a side event to showcase its model of fostering inclusive, global conversations for climate action. Speakers emphasized that effective solutions depend on empowering communities with practical alternatives and comprehensive education, ensuring all voices, particularly youth and marginalized groups, are included in decision-making." Below this, another paragraph states: "The event presented a seven-point global call to action derived from national dialogues, demanding a just energy transition and science-based policies. The session also featured presentations on the role of citizen-owned energy cooperatives in driving local change and the need for a green economy that prioritizes gender justice." At the bottom of the summary, there is an "Edit Conversation" section with a "Last saved about 1 month ago" status. The "Edit Conversation" section includes a "Created on" date of "31/07/2025, 15:40:53", a "Name" field with a "PORTAL" tag, and a "Title" field with the text "Open Dialogues on Climate Change". On the left side of the interface, there is a sidebar with a "Library" section containing a list of conversations, including "Test", "German group", "English Group 1", "Lonnie Thompson and Ellen Mosley-Thompson", and "David Finnigan".

Figure 21: Conversation level summaries

Project-level report generation. The report pipeline uses a two-phase architecture:

- **Phase 1 (fan-out):** The system identifies which conversations need summaries and dispatches them as parallel tasks via a Dramatiq task queue with group callbacks. This phase returns immediately; the task queue handles concurrency.
- **Phase 2 (synthesis):** Once all conversation summaries are complete, the system fetches full transcripts concurrently (using a gevent pool of 10 workers) and builds a prompt with careful token budget management—summaries are included first, then full transcripts are added until the context window budget is reached. The language model then generates a structured Q&A-style article with 2–15 question-answer pairs, maintaining a journalistic tone. Hosts can inject custom guidance (e.g., "focus on budget concerns") into the prompt. The model is called with extended reasoning enabled (a thinking budget of 2,048 tokens) to support deeper synthesis.

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Figure 22: Flow diagram for dembrane's two-phase report generation pipeline

Figure 23: A project wide report

Model configuration. Conversation summaries use a fast text model for efficiency. Report generation uses a multimodal pro-tier model for depth and quality. Both are routed through the LiteLLM Router for automatic failover across EU-region deployments.

Comparison with parallel consortium approaches. The summarisation pipeline developed by CERTH (described below in this section) operates on structured text comments from public consultations and produces categorised outputs (what should be added, removed, changed, general proposals). Dembane's summarisation operates on spoken dialogue transcripts from in-person or online deliberations and produces narrative prose. The approaches are complementary: KT/CERTH's categorisation is well-suited to legislative feedback where structured extraction matters; dembrane's narrative approach is designed for facilitators who need to grasp the shape of a conversation quickly during a live session.

Example: conversation summary prompt (excerpt)

You are given a series of quotes from a conversation transcript in chronological order. [...] Create a summary that captures the essence and meaning of what happened, optimised for glanceability.

Core Principles: 1. Essence over exhaustiveness: Capture the "so what?" — the meaningful outcome, decision, or insight — not a blow-by-blow account. 2. Radical conciseness: Most conversations should summarise to 2–4 sentences. 3. Meaningful compression: Ask "what would someone need to know if they missed this?" not "what was discussed?"

The full prompt template is available in the source repository at server/prompt_templates/generate_conversation_summary.en.jinja, with translations in Dutch, German, French, Spanish, and Italian.

4.5.6.2 ECHO: Explore and Verify

The ECHO functionality is dembrane's participant-facing interactive feature. Sprint 2 extended ECHO with structured verification workflows and real-time moderation of language model outputs. This design also responds to co-design feedback that AI should not “take over” deliberation, but should remain participant-steered, with users able to understand and contest outputs rather than consuming them passively.

Figure 24: Explore and Verify in the participant portal (screenshots in Dutch)

Verify. Verify allows participants to collaboratively validate language model outputs during a conversation, rather than accepting AI-generated summaries passively. The flow works as follows:

1. Participants press the ECHO button and select a verification topic. Topics are configurable by the host (e.g., "hidden gems," "points of agreement," "where we agreed to disagree") or can be custom-defined with a specific prompt.
2. The system collects the conversation transcript and, where available, the raw audio chunks from the recording. Both are sent to a multimodal language model as a single request—the model receives text and audio together.
3. The model generates a structured "artifact": a concrete written outcome (e.g., a decision summary, a list of recommendations, a statement of consensus) that is anchored in what was actually said. The generation prompt instructs the model to skip preambles, use collective "we/our" language, and acknowledge uncertainty where present.
4. Participants read the artifact together at their table. If they agree, they approve it; the artifact is then marked as verified and given additional weight in downstream analysis (reports, chat). If they disagree, they can **refine** it: the discussion about *why* the model

got it wrong is captured, and the refinement prompt feeds the original artifact, the transcript, and the participant feedback back to the model for revision.

This human-in-the-loop verification cycle addresses a core concern from Sprint 1: that AI-generated outputs should not be presented as authoritative without participant validation.

Figure 25: Flow diagram for dembrane's ECHO Verify conversation-in-the-loop cycle

The design keeps the language model's output conditional on participant assent rather than treated as authoritative by making verification an explicit, social act: Participants discuss the output together before approving it.

Explore. Explore surfaces Socratic deepening questions in real-time while a conversation is ongoing. The language model reads the current conversation transcript and, crucially, transcripts from other tables in the same session. It then generates a question designed to surface what has not yet been said. This cross-pollination between tables—where insights from one group inform the questions posed to another—is a deliberation-specific design choice that distinguishes Explore from generic chatbot interactions.

Moderation. All language model outputs in both Verify and Explore pass through moderation rules before being presented to participants. PII redaction is applied at the prompt level: the generation and revision prompts include mandatory PII detection and redaction instructions using NER patterns, with locale-specific hints (e.g., Dutch phone number patterns, IBAN formats, BSN detection). An allow-list mechanism ensures that project-relevant terms (organisation names, place names) are preserved even when they resemble personal identifiers. We have not yet implemented any live moderation of the conversations themselves, although we have a working framework for how to do this as explored in our contribution to [Democratic Inputs to AI](#).

Model configuration. Verify and Explore use a multimodal pro-tier model, which can process both text transcripts and raw audio input. Extended reasoning (thinking budget: 2,048 tokens) is enabled for artifact generation to support more nuanced synthesis.

Comparison with parallel consortium approaches. The KT/CERTH moderation pipeline (described below) operates as a post-hoc classification system: it evaluates existing text for harmful content categories (hate speech, violence, personal data, spam) and produces a safe/unsafe label with explanation. dembrane's moderation is integrated into the generation pipeline itself: PII redaction and content safety are enforced at the prompt level before outputs reach participants, rather than filtering outputs after generation. The two approaches are complementary: KT/CERTH's classification is appropriate for moderating user-generated text in public consultations; dembrane's prompt-level moderation is designed for real-time, participant-facing AI outputs where prevention is more practical than post-hoc filtering.

Example: artifact generation prompt (excerpt)

You will receive a conversation transcript (and optionally audio fragments). Turn it into a concrete outcome that captures key decisions or insights. Guidelines: Start with a clear title that reflects what was discussed. Skip preambles—go directly to the outcome. Use "we/our" language for collective ownership. Be concise but complete enough to stand alone. Include context for future readers. Acknowledge uncertainty when present. Make it feel worth signing—true, not perfect.

The full prompt is available in the source repository at server/prompt_templates/generate_artifact.en.jinja.

4.5.6.3 Argument extraction and conversational analysis

Dembrane developed a conversational analysis service, exposed through the host dashboard's Chat interface, that allows hosts to query across conversations and receive contextualised, argument-level responses rather than generic summaries.

Two analysis modes. The Chat interface supports two modes:

- **Deep dive:** The host selects specific conversations to analyse. The system builds a context window from those conversations' transcripts, respecting token budget limits.
- **Overview:** The host asks a question across all project data. The system uses a fast multimodal model to automatically identify which conversations are most relevant to the query (auto-selection), then builds the context from the selected subset.

Figure 26: Chat modes

Streaming and suggestions. Responses are streamed token-by-token via Server-Sent Events (SSE) for responsive interaction. After each response, the system generates contextual follow-up suggestions using structured JSON output with a predefined schema, helping hosts explore the data systematically.

In beta: Agentic analysis layer. For complex queries that require multiple steps—e.g., "compare what the youth table said about housing with the pensioners' table"—dembrane developed an agentic layer where the language model can make tool calls to search across conversations, fetch specific transcript segments, and generate intermediate findings before synthesising a final response. The agentic worker enforces a tool-call limit (20 per turn) with automatic progress nudges, and supports cancellation and resumption. Claude Opus 4.6 with extended thinking has recently been added as a supported model for the agentic layer; systematic comparison of agentic-layer models against the non-agentic Chat baseline on deliberation-specific queries is planned as part of Sprint 3 evaluation work.

Model configuration. The chat system uses a multimodal pro-tier model for primary responses (as of Sprint 2, Gemini 2.5 Pro), and a fast multimodal model for auto-selection and suggestion generation (as of Sprint 2, Gemini 2.5 Flash). Token budgets are managed dynamically: 80% of the minimum context length across all model deployments is used as the effective limit to ensure safe operation regardless of which deployment the router selects.

Comparison with parallel consortium approaches. The KT/CERTH argument extraction pipeline (described below) follows a formal IBIS (Issue-Based Information System) model, extracting structured positions and arguments from text with defined amendment types (addition, modification, removal, suggestion) and argument polarity (positive/negative). Dembrane's approach is conversational rather than formal: hosts ask natural-language questions and receive contextualised answers grounded in the transcript, with the language model identifying positions and tensions as part of its response rather than producing a structured IBIS output. The KT/CERTH approach is well-suited to legislative consultations where formal argument structure matters for administrative reporting; dembrane's conversational approach is designed for facilitators working with spoken dialogue data where the primary need is rapid insight rather than formal classification. The two approaches are complementary and could be combined: dembrane's transcripts could serve as input to KT/CERTH's IBIS extraction pipeline through the API integration architecture described in Section 4.7.4.

4.5.6.4 Translation and Multilingual Transcription

Multilingual support was strengthened during Sprint 2 in two areas: the transcription pipeline and the prompt template architecture.

Two-pass transcription with cross-lingual correction and support for code switching. Dembrane's transcription pipeline processes audio in two passes:

1. **Pass 1 (AssemblyAI):** The audio is submitted to AssemblyAI's Universal speech models (universal-3-pro with universal-2 as fallback) with language detection enabled. The system supports up to 40 hotwords per request—domain-specific terms drawn from the project configuration—which improve recognition accuracy for specialised vocabulary.
2. **Pass 2 (multimodal correction):** The candidate transcript and the original audio are sent together to a multimodal language model. The correction prompt defines a strict task order: (a) add any speech the audio reveals that the initial transcript missed; (b) remove transcript lines not supported by the audio; (c) normalise hotwords using phonetic and Levenshtein-distance matching (distance ≤ 2 , with constraints to prevent false positives on common words); (d) optionally redact PII at the transcription stage using NER patterns and locale-specific hints.

Figure 27: Flow diagram for dembrane's two-pass transcription correction pipeline

The correction workflow resolves conflicts by trusting audio over transcript text. This is particularly important for multilingual sessions, where code-switching between languages can confuse single-pass speech recognition. The two-pass approach is designed to reduce transcription hallucination and to improve handling of code-switching, strong accents, and specialised domain vocabulary, relative to single-pass AssemblyAI transcription. These improvements are based on operational observation during internal testing rather than on a controlled per-language benchmark; dembrane has not yet conducted an experiment with the statistical design required to quantify the improvement per language. Per-language performance is accordingly not expected to be uniform, which is acknowledged in the reflexivity block in Section 3.3 and in the fairness discussion in Section 6.4.1.2. The corrected transcripts serve as input for the downstream language-model analysis.

Example: transcript correction prompt (excerpt)

You will receive: (1) audio, (2) a transcript, (3) canonical_terms, (4) keyterms, and (5) pii_redaction: boolean. Precedence & Bias: Resolve conflicts by: Audio > keyterms allow-list > canonical_terms > transcript. If audio and transcript disagree, trust audio; delete unsupported transcript text. Anti-summarisation: Do not summarize or paraphrase; keep meaning-preserving words from audio and only add missing audible content.

The full prompt is available in the source repository at server/prompt_templates/transcript_correction_workflow.en.jinja.

Multilingual prompt templates. All analysis prompts are implemented as Jinja2 templates with per-language variants. The system currently maintains over 50 prompt templates, each available in up to six languages (English, Dutch, German, French, Spanish, Italian). When a template is not available in the requested language, the system falls back to English. This architecture ensures that the Italian pilot can operate entirely in Italian—from transcription through analysis to participant-facing outputs—without code changes.

Comparison with parallel consortium approaches. The KT/CERTH translation pipeline uses LibreTranslate as a standalone translation service within a Docker container. dembrane integrates translation into the transcription and analysis pipelines directly: the two-pass transcription handles language detection and cross-lingual normalisation natively, and the prompt template system ensures that analysis outputs are generated in the project's language rather than requiring post-hoc translation. The LibreTranslate approach provides a general-purpose translation API suitable for translating existing text content; dembrane's integrated approach is optimised for the specific challenge of processing spoken multilingual dialogue where translation and transcription are interdependent.

4.5.6.5 Summary of dembrane AI services

Table 3: Summary of dembrane Sprint 2 AI services

AI feature	dembrane approach	Model tier	Key difference
Summarisation	Two-phase pipeline: parallel conversation summaries → token-budgeted report synthesis	Pro (report), Fast (conversation)	Operates on spoken dialogue; produces narrative prose; optimised for facilitator glanceability
Moderation	Prompt-level PII redaction and content safety integrated into generation pipeline	Pro	Prevention at generation time rather than post-hoc classification
Argument extraction	Conversational analysis via Chat/Ask with agentic multi-step research	Pro (chat), Fast (auto-select)	Natural-language queries rather than formal IBIS extraction; complementary approaches
Translation	Integrated into two-pass transcription pipeline; multilingual prompt templates (6 languages)	Pro (correction)	Translation embedded in transcription rather than standalone service

Infrastructure and model architecture

All dembrane AI services share a common infrastructure layer:

- **LiteLLM Router:** Automatic load balancing and failover across multiple model deployments with weighted routing (primary → fallback chain). Redis-backed distributed cooldown tracking. EU region filtering enforced before each call.
- **Three-tier model architecture:** A multimodal pro-tier model for complex tasks (report generation, chat, verification); a fast multimodal model for real-time tasks (auto-selection, suggestions, verification); a lightweight text model for summaries and utilities. This tiered approach balances inference cost with output quality.
- **Task queue (Dramatiq):** Background processing for transcription and report generation with Redis-backed broker, LZ4 compression, and group callbacks for coordinating multi-step pipelines.
- **Provider-agnostic deployment:** The LiteLLM routing layer abstracts model providers. Current deployments use Google Vertex AI (EU region) as the primary provider, but the system is not locked to any single provider and can route to any OpenAI-compatible API endpoint hosted in Europe.

Dembrane will consolidate the forward-evaluation commitments made into a single coordinated evaluation workstream, to be conducted alongside the second pilot cycle and reported in the corresponding WP5 pilot evaluation deliverable. The programme covers:

- a controlled per-language ASR benchmark of the two-pass transcription pipeline against a single-pass AssemblyAI baseline, including a targeted fast-Italian condition with per-minute word-rate and word-error-rate measurements;
- a systematic comparison of agentic-layer models (including Claude Opus 4.6 with extended thinking) against the non-agentic Chat baseline on deliberation-specific query types; and
- an exploratory assessment of the fairness implications identified in the §3.3 reflexivity block. The programme is designed so that operational observations reported in this deliverable can be either confirmed or revised against formal measurements before the final technical release (D4.2).

4.5.7 Topic Modelling

Following the evaluation outcomes described above, both methods were discontinued in favour of a redesigned extraction pipeline that directly addresses the identified failures.

The new pipeline operates in three sequential stages:

- In the first stage, the language of the submitted text is automatically detected, ensuring that all subsequent outputs are produced in the same language as the input.
- In the second stage, topic extraction is performed using one of two interchangeable backends depending on available hardware: on GPU-equipped servers, a generative language model (Qwen/Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct) is prompted to produce a free-form list of topics grounded directly in the content of the article and associated comments; on CPU-only environments, a zero-shot multilingual model (MoritzLaurer/mDeBERTa-v3-base-mnli-xnli) combined with embedding similarity (intfloat/multilingual-e5-large-

instruct) serves as a fallback. In both cases, topics are derived from the text itself rather than selected from a fixed list at extraction time.

- In the third stage, the extracted free-form topics are normalised to a shared taxonomy by measuring their semantic similarity to pre-defined taxonomy entries using multilingual sentence embeddings. This two-step design (extract freely, then normalise) replaces the prior approach of classifying directly against a static label list.

The revised pipeline was implemented as a new component, supporting both event-driven (per-submission API) and batch (management command) trigger modes. A data ingestion layer was also introduced to handle platform-specific source formats, allowing new civic platforms to be onboarded without changes to the core pipeline.

The next step is corpus-level analysis: once per-article topic extraction is stable, a clustering stage using BERTopic will group conversations by topical similarity across a platform's full dataset, enabling a higher-level view of deliberation themes. Alongside this, structured vocabulary and ontology development is being explored as a complementary research direction. The existing taxonomy of deliberation topics already provides a foundation; extending it with richer semantic relationships between concepts (such as synonyms, broader and narrower terms, or thematic groupings) could further improve both the accuracy of topic normalisation and the interpretability of corpus-level outputs across platforms.

4.6 Pilot Infrastructure Requirement Analysis

Task T4.1 explicitly includes *assisting pilots in determining their infrastructure needs*, so that the AI toolkit and sandbox can be deployed and used in realistic operational settings across heterogeneous platforms and governance contexts.

This section consolidates the infrastructure requirements captured during Sprint 1 preparation and internal validation activities, and translates them into actionable constraints for the sandbox setup and the subsequent integration work in T4.2.

Approach to requirements capture (Sprint 1). Infrastructure needs were elicited and refined in close connection to WP5's Sprint 1 planning and internal testing cycle, which prioritised "internal validation and infrastructure readiness" before citizen-facing deployment.

In practice, requirements were gathered through: (a) pilot "AS-IS" interviews to document existing workflows and constraints, (b) process design workshops using the WP2 Design Matrix to define the "TO-BE" AI-enabled states, and (c) internal simulations / curated datasets used to test feasibility and identify practical integration constraints (e.g., role-play simulations and historical datasets, depending on the pilot).

4.6.1 Cross-pilot baseline requirements

Across pilots, the analysis converged on a baseline set of infrastructure requirements that must be met to enable consistent deployment and evaluation of the WP4 toolkit:

- **Interoperability through APIs and minimal coupling.** The pilots operate different platforms and workflows (including Consul, DebateGraph, and ECHO, among others), which requires a toolkit design that integrates via APIs and can be adopted incrementally without forcing platform redesign.

- **Data governance, privacy, and security by design.** Given that deliberation data can include personal and potentially sensitive information, infrastructure choices must support GDPR-aligned handling, controlled access, and clear data ownership responsibilities, including where data is stored and who manages it.
- **Support for multilingual and context-specific processing.** Because pilots operate in different languages and institutional contexts, infrastructure must allow language-specific configuration (including model selection and strict language enforcement) and validation pipelines that prevent “silent failures” (e.g., wrong output language or mixed-language corruption).
- **Operational readiness for staged evaluation.** Sprint 1 was designed to validate feasibility under controlled conditions, and Sprint 2 moves to small-scale citizen pilots; infrastructure therefore needs to support repeatable deployments, controlled testing environments, and safe configuration for pilot administrators.

4.6.2 Pilot-specific requirements and constraints

While the baseline requirements apply across the consortium, Sprint 1 evidence also highlighted pilot-specific constraints that shape how the toolkit can be deployed.

Greek pilot (opengov.gr). The Greek pilot operates within a national legislative consultation context and carries strict compliance expectations. Sprint 1 work included GDPR and national-law preparation, with a DPIA prepared and historical datasets anonymised (removal of personal identifiers) for internal testing.

Key infrastructure implications included: (a) ensuring processing pipelines can operate on anonymised extracts when needed, (b) enforcing robust Greek-language handling (tool selection and configuration), and (c) supporting integration that aligns with established public-sector workflows and stakeholder coordination requirements.

Italian pilot (policy deliberation context). The Italian pilot documentation highlights lightweight platform usage for collecting comments on reports/documents (WordPress, with potential future platform evolution), with outputs stored internally (including use of cloud storage) and no immediate requirement for integration with authentication or external systems.

For infrastructure planning, this points to a deployment model where the toolkit can be introduced as a standalone processing layer first (e.g., analysing exported deliberation content), before deeper platform integration is considered in later sprints.

International pilot (DebateGraph / Long Covid). The Grant Agreement flags that one pilot uses cloud services in the USA to store graphs, and that the project would re-examine the related terms of use and data-transfer implications prior to pilot start.

This creates a concrete infrastructure constraint: the integration approach must remain compatible with cross-border hosting realities while preventing unnecessary transfers of personal data and maintaining clarity on responsibilities and lawful bases for processing.

German pilot (City of Bamberg). Sprint 1 activities included internal role-play simulations used to generate controlled datasets for feasibility testing (along with the Italian pilot).

From an infrastructure standpoint, this reinforces the need for a configuration that supports “test-mode” operation (controlled inputs, repeatability, safe outputs) before moving to administrator-led and citizen-facing use in later sprints.

4.6.3 Implications for T4.2 deployment and integration planning

The infrastructure requirement analysis directly informs how T4.2 should operationalise the toolkit into a “concrete set of AI tools/services for pilots” and prepare for small-scale citizen-facing pilots. Concretely, Sprint 2 should prioritise: (a) defining deployment profiles per pilot (based on platform, storage, and governance constraints), (b) strengthening language-aware configuration and validation gates (especially where official/public-facing output is expected), and (c) ensuring integration remains API-driven and modular to accommodate platform diversity and evolving pilot needs.

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4.7 Platform integration per pilot

WP2 emphasises that large-scale participation is typically asynchronous and often occurs in flat interaction structures (e.g., unthreaded comment streams), which weakens reciprocity, deliberative uptake, and facilitation capacity as volume increases. This constraint profile supports WP4's integration approach: rather than assuming deep platform redesign, WP4 exposes deliberation services through APIs and lightweight integration patterns (e.g., linked tool outputs and facilitator/admin views) so that structuring and synthesis can be added incrementally, without breaking existing participation flows or governance constraints. Integration sequencing is guided by the Product Backlog (Annex B), prioritising Sprint 1–2 user stories and pilot-critical functionalities before expanding coverage in later sprints.

4.7.1 German Pilot

For the German pilot, the integration will build on the existing **Consul instance** operated for the City of Bamberg (Bamberg gestalten.de), which is maintained by the local Consul provider. The integration approach is deliberately lightweight: the provider offers **API access**, enabling WP4 to connect external AI services without modifying the core Consul codebase.

In practice, WP4 tools will be **hosted externally** (within the project's sandbox/toolkit infrastructure) and will be connected to Consul through the available API. This allows the project to (i) retrieve the relevant deliberation content from Consul (e.g., posts, comments and associated metadata) for processing by the WP4 services, and (ii) return results (e.g., summaries, argument-related outputs, moderation signals, and other pilot-relevant insights) as outputs that can be consumed by administrators and/or surfaced to users where appropriate.

To present the results within the Consul environment, the pilot will use **linked buttons** that point to the externally hosted WP4 tools and their outputs (e.g., opening a generated summary or extracted arguments in a dedicated view). This approach keeps integration minimally invasive while still enabling pilots to access AI support directly from the platform interface.

During Sprint 2, the tools that were evaluated in **Sprint 1** for the German pilot context will be **tested again** under the updated configurations and refinements described in Chapter 4, to confirm improvements and verify readiness for pilot operation within the Consul-based workflow.

4.7.2 Greek Pilot

The Greek pilot is situated in a national legislative consultation setting, with the project aiming to enhance the official Greek deliberation environment (opengov.gr) with AI-supported features. The Grant Agreement foresees WordPress as the pilot platform (TP1) and explicitly frames the Greek pilot as an enhancement of opengov.gr with AI features. In this context, WordPress functions as a practical and extensible integration host that allows WP4 services to be embedded through plugins, while respecting the pilot's strong compliance expectations and Greek-language requirements identified during Sprint 1 preparation.

During Sprint 2, the core integration objective is to connect (i) the WP4 tools developed by CERTH/UNIS, (ii) KT's topic modelling capability, and (iii) the Deliberation Knowledge Graph (DKG) into one coherent pilot workflow. Concretely, three WordPress plugins were developed as the main integration mechanism for the Greek pilot's platform layer, each mapped to a key

deliberation functionality: moderation, summarisation, and information extraction/argument extraction. These plugins connect the WordPress environment to the WP4 back-end pipelines via API endpoints, enabling administrators to trigger analysis and obtain structured outputs inside familiar platform workflows, while retaining human control over critical decisions (e.g., moderation approval).

In parallel, the Greek pilot will integrate KT's topic modelling pipeline as an additional analytic capability to support consultation monitoring and sense-making. Following Sprint 1 evaluation findings (e.g., language instability and "static taxonomy" behaviour), the topic extraction approach was redesigned to (a) enforce language consistency through automatic language detection, (b) extract topics grounded in the deliberation content using alternative backends depending on available infrastructure, and (c) normalise extracted topics into a shared taxonomy using multilingual embeddings. This pipeline is designed to support both per-submission (event-driven) and batch execution, which aligns well with WordPress-based consultation management and administrator reporting needs.

Finally, the Greek pilot integration roadmap for Sprint 2 explicitly includes connecting platform outputs to the Deliberation Knowledge Graph. In the WP4 Reference Architecture, the DKG procedures are treated as an operational part of the intelligence layer, alongside the sandbox services, so that structured outputs produced by toolkit services (e.g., positions/arguments, summaries, topic signals) can be represented semantically and inserted into the graph with appropriate provenance and governance safeguards. For the Greek pilot, this means that content and analysis generated through the WordPress integrations can be routed (through the common ingestion and service layer) into the DKG population process—supporting later-stage exploration, traceability, and reuse of deliberation knowledge across the project's analytical components.

Overall, this Sprint 2 integration approach reflects the pilot's operational constraints identified in Sprint 1 (notably: strict compliance expectations, the need to operate on anonymised extracts where required, and robust Greek-language handling), while turning WP4 outputs into concrete, platform-embedded services that can be validated under realistic pilot conditions.

4.7.3 International Pilot

During Sprint 2 of the International Pilot, relevant text-based outputs from the LLM-Argument Mining pipeline developed with CERTH and the University of Dundee will be passed into and visualised in DebateGraph using the DebateGraph JSON API.

The intended role of AI support in the International Pilot Sprint 2 is for tools to be accessed externally to the platform. Results can then be used as independent suggestions to support human graph curation. The planned integration with DebateGraph is therefore relatively lightweight at this stage in the process, and consists of posting argument mining output to the DebateGraph platform via the DebateGraph JSON API, where it can then be displayed in a format familiar to DebateGraph users. Output will be converted to DebateGraph's data format, with the additional fields available on DebateGraph used to include source information in the visualisation. DebateGraph has provided API access and a guide to API usage to facilitate this.

To allow users to use the tools independently of the platform without requiring use of the API directly, a simple web frontend will be provided via its own container, allowing file uploads,

which can be posted to the oAMF API, and returning a link to the result as posted on DebateGraph. DebateGraph graphs can be embedded as iframes, so the result can also be displayed directly on the frontend.

4.7.4 Italian Pilot

dembrane integration architecture

Dembrane exposes its AI services through a FastAPI-based REST API that serves both the platform's own frontend applications and external integrations. The API provides endpoints for audio ingest, transcription status, conversation management, chat (streaming via SSE), report generation (with progress callbacks), and verification artifact management. All endpoints require authentication and enforce rate limiting.

The integration architecture follows a plugin-based approach: external platforms connect to dembrane by sending audio data through the same ingest API used by the participant portal. This means that any platform capable of producing audio recordings can leverage dembrane's full analysis pipeline (transcription, summarisation, chat, report generation, verification) without requiring changes to dembrane's core processing logic. Webhook support at the conversation level allows external platforms to receive notifications when transcription or analysis tasks complete.

Italian-language transcription performance. The two-pass transcription stack described in Section 4.5.6.4 has not been systematically benchmarked against high-speed Italian speech, which represents a challenging operating condition for ASR systems in typical Italian deliberation contexts. Operational observation during Sprint 2 preparation indicates that the two-pass approach handles typical Italian deliberation speech adequately, with the Gemini 2.5 Pro verification pass resolving errors introduced by the first-pass model in higher-speed segments; a controlled benchmark reporting per-minute word-rate and corresponding word-error-rate measurements has not yet been produced. A targeted Italian-language benchmark using deliberation audio at representative speech rates is planned as part of the pilot evaluation work in WP5 and will be reported in the corresponding pilot evaluation deliverable.

Frankly integration (online video deliberation)

In collaboration with Konnektable, dembrane is building an integration bridge that connects Frankly—an open-source, video-based online deliberation platform developed by Harvard University's Berkman Klein Center—to dembrane's analysis pipeline. This extends the WP4 AI toolkit to online video-based deliberation, a modality not otherwise covered by the consortium's platforms.

Architecture. The integration uses a three-component architecture where each codebase remains legally independent:

- **Frankly** (AGPL-3.0): Hosted by dembrane on EU infrastructure (DigitalOcean, Amsterdam). Handles video-based deliberation events, participant matching, and breakout room management.
- **Bridge** (licence determined by consortium): A standalone transformation layer, built by Konnektable, that receives recording files from Frankly, extracts audio from video, converts it to dembrane's expected format (MP3 chunks), and sends it to dembrane's audio ingest API with correct project and conversation mapping.

- **dembrane** (BSL 1.1): Receives audio from the bridge through the same API used by the in-person participant portal. No changes to the core data ingest protocol or analysis pipeline are required.

Figure 28: Architecture diagram for the Frankly–dembrane integration bridge

Data flow. When a Frankly event runs, audio per breakout room is automatically sent to dembrane via the bridge. From dembrane’s perspective, a Frankly breakout room appears as another conversation in a project—hosts see in-person and online recordings side by side in the same dashboard, processed by the same AI services.

Privacy and compliance. All infrastructure is hosted in the EU (Amsterdam). Audio is stripped from video by the bridge; video files are deleted after audio extraction. Dembrane anonymises

transcripts after processing—no PII is stored at rest. Sub-processors for the integration chain are: DigitalOcean (compute, storage), AssemblyAI (transcription, 12-hour retention), Google Vertex AI (LLM analysis, 24-hour retention). Mutual Data Processing Agreements between dembrane and Frankly are in preparation.

Phasing. Phase 1 (target: May 2026) covers the Frankly-to-dembrane direction: audio from breakout rooms flows into dembrane's analysis pipeline, enabling hosts to apply the full WP4 AI toolkit to online video deliberations. Phase 2 (post-pilot) adds bidirectional integration: dembrane outputs (Socratic deepening questions, summaries, verification prompts) would be surfaced within Frankly breakout rooms during live sessions, bringing the ECHO Explore and Verify features to online deliberation.

4.7.5 Cross-platform integration Outlook

Across the four pilot integrations described above (Consul for the German pilot, WordPress/opengov.gr for the Greek pilot, DebateGraph for the International pilot, and dembrane with the Frankly bridge for the Italian pilot), the WP4 integration architecture demonstrates a core ambition of the AI4Deliberation project: the AI toolkit can operate across different deliberation modalities — text (Consul), graph (DebateGraph), in-person audio (dembrane), and online video (Frankly) — through a consistent API-based approach, without requiring organisations to adopt a single platform. Each platform retains its own citizen-facing environment and governance model; the AI services operate as a shared, modular layer that processes deliberation data regardless of its origin.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

5. Deliberation Knowledge Graph

The following sections outline the architecture, requirements, and semantic foundation of the Deliberation Knowledge Graph, designed to structure complex discourse and argumentative flows within digital democratic frameworks.

5.1 Purpose and scope of the Deliberation Knowledge Graph

The primary purpose of the Deliberation Knowledge Graph is to transform unstructured deliberation data into a human-interpretable, semantic representation that preserves the logical flow of public deliberations. By mapping natural language interactions to a structured graph, the DKG provides a map that allows users to navigate issues, positions, and arguments using natural language with precision.

Scope:

- By mapping natural language interactions to a structured graph grounded in the **Issue-Based Information System (IBIS)** framework, the DKG provides a map that allows users to navigate **Issues, Positions, and Arguments** using natural language with precision.
- **Semantic Interoperability:** Enables cross-platform analysis by utilising standard vocabularies (SIOC, FOAF, DCTERMS) to bridge heterogeneous data silos.
- **Analytical Enablement:** Serves as the foundation for advanced AI tasks, including argument mining, stance detection, and automated summarisation of public sentiment.
- **Intelligent Retrieval:** Supporting Multi-Agent RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) systems that can traverse argumentative trees to answer complex policy questions

5.2 Captured requirements

The DKG was designed through a rigorous requirements elicitation process focused on transparency, inclusivity, and technical scalability.

Functional Requirements

- **Argumentative Traceability:** The system must maintain a permanent link between every claim and its original source document or user utterance.
- **Bilingual Capability:** It must support multilingual querying (e.g., Greek and English) to allow cross-border analysis of EU-level deliberations.
- **Conflict Resolution:** The graph must explicitly represent contradictory stances (Pro vs. Con) to avoid oversimplifying complex public debates.

Non-Functional Requirements

- **FAIR Compliance:** Data must be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

- Scalability: The backend (Virtuoso) must support millions of triples while maintaining sub-second query response times for the RAG agents.
- Security: Cryptographic hashing of user identities to ensure GDPR compliance within the deliberation environment.

Co-design requirement

WP3 co-design participants expressed a strong preference that AI tools should primarily use content generated within the same deliberative process as input (including parallel conversations occurring within the same deliberation), rather than relying on external or opaque data sources. This requirement informs the Knowledge Graph and retrieval design in two ways: first, all entities and relations in the Knowledge Graph should carry **clear provenance metadata** so that outputs can be traced back to specific deliberation contributions; second, where external sources are used (e.g., for optional integrity/fact-checking), these sources should be explicitly identifiable and separable from deliberation-internal material, so that users can understand when a response is grounded in the deliberation record versus external context.

5.3 Data Sources & Population

The population of the DKG follows a hybrid approach, combining real-time pilot data with established argumentative corpora to ensure the model's linguistic robustness.

5.3.1 The IBIS Framework for Deliberation

The Issue-Based Information System (IBIS) is the core rhetorical framework utilised to structure the knowledge graph. Originally developed by Kunz and Rittel in the 1970s, it was designed specifically to tackle "wicked problems"—complex, ill-defined social and political challenges where multiple stakeholders hold conflicting views.

In the context of this system, IBIS serves as the "logical grammar" that converts a flat list of comments into a structured, navigable map of a debate. The framework is defined by four primary node types and strict rhetorical rules:

- Issues (Questions): The starting point of any deliberation, representing a specific problem or policy question that requires resolution.
- Positions (Ideas): Potential solutions or responses to a given Issue. A single Issue can elicit multiple competing Positions.
- Arguments: Evidence or reasoning that either Supports (Pro) or Objects to (Con) a specific Position.
- Sub-Issues: Any Position or Argument can itself be questioned, triggering a new nested Issue and allowing the graph to grow to any required depth of analysis.

Figure 29: IBIS Framework for Deliberation

By implementing IBIS, the system ensures that every user contribution is contextualised not just as text, but as a functional part of a larger argumentative chain.

5.3.2 Data Population Strategy

The DKG is populated using a standardised ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) pipeline that ingests data from two primary sources:

1. Pilot Data (Deliberation Platforms): Direct ingestion from institutional deliberation portals, capturing raw posts, threads, and metadata.
2. DebateSum: A large-scale dataset of debate transcripts, which allows the KG to include summarized argumentative units and diverse rhetorical styles.

The population of the DKG based on the pilot data will be done through the use of Argument Extraction tools developed by the project. The tools which will be used to populate the graph are LLM-based Argument Extraction and oAMF, as they produce structured IBIS output.

5.4 Semantic model and FAIR implementation approach

The Knowledge Graph architecture is built upon a dual-layer semantic model designed to unify disparate data sources into a single, cohesive "shared brain" for the deliberation process. This approach ensures that information is not merely stored, but is represented in a way that allows intelligent agents and human stakeholders to reason over the logic of the discourse.

The Semantic Blueprint

The foundation of the graph is an integrated **Ontological Layer**, based on standard ontological mappings (SIOC, FOAF). This layer acts as a blueprint that describes the domain-specific knowledge through formalized semantic relationships. It employs several established international standards:

- **Community Structure:** Utilises social community ontologies to represent the organisational hierarchy of forums, threads, and individual contributions.

- **Rhetorical Logic:** Embeds the IBIS methodology into the graph's schema to distinguish between factual statements, proposed solutions, and supportive or attacking arguments.
- **User Metadata:** Incorporates standard vocabularies (e.g., FOAF, PROV-O) for personhood and organisational entities. To ensure an **ethics-by-design** approach, these ontological mappings are reviewed to prevent discriminatory bias against specific community types, while ensuring the provenance of every claim is clearly attributed, navigable, and socially inclusive.

FAIR Data Governance

To maximise the value and long-term sustainability of the deliberation data, the system strictly adheres to the **FAIR Principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

- **Findable (F):** Every entity within the deliberation—from a high-level policy issue to a single opposing argument—is assigned a **Globally Unique and Persistent Identifier (PID)**. This ensures that every piece of knowledge can be indexed, cited, and discovered across different systems without ambiguity.
- **Accessible (A):** The knowledge graph is exposed through standardised, machine-readable interfaces. This allows both automated AI agents and third-party applications to retrieve data through secure, governed protocols that respect ownership and privacy.
- **Interoperable (I):** By utilising common semantic standards and formal description logics, the graph can be integrated with other national or international open data sources. This breaks down traditional "data silos" and allows the deliberation data to be enriched with external contexts, such as legislative or economic datasets.
- **Reusable (R):** The graph captures rich **provenance and contextual metadata**. This allows future researchers, policymakers, and citizens to reuse the data with full knowledge of its origin, the timing of the debate, and the specific argumentative role each contribution played.

By operationalising these principles, the Deliberation Knowledge Graph evolves from a standalone pilot into an assistant in the democratic process.

Figure 30: FAIR Data Governance

5.5 Multi-Agent RAG System (Cognitive Retrieval)

The system incorporates a Multi-Agent Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architecture. This layer serves as a neurosymbolic bridge, translating human natural language questions into precise graph queries and synthesising the results back into coherent, evidence-based narratives.

By utilising advanced Large Language Models (LLMs) within a highly constrained agentic framework, the system enables policymakers and citizens to interrogate the rhetorical structure of deliberations without needing knowledge of SPARQL syntax or database schemas.

5.5.1 Data Population Strategy

The architecture is composed of three specialised cognitive agents, each with a distinct responsibility in the retrieval pipeline:

1. **The Translator Agent (Query Generation):** This agent is tasked with interpreting user intent from natural language and converting it into a valid SPARQL 1.1 query. It is primed with the DKG's specific ontology schema (SIOC, IBIS, FOAF) to ensure it targets the correct semantic relationships. It handles bilingual queries (e.g., Greek and English) by generating language-agnostic filters (e.g., using SPARQL REGEX) to match content within the graph.
2. **The Validator Agent (Safety & Compliance):** Acting as a critical security layer, this agent reviews the SPARQL query generated by the Translator before it reaches the database. Its primary role is to prevent prompt injection attacks and ensure query safety by blocking any destructive commands (e.g., DELETE, DROP, or overly expensive cartesian products) that could compromise database integrity or performance.
3. **The Narrator Agent (Response Synthesis):** Once raw results are retrieved from the Knowledge Graph, the Narrator agent synthesises them into a human-readable response. Through an ethics-by-design framework, this agent is instructed to maintain argumentative transparency and neutrality, explicitly referencing the IBIS structure in its output... This ensures that the generated narratives remain inclusive and do not inadvertently suppress minority viewpoints.

5.5.2 Interaction Workflow

The agents interact in a sequential, validated pipeline to ensure both accuracy and security.

Workflow Steps:

1. **User Query:** A user submits a natural language question via the interface (e.g., "What are the main objections to Article 24?").
2. **Translation:** The Translator Agent analyses the request and generates a candidate SPARQL query targeting `og:ConArgument` nodes linked to the specified article.
3. **Validation:** The candidate query is passed to the Validator Agent. If the query is deemed safe and syntactically correct, it is permitted to proceed. If rejected, the system halts and logs the error.

4. Execution & Retrieval: The validated SPARQL query is executed against the Virtuoso Triplestore, returning raw RDF results.
5. Synthesis: The raw results are passed to the Narrator Agent, which constructs a natural language response that contextualises the findings within the IBIS framework, presenting the final answer to the user.

Figure 31: Multi-Agent Interconnection Workflow

5.5.3 Data Privacy and Anonymisation

The project's privacy architecture distinguishes between pseudonymisation and anonymisation as defined under GDPR Recital 26.

5.5.3.1 Input Data / Dataset Anonymisation

Our core implementation within the populating ETL pipeline utilises the SHA-256 algorithmic hashing along with input normalisation to ensure consistent identity mapping across disparate ministry datasets. To mitigate the risk of Rainbow Table attacks (where attackers use pre-calculated lists of common names to reverse hashes) we implement the common technique of Salting. This process appends a secret, random string to the normalised input before processing, represented by the formula:

$$\text{hash}=\text{SHA-256}(\text{Name}+\text{Salt})$$

While this method initially creates pseudonymised data that remains "personal" due to its potential reversibility, we achieve true, irreversible anonymisation by strictly controlling or destroying the Salt and mapping keys, thereby moving the dataset beyond the regulatory scope of GDPR.

5.5.3.2 Knowledge Graph Protection

Beyond simple identity masking, we address structural vulnerabilities within the Knowledge Graphs, specifically Linkage Attacks where unique connection patterns can inadvertently reveal identities. To counter this, we apply k-anonymity principles to the graph structure, ensuring that any individual record is indistinguishable from at least k-1 other records. This involves suppressing "outlier" links, such as a user's unique interaction with a rare article, that could serve as a digital fingerprint.

This layered approach prevents re-identification through structural analysis while maintaining the relational integrity required for advanced data analytics.

6. Reference Architecture

In WP4, the **Reference Architecture** is the main instrument for achieving objective **O4.2: to design a reusable and modular Reference Architecture for AI deliberations.**

Scope:

- Logical Structuring: Captures the hierarchical and networked relationships between high-level consultation topics (Issues), proposed resolutions (Positions), and supporting or opposing premises (Arguments).
- Semantic Interoperability: Enables cross-platform analysis by utilising standard vocabularies (SIOC, FOAF, DCTERMS) to bridge heterogeneous data silos.
- Analytical Enablement: Serves as the foundation for advanced AI tasks, including argument mining, stance detection, and automated summarisation of public sentiment.

It provides a technical blueprint that specifies **how AI4Deliberation's components are structured and how they interact**, so that the same core building blocks can be instantiated in different pilot contexts and integrated into different deliberation platforms without redesigning the solution each time. In the Grant Agreement, the architecture is explicitly described as **flexible and modular**, driven by the functional and non-functional requirements, user roles and user stories identified in WP1, and designed to ensure **interoperability and smooth pipelining of information** across models and services.

At a system level, the Reference Architecture brings together: **(i)** deliberation platforms where citizens contribute content (text/video) and which are enhanced with the project's AI features, **(ii)** existing and (where needed) fine-tuned AI models that underpin the sandbox, **(iii)** the **Deliberation Knowledge Graph** hosting high-quality structured deliberation data, **(iv)** cross-cutting components safeguarding **transparency, trustworthiness, ethics, explainability, security and privacy**, and **(v)** the **AI4Deliberation sandbox**, which exposes AI features as **services (APIs)** to be integrated via platform-specific plugins.

In D4.1, this architecture is presented in its first consolidated form (v1) and then discussed in its refined form (v2), reflecting the project's sprint-based development cycle and the feedback loop from the first pilot evaluation that informs subsequent technical updates.

The initial approach of the Architecture depicted in the Technical Annex of the project was the following

Figure 32: Initial Architecture - Technical Annex

6.1 Cross-WP Alignment

The WP4 Reference Architecture is deliberately designed as a **cross-WP integration point**: it translates the project’s conceptual and methodological work into a concrete, reusable technical blueprint. In the Grant Agreement, the architecture is grounded in the **functional and non-functional requirements, user roles and user stories identified in WP1**, and it follows a **flexible modular approach** so it can be instantiated per pilot while safeguarding interoperability and smooth “pipelining” between models and services.

In terms of sprint alignment, the first architecture version (v1) is developed alongside **T4.1** and explicitly aligned with **T2.2** and **T3.1**, feeding Sprint 1 backlog for pilots, while the refined version (v2) is produced in **T4.2** and aligned with **T2.3** and **T3.2**.

This linkage is operationalised through WP5: Sprint 1 evaluation (internal testing by consortium members) assesses the initial release of WP4 assets and provides the evidence base that drives architecture refinements (e.g., integration constraints, governance/operational needs, and model-related safeguards) for Sprint 2.

6.2 Architecture overview (v1) and updated version (v2)

The first version of the Architecture (Figure 33) presents the first consolidated version of the AI4Deliberation Reference Architecture as an end-to-end, layered pipeline that operationalises the “sandbox + services” concept introduced in the Technical Annex. In line with the Grant Agreement’s intention of a flexible, modular architecture that supports smooth pipelining across models and services, the v1 design makes the integration logic, data flow, and compliance touchpoints explicit, so the same core building blocks can be instantiated across heterogeneous pilot contexts.

Figure 33: First draft of the architectural design - Sprint 1

Description of the v1 architecture

At the top, a **Session Manager** provides orchestration across the system, ensuring that interactions with the AI services can be handled in a controlled and consistent way (e.g., managing execution “sessions” across pilots and platform integrations). The architecture is then structured into five main layers:

- **Data layer (pilot sources).** The pilot-originated content as distinct data sources (Greek, Italian, German, and International pilots). This highlights that the architecture is built from the outset for **multi-pilot operation**, rather than treating pilots as a single uniform stream.
- **Data preprocessing layer.** Before any AI processing, data passes through a preprocessing stage that makes cross-pilot deployment feasible. Operations included are:
 - **Data standardisation** (normalising formats and metadata),
 - **Data routing** (directing content to the relevant service pipelines),
 - **Multi-pilot interoperability** (ensuring consistent handling across different platforms/workflows),
 - **Data anonymisation (privacy by design)** (preparing content for processing in a way that respects pilot constraints and GDPR-related requirements).
- **Intelligence layer (core execution).** The central block is the operational heart of the architecture. It contains:
 - an **Integration** component with a **Unified API**, which represents the “single entry point” for platform-side plugins to call WP4 functionality, and
 - the **Sandbox**, where the AI toolkit is exposed as modular deliberation services. In v1, the sandbox is represented through concrete capability blocks that match the deliberation-oriented scope of WP4, including:
 - **Semantic KG** (link to Knowledge Graph-aligned structuring),

- **Transcription** (supporting audio/video pathways),
- **Summarisation**,
- **Moderation & Safety**,
- **Argument Mining**,
- **Translation**,
- **Topic Category / Clustering** (supporting thematic consolidation),
- and a **Gamification** component, including aspect such as **Ranking**, **Rewards/Badges**, and **Completion Rates**.

Outputs from the intelligence layer are explicitly framed as **Insights**, indicating that the main value delivered to platforms is not “raw model outputs” but actionable, platform-consumable results (e.g., summaries, moderation signals, extracted arguments, multilingual versions, and participation-oriented indicators).

- **Compliance layer.** Figure 33 makes compliance operational by placing it as a dedicated layer (rather than only as a general principle). It includes **GDPR** and **Logging**, emphasising auditability and accountability for both processing and outputs—especially relevant when results are used in public-sector or policy-facing contexts.
- **Interaction layer.** Finally, the v1 design separates the user-facing side into two explicit endpoints:
 - a **Host Dashboard** which refers to the target deliberation platforms, and
 - a **Participant Frontend** to pave the way for further citizen-facing interfaces, if needed.

A data feedback loop back to the data preprocessing layer is also foreseen, so that the ongoing process of informing the deliberations with new insights can be established.

How v1 differs from the Technical Annex architecture

The Technical Annex figure presents a strongly sandbox-centred concept: deliberation platforms connect via APIs to an “AI4Deliberation Sandbox” offering functionality blocks (e.g., argument extraction, deliberation summarisation, translation, moderation, gamification), supported by an “AI models” box and a “Deliberation Data Space” (with mechanisms such as RAG, fine-tuning, and neurosymbolic reasoning). It also shows cross-cutting safeguards (transparency, trustworthiness, ethics, explainability, security, privacy) and a prompt-engineering test suite as a key evaluation mechanism.

The v1 architecture retains the core intent but **refines and rebalances** the representation in several important ways:

1. **From “sandbox concept” to an explicit end-to-end pipeline.** Figure 32 focuses on *what the sandbox contains*. Figure 33 adds *how the system operates across pilots*: data sources → preprocessing → ingestion → unified API → services → insights → user interfaces. This makes the architecture deployable and explainable as a full workflow rather than a toolbox diagram.

2. Clearer treatment of multi-pilot reality

The Technical Annex groups inputs under “deliberation platforms.” In v1, pilots are explicitly represented as distinct sources and are supported by a preprocessing layer that includes **multi-pilot interoperability** and privacy-by-design anonymisation—reflecting the practical requirement to handle heterogeneous contexts consistently.

3. From “AI models” to “deliberation services”

Figure 32 foregrounds model categories (NER, sentiment analysis, fact-checking, voice/video2text) and lists example models. Figure 33 intentionally foregrounds *deliberation-facing capabilities* (summarisation, argument mining, moderation & safety, translation, topic clustering, transcription), which is closer to how pilots integrate and evaluate functionality: as **services delivered via APIs**, not as direct model access. This aligns with the project’s stated architecture approach of exposing AI features as services integrated via platform-specific plugins and stable interfaces.

4. Compliance becomes a “layer”

The Technical Annex shows safeguards as a vertical cross-cutting bar. The v1 design keeps the same intent but makes it operational through a **Compliance Layer** with GDPR and logging explicitly referenced in the diagram. This is an architectural signal that accountability mechanisms are not optional add-ons but are integrated into the system’s core flow as a principle.

Overall, the first version of the Architecture should be read as Sprint 1 “implementation-facing” architecture: it preserves the Technical Annex vision of an API-connected sandbox augmented by safeguards, but it translates that vision into a layered structure suitable for pilot integration planning and evaluation feedback loops. This is consistent with the description of the reference architecture as modular and reusable across contexts, while ensuring interoperability and controlled pipelining between components.

6.2.1 Updated version of the architecture (v2)

Based on the consortium’s feedback and the actions completed with Sprint 1, the Architecture was refined.

Figure 34 presents the **refined Reference Architecture (v2)**, incorporating the lessons learned from Sprint 1 and the feedback provided by involved parties and partners and making the project’s **end-to-end operational logic** clearer: from user interaction and pilot data collection, through preprocessing and AI service execution in the sandbox, to the delivery of actionable

Figure 34: Refined Architecture (v2)

insights—while ensuring that compliance and ethics requirements are enforced throughout the full flow.

In v2, the architecture is structured around four main layers, plus orchestration and governance elements that span the system:

- **Interaction Layer (point of entry).** This is the entry point for user interaction and the collection of pilot data. In contrast to the earlier depiction, v2 explicitly shows the **three target platforms (Consul, DebateGraph, dembrane)** and the **mobile app** as interaction endpoints, alongside the pilot data streams (Greek, Italian, German, International). This makes it clear that the toolkit is designed to be integrated across heterogeneous environments with integration happening through APIs.
- **Data Preprocessing Layer (data readiness).** Before any AI processing, v2 makes preprocessing a distinct layer that prepares pilot data for safe and consistent use across pilots. It includes **data standardisation, data routing, multi-pilot interoperability, and data anonymisation (privacy by design)**. This layer formalises the “readiness gates” needed to ensure that the intelligence layer receives clean, structured, and policy-compliant inputs (especially important in multilingual, public-sector contexts).
- **Intelligence Layer (sandbox execution).** The intelligence layer hosts the **sandbox**, where the WP4 AI toolkit is integrated and exposed via a **Unified API**. In v2, the

sandbox is represented not only as a set of AI services (e.g., **summarisation, moderation & safety, argument mining, translation, topic categorisation/clustering, transcription, semantic KG, and video understanding**) but also as the place where **Knowledge Graph procedures** are operationalised. The inclusion of Knowledge Graph functionality directly inside the intelligence layer clarifies that the KG is not an “external repository” but a core operational component that interacts with AI services and outputs.

- **Compliance Layer (enveloping governance).** The most important structural refinement in v2 is that the **Compliance Layer explicitly encompasses all layers**, rather than being shown as a separate block next to the pipeline. This makes compliance an architectural property of the full system, with relevant compliance and privacy frameworks being followed throughout the data flow and procedures. Figure 34 expands compliance to include: **GDPR, the AI Act, and FAIR principles** (for the Knowledge Graph), and it explicitly embeds **ethics-by-design** through the **HLEG principles** (e.g., human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity and non-discrimination, societal well-being, accountability). Logging is also represented more concretely (timestamp, query, action/tool used, response), reinforcing traceability and auditability.

Two additional refinements strengthen operational readiness. First, **User Consent** is now explicitly shown as part of the interaction side of the architecture, clarifying that data use and AI-supported features must be anchored in informed participation and appropriate permissions. Second, the **Session Manager** is shown as a shared orchestration function underpinning the interaction and intelligence sides—signalling that calls to the toolkit services are handled in a controlled way (session handling, continuity of requests, and consistent execution across platforms and pilots).

Rationale for the changes from v1 to v2. While v1 already introduced the layered flow (data → preprocessing → sandbox → compliance → interfaces), v2 refines it into a clearer deployment blueprint: (i) it makes the **platform integration targets explicit** (including the mobile app), (ii) it strengthens the **operational role of preprocessing** as the bridge between heterogeneous pilots and shared services, (iii) it clarifies that **KG procedures are executed within the intelligence layer**, and (iv) it upgrades compliance from a “component” to an **end-to-end envelope** aligned with GDPR, AI Act and FAIR, grounded in ethics-by-design. Overall, v2 better communicates how WP4’s modular services can be safely reused across different deliberation environments while maintaining accountability, transparency, and trustworthiness throughout the full data flow. Lastly, Frankly is treated as an external integration path via dembrane, which is why it is not initially mapped in the Architecture.

6.2.2 Data Flow Architecture

Figure 35 presents the Data Flow Architecture, which complements the layered view of Figure 34 by making explicit how data physically moves from pilot sources to the shared AI Toolkit. Where Figure 34 describes *what* the system contains and how its layers relate, Figure 35 describes *how* content travels through those layers in practice, and what processing takes place at each step.

Figure 35: Data Flow Architecture

6.2.2.1 Design choice: decentralised operation with no central data lake

The architecture adopts a decentralised model in which each pilot retains ownership and control of its data throughout the flow. No raw or processed citizen content is pooled into a centralised repository. This is a design decision motivated by the legal and operational heterogeneity of the participating contexts: pilots operate under different national legal frameworks, involve different platform operators, and serve communities with different expectations around data sovereignty. By keeping data handling local until it is needed for AI processing, the architecture minimises cross-border data exposure, supports GDPR compliance at the point of collection, and avoids creating a shared liability surface that would be difficult to govern uniformly across the consortium.

This approach reflects the constraints and requirements of the current sprint as having been identified so far. Should future pilot needs, platform capabilities, or tool development require persistent intermediate storage, the architecture is designed to accommodate a transition to a more centralised or hybrid data model without restructuring its core components.

6.2.2.2 Pilot data flow

Each pilot follows the same local sequence before any content reaches shared infrastructure. It has been suggested that raw data is first passed through an anonymisation and data compliance step, which enforces the pilot's specific legal and ethical requirements. Additionally, each pilot may make use of AI tools that are not hosted in the shared toolkit (ECHO tools in the Italian context, Consul tools in the German context, or DebateGraph tools in the International pilot). These locally-operated tools serve integration purposes specific to

each platform. Only once local processing and compliance checks are complete does content move downstream into the shared infrastructure.

6.2.2.3 Shared infrastructure flow

The shared infrastructure receives content from all pilots through a Data Ingestion and Post-processing stage, which normalises and prepares inputs from heterogeneous sources for consistent AI processing, directly corresponding to the Data Preprocessing Layer described in Section 6.2. Processed data at this stage is treated as *non-persistent* in the current design: it is held only for the duration of the AI processing cycle and is not retained in any intermediate store. This is a further privacy-by-design measure, ensuring that the shared infrastructure does not accumulate citizen-generated content beyond what is operationally necessary. Should future requirements present the need for retaining processed data beyond the processing cycle, a corresponding reassessment of the compliance and governance framework governing this layer would take place, in order to transition to a more hybrid model.

Metadata and operational records related to AI usage (e.g., for logging, auditability, and session management) are retained in a structured and governed form, consistent with the Compliance Layer requirements described in Section 6.2.1. The processed content then passes to the AI Toolkit, which is implemented as a set of independently deployable containers, each hosting a distinct capability (e.g., summarisation, topic extraction, argument mining), and exposed to platforms via the Unified API.

6.2.2.4 Relation to the layered architecture

The Data Flow Architecture does not introduce new components; it provides the operational reading of the v2 architecture. The per-pilot anonymisation step corresponds to the privacy-by-design function within the Data Preprocessing Layer. The shared ingestion stage operationalises the bridge between that preprocessing layer and the Intelligence Layer. The non-persistent processed data model reflects the compliance requirement that personal data is not retained beyond necessity. The containerised AI Toolkit is the concrete deployment form of the sandbox services. Together, Figure 34 and Figure 35 should be read as complementary views of the same architecture: one structural and one operational.

6.3 Correlation with the Knowledge Graph and the AI toolkit

The Reference Architecture is the *technical bridge* that connects (i) the **AI toolkit** developed and exposed through the sandbox and (ii) the **Deliberation Knowledge Graph (DKG)**, ensuring that both evolve as interoperable building blocks rather than as standalone technical outputs. In practice, the architecture defines *where* each capability runs (preprocessing, sandbox services, KG procedures), *how* components exchange data (Unified API and ingestion flow), and *under which safeguards* they operate (compliance, consent, logging).

How the architecture enables the AI toolkit to feed and operationalise the Knowledge Graph

Across both v1 and v2, deliberation content originating from the pilots is first handled through the **data preprocessing layer** (standardisation, routing, multi-pilot interoperability, and anonymisation/privacy-by-design). This is a prerequisite for Knowledge Graph population, because it ensures that inputs are consistent and governed before any semantic structuring

takes place. In the **intelligence layer**, the toolkit services (e.g., argument mining, summarisation, topic clustering, transcription/translation) can produce structured outputs that are directly usable for **semantic representation** and downstream graph insertion (e.g., linking issues/positions/arguments and attaching provenance). In v2 (Figure 34), this relationship is made explicit by placing **Knowledge Graph procedures inside the intelligence layer**, alongside the toolkit services—signalling that KG construction and update are part of the operational pipeline and not an external, disconnected repository.

How the Knowledge Graph strengthens the toolkit and its outputs.

The Knowledge Graph is not only a “storage layer”; it becomes a **shared structured backbone** that can improve the quality, traceability, and reuse of AI services. First, it supports **grounded outputs** by enabling services (and the project’s RAG layer) to retrieve relevant structured context rather than relying solely on open-ended generation. Second, it improves **explainability and argumentative traceability** by maintaining links between structured nodes (e.g., issues/positions/arguments) and the original deliberation sources, which is critical for administrator-facing “insights” and for accountable use in policy settings. Third, the KG provides a stable semantic target that makes tool outputs more interoperable across platforms and pilots: even if different tools are used for the same function, their results can converge into a common semantic representation and become comparable and reusable across contexts.

Architectural mechanisms that support both assets jointly

Three architectural elements are particularly important for the co-development of the toolkit and the KG:

- **Unified API / Integration component:** it provides stable interfaces for platform plugins and enables the sandbox to expose both AI services and KG-related operations in a controlled way, supporting modular replacement of tools without breaking integration contracts.
- **Session management and “insights” outputs:** these ensure that toolkit execution (and, where relevant, KG write/read operations) is handled as a controlled workflow and that results are delivered as actionable, role-appropriate outputs (e.g., for host dashboards vs participant-facing features).
- **Compliance envelope (v2):** by explicitly defining compliance as a layer that encompasses all layers/technical components (including FAIR principles for the KG and GDPR/AI Act considerations, plus logging), instead of a separate technical component, the architecture ensures that compliance is treated as a principle; KG population and toolkit execution follow the same governance and traceability standards end-to-end.

Overall, the architecture operationalises a virtuous cycle: the **toolkit services** transform pilot deliberation data into structured outputs that can populate and enrich the **Knowledge Graph**, while the **Knowledge Graph** provides structured, traceable context that can improve the robustness, transparency, and reuse of the toolkit services across pilots and platforms.

6.4 Ethics

An overarching principle of the AI4Deliberation Reference Architecture is ensuring compliance with relevant EU legislation, most notably the AI Act, GDPR and national legislation in these fields, as well as various non-binding instruments for AI development and research, such as guidelines, white papers, principles and policies.¹⁷

With regard to GDPR the most prevalent issues with the processing of personal data of research participants involved in the four pilots, survey and observation studies concern the lawful basis (specifically consent), data minimisation and safe storage, the processing of special categories of personal data, secondary use of previously collected personal data for the purposes of the AI4Deliberation project and the transfer of personal data to/from non-EU countries.¹⁸

The EU AI Act includes several provisions relevant for the development and deployment of AI tools, most notably ensuring accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity (Art. 15), transparency obligations (Art. 50), maintaining accurate and up-to-date documentation (Art. 53), data governance (Art. 10), as well as post-deployment monitoring duties and human oversight.

AI tools which were chosen to be deployed in pilot trials were assessed against the HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. The latter are non-binding guidelines designed to ensure AI systems are developed and used in ways that are lawful, ethical, and robust. They were drafted by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), an independent expert group set up by the European Commission in April 2019 to provide a foundational ethical framework for AI in Europe. The guidelines identify seven key principles that embody the concept of trustworthy AI: human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, privacy and data governance, transparency, diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, societal and environmental well-being, and accountability. The guidelines also include practical tools, such as the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI), to help developers and deployers operationalise the ethical requirements. In exercising their role as Ethics Manager, the Institute of Criminology chose the HLEG guidelines as one of the main methodological tools in assessing the ethics compliance and fitness-for-purpose of selected AI tools, which were extensively assessed against the principles therein (see Deliverable D2.1)¹⁹. All activities implemented were in accordance with sprint Methodology from the Technical Annex and based on the information collected from T1.3: Product backlog.

An additional element of the compliance layer comprises FAIR principles research data management in EU Horizon (and Horizon Europe) projects. The initials stand for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable research outputs, which should be properly described with metadata, assigned persistent identifiers (such as DOIs), and deposited in trusted repositories. It should be noted, that accessibility does not necessarily mean open access, but data must be retrievable under clearly defined conditions, including authentication and authorisation where needed. In Horizon Europe projects, beneficiaries are expected to prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) outlining how data will be handled in line with FAIR

¹⁷ For a complete list of relevant legal instruments see Deliverable 2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects, Chapter 5.4.

¹⁸ For a detailed approach to the processing of personal data within the AI4Deliberation project see Deliverable 2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects, Chapter 3, and Data Protection Impact Assessment (Annex 13).

¹⁹ For a complete analysis of the results see Deliverable 2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects, Chapter 5

principles throughout the project lifecycle. The implementation of FAIR principles supports transparency, reproducibility, and long-term impact of EU-funded research, aligning with the broader Open Science policy of the European Commission.

6.4.1 AI tools Ethics Assessment²⁰

Groups of AI tools selected for pilot deployment were assessed against the HLEG Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. The following groups of AI tools were assessed.

6.4.1.1 Large Language Models (LLMs)

The assessed foundational language models are used as core engines for specialised AI tools supporting deliberation processes. They differ structurally in governance regime: some operate under proprietary, while others follow open-source or open-weight approaches, shifting responsibility for ethics and legal compliance to downstream deployers. The assessment evaluates alignment with HLEG's principles for trustworthy AI, especially in light of their application in democratic processes, where risks to fundamental rights are amplified. The evaluation focuses on identifying systemic risks such as automation bias, overreliance, hallucinations, oversimplification, misuse, and manipulation, and includes proposals for effective mitigation methods.

Across the evaluated models, proprietary models generally embed built-in safety and transparency features, which support user protection. Open models provide greater flexibility but require deployers to actively implement safeguards. Thus, alignment with agency and oversight depends heavily on governance design and deployment practices. LLMs offer powerful capabilities for democratic deliberation support, including summarisation, translation, and multimodal interaction. However, identified risks related to bias, opacity, privacy, and human autonomy remain significant. Trustworthiness depends not only on model choice alone, but significantly on governance architecture, safety calibration, transparency practices, and human oversight mechanisms.

6.4.1.2 Specialised AI tools for deliberative processes

AI tools, which can support deliberative processes through specialised functionalities, were clustered into the following categories:

- Argument mining & deliberation tools
- Moderation & safety tools
- Translation & accessibility tools
- Gamification & engagement tools

Argument Mining and Deliberation Tools analyse argumentative structures, discussion patterns, and conversational dynamics. Unlike LLMs, they are typically research-oriented and human-supervised by design, and enable some traceability of reasoning steps adding to the transparency of the model's outputs. When these models are built on public datasets, privacy

²⁰ For a complete evaluation see Deliverable 2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects, Chapter 5.

risks are less prominent. Overall, the analysed models seemed robust and fit-for-purpose, but may require some fairness evaluation.²¹

Moderation and Safety Tools classify and/or flag harmful content. They are explicitly designed for human-assisted moderation, not full automation, meaning the final decision should be made by a human reviewer, to avoid more subtle or nuanced breaches as well as potential false positives and over-blocking. Open-source models increase the auditability of the tools, but trustworthiness still depends heavily on deployer practices. These tools can effectively identify and help reduce harassment, but must be subject to human oversight.

Translation and Accessibility Tools feature automatic speech recognition and translation, with the aim to expand accessibility and multilingual inclusion. One of the more prominent risks is the English-centric training bias, as well as gender bias. These tools align well with privacy and transparency principles, but fairness for lower-resource languages remains a key concern.

Gamification & Engagement Tools apply points, badges, and incentives to increase participation through a more user-oriented experience. These systems can be prone to subtle manipulation or coercion, and enhance social comparison pressures, but can support not only civic engagement, but also authentic learning.²²

Across all categories, the ethics assessment showed that human agency and oversight are most supported when there is an active human moderator in the loop, fairness and diversity must be addressed systemically by deployers due to biased training data, and societal and environmental impacts are under-documented in most cases.

6.5 Compliance with methods

The WP4 Reference Architecture has been developed in line with the project's methodological commitments and working practices, ensuring that architectural decisions are (i) **requirements-driven**, (ii) **iteratively validated through the sprint cycle**, and (iii) **ethics- and compliance-aware by design**. In particular, the architecture is explicitly grounded in the **functional and non-functional requirements, user roles, and user stories identified in WP1**, and follows a modular approach to enable interoperability and "smooth pipelining" of information across models and services.

Requirements-driven design (functional and non-functional). WP1 elicits stakeholder needs and categorises them as **functional and non-functional**, using agile documentation practices (epics, user stories, and a project product backlog). These artefacts are directly reflected in WP4's architectural choices, such as (a) the use of a unified, service-based interface (APIs) to support diverse platform needs, (b) the separation of concerns into layers (interaction, preprocessing, intelligence/sandbox, compliance) to address heterogeneous deployment constraints, and (c) explicit support for cross-pilot interoperability and multi-language operation.

WP2 identifies "layered and networked architectures" as a key scaling strategy to connect small-group or local deliberative moments with system-level synthesis, feedback loops, and institutional outputs, while preserving local authenticity and collective legitimacy. The WP4 Reference Architecture follows this logic by separating interaction, preprocessing,

²¹ For more information, you can refer to Deliverable 2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects.

²² For a complete evaluation see Deliverable 2.1 Legal and Ethics Aspects, Chapter 5.

intelligence/services, and compliance functions so that deliberation data can move through a controlled pipeline (with traceability, validation, and governance checks) while enabling synthesis and structured outputs to be returned to platforms and facilitators in usable forms.

Table 4: WP2 correlation with WP4, methods-to-technology

WP2 design driver	What WP4 provides
Quality vs size tension (large volumes reduce interaction quality)	Summarisation, clustering/topic extraction, argument/structure extraction services to support scalable sense-making and synthesis; structured outputs for facilitator/admin use.
Community vs anonymity tension (weak social cues in async settings)	Moderation & safety services + human-in-the-loop workflows; governance patterns that keep humans responsible for interpretation and final decisions.
Diversity vs depth (breadth increases but reflection can drop)	Multimodal/accessibility services; layered summaries; options to preserve disagreement and minority reasoning rather than collapsing to a single narrative.
Consequentiality vs engagement (low perceived impact reduces motivation)	Gamification mechanisms calibrated for deliberation (badges/progress/reputation etc.), explicitly constrained to avoid over-competition and participation inequality effects.
AI framing/opacity risk (silent algorithmic choices)	Traceability/grounding priorities; prompt test suite as a repeatable control mechanism; documentation of when/why AI intervenes.
Human–AI collaboration boundary (avoid over-automation)	Opt-in/triggered use patterns, facilitator review, and validation loops; explicit separation between AI assistance and human judgement.

Agile, sprint-based iteration and evaluation loop. The architecture evolves through the project’s four mega-sprints, where each sprint refines previous work and adds features as confidence increases. Within this approach, Sprint 1 focuses on building the socio-technical “infrastructure” and testing it internally (consortium members only), while Sprint 2 produces the artefacts needed for pilots to start small-scale citizen-facing operation. In WP4 terms, this is operationalised as **Architecture v1** (T4.1 baseline) and **Architecture v2** (T4.2 refined blueprint), where refinements are informed by sprint evaluation outputs (WP5) and the technical evidence gathered through sandbox testing.

Open, transparent co-creation alignment. The project methodology explicitly commits to open, transparent and deliberative co-creation practices for key artefacts. WP4 aligns with this by keeping the architecture modular and reusable (so it can be instantiated across pilots and reused beyond them), and by structuring core assets (toolkit services, KG procedures,

integration interfaces) in a way that supports partner contributions and incremental integration without redesigning the whole system.

Ethics-by-design and privacy-by-design embedded in the architecture. The overall project methodology requires that legal and ethical aspects (including consent procedures and GDPR-compliant data processing planning such as DPIAs) are integrated across all phases of platform setup and operation, explicitly following ethics-by-design and privacy-by-design principles. Consistent with this, WP4's architecture includes privacy-preserving data handling (e.g., anonymisation in preprocessing), operational accountability mechanisms (logging and traceability), and governance safeguards across the pipeline. It also aligns with EU regulatory and policy expectations by considering GDPR, AI Act-relevant obligations (e.g., robustness/cybersecurity, transparency, documentation, human oversight), Trustworthy AI principles (HLEG), and FAIR-oriented data management for the Knowledge Graph.

In summary, the Reference Architecture is “method-compliant” because it translates the project's requirements engineering (epics/user stories and non-functional constraints), sprint-based development and evaluation, co-creation principles, and ethics/compliance commitments into concrete technical structures—resulting in a reusable, modular blueprint that can be validated and refined across pilots under controlled and progressively more realistic conditions.

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7. Conclusions and next steps

7.1 Summary of accomplishments

D4.1 consolidates the first two WP4 sprints (T4.1 and T4.2) into a coherent set of technical results that establish AI4Deliberation’s core technical foundation: an **AI toolkit and sandbox**, a **Deliberation Knowledge Graph**, and a **reusable Reference Architecture** designed for integration into heterogeneous deliberation platforms. Across these sprints, WP4 progressed from a requirements-driven tool identification and evaluation phase to the implementation of concrete, pilot-relevant services and early platform integration artefacts, while embedding cross-cutting safeguards (privacy, security, explainability, trustworthiness) and aligning developments with the project’s ethics-by-design approach.

A first core accomplishment is the **structured, consortium-wide methodology for tool selection and refinement**, which ensured that WP4 developments are traceable to deliberation needs rather than technology availability alone. Tool identification started from the functionalities derived from WP1 and the deliberation-method analysis, and followed a transparent pipeline: requirements-to-functionality mapping, tool scouting and long-listing, evaluation through a shared questionnaire, three-tier ranking, and collective validation by partners. The process explicitly adopted risk-mitigation principles (e.g., selecting more than one candidate per functionality when feasible) and introduced down-selection decisions based on Sprint 1 evaluation evidence, prioritising tools and configurations that are integration-ready and usable under pilot constraints (language, modality, governance).

A second accomplishment is the establishment of the **WP4 sandbox as an experimentation and validation environment** for AI-enhanced deliberation. The sandbox operationalises the project’s intention to test AI capabilities in a controlled setting before citizen-facing deployment, and it supports (i) experimentation with deliberation functionalities (e.g., summarisation, moderation and safety, translation, argument extraction and clustering), (ii) experimentation with gamification mechanisms, and (iii) clarification of pilot-specific infrastructure needs based on observed model behaviour. A key component of this sandbox-based approach is the **prompt engineering test suite**, which enables consistent model evaluation and comparison and provides the evidence base for deciding whether refinement through prompting, pipeline changes, or fine-tuning is required.

A third major accomplishment is the delivery of **concrete AI services and pipelines** aligned with deliberation settings and modalities. During Sprints 1 and 2, the consortium developed parallel services for core deliberation support features—**summarisation, argument extraction, moderation, and translation**—recognising that deliberation contexts differ substantially across pilots and that no single pipeline is universally optimal. For example, summarisation work evolved into complementary approaches: (i) structured summarisation for public consultation comments (categorised outputs and clustering + LLM synthesis) and (ii) facilitator-oriented narrative summarisation for spoken dialogue, designed for “glanceability” and rapid sense-making in live sessions. Similarly, argument extraction progressed into both a formal, IBIS-aligned pipeline (suitable for structured reporting and Knowledge Graph population) and conversational analysis styles that support facilitator exploration, reflecting different user needs (administrative analytics vs. live facilitation).

A fourth accomplishment is the translation of these services into **pilot-oriented integration artefacts**, demonstrating the feasibility of the project’s API-based integration approach across platforms. In the Greek pilot context, WP4 developed a WordPress-based integration host and implemented three concrete plugins—moderation, summarisation, and argument extraction—connecting WordPress workflows to WP4 backend pipelines and enabling administrators (and, where relevant, participants) to access structured outputs through the platform. This includes a clear human-in-the-loop moderation workflow (labels stored with comments, final approval by human moderators) and pilot-ready interfaces for summary generation and argument extraction (including clustering and frontend presentation). In parallel, the International pilot integration approach was specified as lightweight but concrete: argument-mining outputs will be converted to DebateGraph-compatible formats and posted via the DebateGraph JSON API, supported by a simple web frontend to allow users to access the tools without direct API use. For the Italian pilot, the dembrane platform provides an audio-first deliberation environment and contributes its own analysis capabilities, while also serving as the bridge for processing online video deliberation data from Frankly through the same analysis pipeline—demonstrating that WP4 services can operate across text, audio, and video modalities via a consistent integration logic. Collectively, these integration strands validate the project’s core ambition: WP4 AI services can be embedded into different deliberation environments without requiring adoption of a single platform.

A fifth accomplishment is the development of the **Deliberation Knowledge Graph (DKG) foundations**, including its semantic model, FAIR-oriented implementation direction, and integration logic with WP4 services. The DKG is structured around a dual-layer semantic model that combines an ontological blueprint (community structure + rhetorical logic + provenance vocabularies) with FAIR data governance principles, enabling deliberation data to be represented as structured, reusable knowledge rather than only stored as raw content. The IBIS framework is adopted as the core “logical grammar” for structuring issues, positions, and arguments (pro/con) supporting traceability and enabling downstream reasoning and analytics. The population strategy is defined through a standardised ETL approach combining pilot data ingestion with argumentative corpora, and explicitly foresees using WP4’s argument extraction tools (LLM-based extraction and oAMF) to generate structured inputs for Knowledge Graph population.

A sixth accomplishment is the introduction of the **Multi-Agent RAG layer (Cognitive Retrieval)** as a neurosymbolic bridge between user questions and structured Knowledge Graph queries. This layer is designed to translate natural language questions into validated SPARQL queries, enforce safety and compliance checks (including protection against prompt injection and destructive queries), and synthesise evidence-based responses that preserve argumentative transparency by explicitly referencing the IBIS structure. This strengthens the project’s ability to make structured deliberation knowledge accessible to non-technical users (citizens, policymakers, hosts) while retaining security and traceability controls.

A seventh accomplishment is the delivery of the **Reference Architecture v1 and its refinement to v2**, which translates the Technical Annex vision into an implementation-facing, layered blueprint for deployment and reuse. The refined architecture clarifies the operational roles of the Interaction, Data Preprocessing, Intelligence (sandbox + KG procedures), and Compliance layers, and strengthens the end-to-end governance framing by positioning the compliance layer as an envelope encompassing the full pipeline (including GDPR, AI Act considerations, and FAIR principles). It also makes explicit the architectural mechanisms that connect toolkit

and KG (Unified API, session management, insights outputs) and formalises the “virtuous cycle” whereby toolkit services generate structured outputs that populate the Knowledge Graph, and the Knowledge Graph provides traceable context that improves the robustness and reuse of toolkit services.

Finally, WP4 achieved meaningful progress on **gamification experimentation** as required by the Grant Agreement, positioning gamification as a mechanism to support participation and deliberation quality rather than as a purely competitive layer. The deliverable defines concrete gamification elements (e.g., levels, badges, leaderboards, voting/reputation mechanisms) and highlights controlled experimentation through the sandbox, including an early WordPress-based gamification plugin example for the Greek context. This establishes the basis for evidence-driven adaptation of gamification mechanics and metrics as further pilot feedback is collected in subsequent sprints.

7.2 WP4 KPIs and progress status

The Grant Agreement defines a set of KPIs for WP4 covering the AI toolkit (AI features exposed through APIs), multimodality, supported languages/functionalities, the modular argument mining framework, the Reference Architecture, the Deliberation Knowledge Graph scale, platform enhancement and gamification, the uptake of AI services by additional platforms, and the delivery of a mobile application. Based on the work completed in **T4.1–T4.2** and reported in this deliverable, WP4 is already progressing against several of these KPIs, while others are explicitly scheduled for completion in **T4.3–T4.4** as integrations mature and pilot data increases.

KPIs already being addressed in T4.1–T4.2 (reported in D4.1)

WP4 has established the core foundations required to meet the toolkit and architecture KPIs: the **Reference Architecture (v1 and refined v2)** is delivered and iterated through the sprint cycle; the **sandbox/toolkit approach** is implemented and used to evaluate and refine tools; and multiple AI functionalities are already implemented and tested (e.g., summarisation, moderation/safety, translation, argument extraction, topic modelling, and early gamification integration). In parallel, WP4 has initiated platform-facing integration through pilot-specific approaches (e.g., API-driven integration patterns and early plugin-based integration in the Greek context), which is the prerequisite for counting AI features as “available through an API” at scale.

KPIs that will be consolidated and counted in T4.3 (next sprint)

The next sprint focuses on moving from validated components to a **first complete toolkit release**, which is the stage at which the project can systematically count and report the number of **AI features available through APIs** and the number of **multimodal AI features** delivered. T4.3 is also the sprint where **platform enhancement** and broader reuse are strengthened through concrete APIs/plugins and expanded integration across platforms, supporting the KPI on the **number of platforms using the developed AI features**.

KPIs targeted for later sprints due to dependency on scale and pilot data (T4.3–T4.4)

Some KPIs depend on (i) the availability of sufficient pilot deliberation data over time and (ii) later-stage integration maturity. In particular, the target of **>1M triples in the Deliberation Knowledge Graph** is expected to be reached through progressive population as pilots operate at larger scale beyond the internal testing phase, combined with continued ingestion and

structuring pipelines. Similarly, the KPI on the **mobile application** is planned for delivery in the later sprints (T4.3/T4.4), alongside finalisation of the toolkit and platform enhancements, as foreseen in the GA sprint plan.

KPIs related to argument mining modules and gamification elements

WP4 has already evaluated and advanced argument extraction/argument mining pipelines (including a modular framework approach and tooling such as oAMF and LLM-based extraction). The KPI on the **number of argument mining modules** will be further consolidated as modules are stabilised, packaged, and integrated as reusable services in T4.3–T4.4. In addition, WP4 has begun implementing and testing gamification mechanisms (e.g., voting/reputation and broader gamification elements discussed in Chapter 4); the KPI on **gaming elements** will be iterated based on pilot feedback and refined metrics, with full validation and final selection expected as pilots progress.

Overall, D4.1 establishes the baseline architecture, sandbox, and validated service pipelines; the next sprints focus on scaling these into a complete API-exposed toolkit, increasing multimodal coverage and platform uptake, and growing the Knowledge Graph and mobile application towards their final KPI targets.

7.3 Next sprints and steps

Following the completion of D4.1 (first version), WP4 continues with **T4.3 “Develop AI Toolkit, Architecture, and Knowledge Graph – third sprint” (M19–M24)**, which aims to consolidate the work of the first two sprints into a **first complete version of the AI toolkit and the Knowledge Graph**, ready to support the next pilot cycle.

In line with the Grant Agreement, the main next steps for **T4.3** are:

- **Consolidation of the AI toolkit and Knowledge Graph into a first complete release.** The toolkit and KG will be extended and stabilised based on the **results of the second pilot evaluation (T5.4)**, applying refinements similar to those in T4.2 where needed (e.g., additional fine-tuning, explainability/transparency/trustworthiness techniques, further gamification iteration, and additional KG population from pilot deliberations).
- **Expansion of KG data population from pilot deliberations.** T4.3 explicitly foresees adding further data from pilot operation into the Knowledge Graph, strengthening its role as a structured backbone for deliberation services.
- **APIs and plugins for platform integration.** A key T4.3 output is the development of **APIs and plugins** to integrate the AI toolkit functionality and gamification elements into one or more deliberation platforms (examples in the GA include **Consul** and **DebateGraph**).
- **First version of the mobile app.** T4.3 includes the development of a **first version of a mobile app**, supporting **conversational video-based exploration of deliberation content**, which operationalises the project’s multimodal citizen-facing vision.
- **Updated Reference Architecture including API integration.** The Reference Architecture will be updated again in this sprint to reflect the concrete integration artefacts (APIs/plugins) and the expanded operational setup; this release is planned to be aligned with **T2.4** and **T3.3**.

Finally, the outputs of T4.3 will be used to feed **Sprint 3 pilot backlog** (internal report), ensuring that the next pilot cycle is driven by the validated technical release. After T4.3, WP4 proceeds to **T4.4 (M25–M33)** for full technical support and final refinements, culminating in **D4.2 (final version)**.

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Annexes

A. Questionnaire for tool selection/evaluation

Each partner completed the following template per AI tool reviewed.

Criteria	Response
Tool Name	
Type (e.g., LLM, multimodal, classifier)	
Open-source?	Yes / No
Targeted Functionality	E.g., summarisation, argument extraction
Licensing/Usage Constraints	
Input Type	Text / Video / Audio
Output Type	Summary / Scores / Clusters
Usability / Documentation	Rate 1–5 with comments
Model Performance (if known)	
Ethical / Privacy Considerations	E.g., explainability, data sensitivity
Strengths	
Limitations	
Overall Suitability for WP4	Yes / No – Please explain

Optional: Include any screenshots, early test results, or data performance notes as appendices or in a zipped folder with your submission.

The results were combined and analysed, and based on this approach the tools were selected.

B. Product backlog

The **Product Backlog** is a WP1 output developed under **Task T1.3** as an internal, requirements-to-implementation planning instrument for AI4Deliberation. It consolidates the project's priorities into a structured list of **Epics** and **User Stories**, describing what capabilities the AI-enhanced deliberation toolkit should provide, what concrete actions/tools should be able to perform, and when/where these capabilities are planned to be implemented across pilots and sprints. In WP4, the backlog is used as a traceability mechanism: it helps ensure that tool selection, sandbox experimentation and integration work are driven by deliberation needs and pilot priorities rather than by technology availability alone.

The detailed backlog template is organised into the following columns:

- **Epic:** a high-level capability area (e.g., Summarisation, Moderation, Multilingual Accessibility, Argument mining and clustering, Gamification, Topic Extraction, Ethics, Platform Architecture).
- **Topic:** the functional or non functional category under which related user stories are grouped.
- **User Story:** a uniquely identified requirement (e.g., US1.2) that expresses a specific capability the system should support. The initial User Stories can be found in D1.1: Demystify digital Deliberative Processes while the new user stories produced during the sprints are accompanying the detailed Product Backlog.
- **Description:** a short, action-oriented statement of what the functionality should do (the “expected behaviour” of the tool/service).
- **Dependencies:** the correlation and dependency of the User Stories.
- **Input from:** the source that the User Story or Description emerged from.
- **Target Sprint / Pilot:** the planned delivery window and/or pilot context in which the user story is expected to be implemented or tested (e.g., Sprint 1, Sprint 2, Greek, German, Italian, and International pilot).

The Product Backlog is a **living document**: it is continuously updated as new evidence emerges from technical developments, pilot preparation, internal evaluation, and sprint feedback (e.g., tool performance results, integration constraints, ethics/compliance requirements, and stakeholder input). For this reason, the version included in this deliverable is provided as a snapshot used during the D4.1 reporting period, and it should be read as an evolving planning artefact that supports agile development and refinement rather than a fixed specification. This version only includes the relevant technical development of Topics during the 1st and 2nd Sprint of WP4. The detailed version of the Product backlog includes more information and connection between WPs. Based on the feedback from Sprint 2 of the pilot evaluation, fine tuning of the tools and missing or additional functionalities will be implemented.

New User Stories are produced along the way based on new needs. Some examples are the following:

US25.1	As a pilot owner I want to have a copy of the original WordPress in order to be able to experiment and conduct pilots in it.
US25.2	As a pilot owner, I want the site to be populated with initial content before launch so that pilot users can fully experience the platform.
US25.3	As a pilot owner, I want the summarisation service integrated to the pilot website so that pilot users can use this feature.
US25.4	As a pilot owner, I want the translation service integrated to the pilot website so that pilot users can use this feature.
US25.5	As a pilot owner, I want the moderation service integrated to the pilot website so that pilot users can use this feature.
US27.1	As a project owner, I want to transform unstructured consultation data into a Semantic Knowledge Graph to enable advanced querying and interoperability.
US27.2	As a user, I want to interact with deliberation data using natural language queries that are translated into SPARQL.
US27.3	As a data architect, I want to define the graph schema using SIOC, FOAF, and DCTERMS standards to ensure adherence to FAIR principles.
US27.4	As a user, I want to filter discussions not just by keyword, but by specific metadata like the creating Ministry, the date, or the type of participant.
US27.5	As a policy maker, I want to analyse engagement patterns across different ministries and years so that I can understand which legislative topics generate the most civic interest.

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Epic	Topic	User Story	Description	Dependencies	Input from
E1	Summarisation	US1.1	Automatically identify and extract key information from discussions.		Backlog v1
		US1.2	Generate a clear and concise text summary of a discussion.	US1.1	Backlog v1
		US1.3	Generate an audio version of the summary.	US1.2	Backlog v1
E2	Moderation	US2.1	Suggest discussion rules and flag inappropriate content.	US19.1	Backlog v1
		US2.2	Guide the conversation for inclusiveness.	US2.1	Backlog v1
		US2.3	(Human) report, flag, and review inappropriate content.		Backlog v1
		US2.4	(Human) delete, approve, and categorize posts.	US2.3	Backlog v1
		US2.5	Acknowledge positive behaviour (e.g., 'Thanks').		Backlog v1
		US2.6	Offer structured sessions to co-set discussion rules.	US2.1	Backlog v1
E3	Fact-Checking	US3.1	Identify factual claims and provide verified info.	US19.1	Backlog v1
		US3.2	Flag potentially misleading content.	US3.1	Backlog v1
		US3.3	Provide evidence-based explanations for misleading content.	US3.1, US3.2	Backlog v1
		US3.4	Access shared repository of trusted sources.	US3.1	Backlog v1
E4	Multilingual & Language Accessibility	US4.1	Translate discussion content automatically.	US19.1	Backlog v1
		US4.2	Translate audio/video to sign language	US4.1, US10.2, US10.3	Backlog v1
		US4.3	Simplify language.		Backlog v1
		US19.7	Support multicultural and regional adaptability.		Backlog v1

E5	Argument mining and clustering	US17.1	Extract and classify arguments from discussions.		Backlog v1
		US5.1	Cluster similar arguments and identify consensus.	US17.1, US1.1	Backlog v1
		US23.1	Extract well-formed and accurate IBIS / argument nodes, relationships and maps from relevant policy documents and discussions	US17.1	Technical WP + Pilot WP
E6	Gamification	US24.1	Gamification to promote thoughtful participation.		Backlog v1
		US6.1	Recognise meaningful contributions.	US24.1	Backlog v1
		US6.2	Include gamified incentives (e.g., badges).	US6.1, US24.1	Backlog v1
		US6.3	Gamified onboarding process to establish shared norms.	US6.1, US24.1	Backlog v1
E7	Suggesting Alternative Perspectives	US7.1	Suggest alternative viewpoints.		Backlog v1
		US7.2	Provide credible sources for alternative views.	US7.1	Backlog v1
E9	Discussion Analytics & Topic Extraction	US9.1	Analyse discussion patterns.	US25.1, US25.2	Backlog v1
		US9.2	Recommend topics based on interests.	US9.1	Backlog v1
		US9.3	Group content and contributions by themes.	US9.1	Backlog v1
		US25.1	Extract topics from discussion contributions on demand, (zero-shot or embedding-based classification without requiring pre-built taxonomy or corpus)	US19.1	Technical WP
		US25.2	Extract topics from discussion contributions in their native language, without requiring translation first	US19.1	Technical WP
		US25.3	Normalize extracted topics against a structured taxonomy, mapping free-form language to controlled vocabulary.	US25.2	Technical WP
		US25.4	Support both GPU-accelerated (LLM) and CPU-only (embedding) backends, with automatic fallback between them.	US25.2, US25.3	Technical WP

		US25.5	Ingest deliberation datasets from external sources for topic analysis.	US25.2, US25.3	Technical WP
		US25.6	Allow for topic analysis re-run on existing content when models or taxonomy definitions are updated.	US25.3	Technical WP
		US25.7	Expose topic extraction as an API endpoint for integration with other platform components.	US25.1	Technical WP
E10	Participation Features	US8.4	Feedback on deliberation processes.	US8.1	Backlog v1
		US10.2	Join discussions using video.		Backlog v1
		US10.3	Join discussions using audio.		Backlog v1
		US10.6	Support synchronous formats like live chats or video events.	US10.2, US10.3	Backlog v1
		US10.7	Support asynchronous formats for deeper deliberation.		Backlog v1
		US10.8	Support various deliberative processes (e.g., debates, consultations, vote & justification, Q&A).	US10.7	Backlog v1
		US12.3	Submit content in multiple formats.		Backlog v1
E11	Ethics (Human agency and oversight, Technical Robustness and safety, Privacy and data governance, Transparency, Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, Societal and environmental well-being, Accountability)	US8.1	Analyse user feedback to identify improvements.		Backlog v1
		US8.2	(Human) Flag inaccurate AI-generated summaries.	US8.1, US22.2	Backlog v1
		US8.3	(Human) Suggest better translations for content.	US8.1, US22.2	Backlog v1
		US11.1	Explain AI actions to build trust.		Backlog v1
		US11.2	Log and publish significant AI interventions.	US11.1	Backlog v1
		US11.3	Provide explanations when content is flagged.	US11.1	Backlog v1
		US21.1	Explain all AI actions in simple terms.	US11.1	Backlog v1
		US21.2	Disclose platform ownership and policies.		Backlog v1

		US22.1	Include human oversight of AI outputs.		Backlog v1
		US22.2	Allow correction of AI errors.		Backlog v1
		US14.4	Request explicit consent for access to their device's microphone and camera.	US14.1	Backlog v1
		US18.1	Securely store and transmit user data.		Backlog v1
		US18.2	Secure data of users who use pseudonyms and avatars.	US18.1	Backlog v1
		US18.3	Provide clear data collection policies.	US18.1	Backlog v1
		US18.4	Comply with regulations like GDPR and AI Act.	US18.1	Backlog v1
		US18.5	Ensure responsible AI training and evaluation.	US18.1	Backlog v1
		US18.6	Exclude data from political/statistical exploitation.	US18.1	Backlog v1
		US18.7	Keep commercial activities separate.	US18.1	Backlog v1
E12	Analysis & Visualisation & Communication	US11.4	Highlight user contributions in update notes.	US8.1	Backlog v1
		US11.5	Periodic updates on discussion impact on policies.	US8.1	Backlog v1
		US12.1	Generate reports and data visualizations from discussions.		Backlog v1
		US12.2	Track metrics like civility and argument quality.		Backlog v1
		US23.2	Feed extracted IBIS / argument nodes, relationships and maps via JSON API to DebateGraph for visualisation	US17.1	Technical WP + Pilot WP
		US12.4	Track and analyse participation data using AI.		Backlog v1
		US12.6	Offer demographic surveys.		Backlog v1
E13		US12.5	Interaction with a chatbot.		Backlog v1
		US13.1	Send reminders and support scheduling.		Backlog v1

	Facilitation, Guidance & User Support	US13.2	Provide discussion topics and structured agendas.		Backlog v1
		US13.3	Offer note-taking and follow-up summaries.		Backlog v1
		US13.4	Provide AI reasoning tools to help users refine their arguments.		Backlog v1
		US13.5	Upload training material in various formats.		Backlog v1
		US20.9	Support outreach tools to include more people.		Backlog v1
E14	Identity, Access & Consent	US10.4	Choose a pseudonym instead of the real name.		Backlog v1
		US10.5	View content without logging in.		Backlog v1
		US14.1	Email/username registration.		Backlog v1
		US14.2	Register via government ID.	US14.1	Backlog v1
		US14.3	Enforce secure authentication.	US14.1	Backlog v1
		US14.5	Prevent multiple account creation.	US14.1	Backlog v1
		US15.1	Create and assign user roles.	US14.1	Backlog v1
		US20.7	Simple and accessible authentication.		Backlog v1
E16	Profiles, Personalisation & Discovery	US10.1	Upload an avatar or a photo for the user's profile.		Backlog v1
		US16.1	Remember user accessibility settings.		Backlog v1
		US16.2	Enable users to personalize profiles.	US16.1	Backlog v1
		US16.3	Provide advanced content discovery tools.	US16.2	Backlog v1
E19	Platform Architecture, Scalability & Interoperability	US19.1	AI tasks should work in real-time when needed.		Backlog v1
		US19.2	The system must support large-scale participation without performance degradation.		Backlog v1
		US19.3	Architecture should support updates.		Backlog v1

		US19.4	Comply with interoperability standards (e.g., DCAT-AP, CPSV-AP).		Backlog v1
		US19.5	Optimise for bandwidth and power efficiency.		Backlog v1
		US19.6	Integrate with external tools.		Backlog v1
		US20.5	Use standard APIs and protocols.		Backlog v1
		US20.6	Be open-source.		Backlog v1
		US20.8	Be hosted on scalable cloud services.		Backlog v1
E20	Usability, Accessibility & Cross-Platform Access	US20.1	Simple and intuitive interfaces.		Backlog v1
		US20.2	Comply with accessibility standards.		Backlog v1
		US20.3	Follow usability principles.		Backlog v1
		US20.4	Work across various devices (smartphones, tablets, pc) and OS (windows, mac os, android, ios).		Backlog v1
E21	Echo and Frankly integration	US21.1	Receive breakout room recordings from Frankly via HMAC-authenticated webhook endpoint		Technical WP
		US21.2	Extract audio from video files using ffmpeg; discard video after extraction	US21.1	Technical WP
		US21.3	Split audio into ~30s chunks and upload to dembrane via the Participant API	US21.2, US21.4, US21.5	Technical WP
		US21.4	Map Frankly event_ids to dembrane project_ids via operator-managed configuration		Technical WP
		US21.5	Bridge authenticates with dembrane as a dedicated service account; no participant PII crosses platform boundaries		Technical WP
E22	SandBox	US22.1	Deploy AI tools as independently deployable containers (where applicable)		Technical WP
		US22.3	Build a Unified API gateway routing all AI toolkit requests to the correct tool container	US22.1	Technical WP

		US22.4	Support API key auth (service-to-service) and JWT (user-facing) through the gateway	US22.3	Technical WP
E25	WordPress platform (opengov)	US25.1	WordPress site (development + hosting)		Technical WP + Pilot WP
		US25.2	Content Creation and population		Technical WP + Pilot WP
		US25.3	Summarisation Plugin and Integration	US1.1, US1.2, US1.3	Technical WP + Pilot WP
		US25.4	Translation Plug In and Integration	US4.1	Technical WP + Pilot WP
		US25.5	Moderation Plug In and Integration	US2.3, US2.4	Technical WP + Pilot WP
				US27.1	Structured Deliberation Data
E27	Knowledge Graph	US27.2	Interaction with Deliberation Data using Natural Language	US27.1	Technical WP
		US27.3	Semantic Ontology Design (T-Box)	US27.1	Technical WP
		US27.4	Simplified Multi-Criteria Search	US27.1, US27.2	Technical WP
		US27.5	Cross-Consultation Analysis	US27.1	Technical WP
				US29.1	Enable user input for custom process constraints and requirements
E29	Process Application (shinyapp)	US29.2	Recommend scalable process designs for deliberation		Deliberation Stages and Processes WP

	US29.3	Recommend tools to support scaled deliberation (AI, multimodal, gamification)		Deliberation Stages and Processes WP
	US29.4	Raise awareness for socio-technical risks		Deliberation Stages and Processes WP
	US29.5	Enable export of recommendations		Deliberation Stages and Processes WP

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